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We are excited to announce that *Babcock University Journal of Education* is accepting papers for its **Vol.10, Number 2** due for publication by **December 15, 2024**. The journal welcomes articles exploring any area of **Education and Humanities**.

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**INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AND LEARNING
TECHNIQUES IN POST COVID-19 ERA: CASE STUDY OF BABCOCK UNIVERSITY
STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT

This study's aim was to investigate the effect of ICT on learning activities among students of Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State in post COVID-19 era. Two research questions and one null hypothesis were formulated for the study.

The survey research method was used and a self-structured questionnaire which was administered to students in Babcock University served as the instrument. The population for the study consisted of 11,000 Babcock University students out of which 386 were picked as sample using stratified random sampling. The research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics while the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using multiple regression analysis.

It was revealed from the findings that the major learning techniques obtainable in Babcock University is taking down notes for future reading (\bar{x} = 3.42; St.D=.87). The students also prefer to see information written on the board, supplemented by assigned readings and visual aids (\bar{x} = 3.34; St.D= .85). They tend to remember things best when they write it down several times. The most available ICT tool being used in Babcock is Google Classroom (\bar{x} = 3.72; St.D= .67) and this is closely followed by Google Meet (\bar{x} = 3.34; St.D= .94). The result revealed a significant positive relationship between ICT tools used and learning techniques in Babcock University (r = .411, $P < 0.05$).

This study concluded that there is a positive relationship between ICT and learning techniques. Based on the finding of this study, it was recommended that current ICT tools can aid learning techniques.

Keywords: Information, Communication, Technology, Learning Techniques, Covid-19.

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a group of technological tools and resources that are used to share, transmit, store, create, or exchange information. These technological tools and resources include computers, the internet (websites, blogs and emails), live broadcasting technologies (television, radio and webcasting), recorded broadcasting technologies (audio and video players, podcasting, and storage devices) and telephony (fixed or mobile, satellite, visio/video-conferencing, etc.) (Ibenwa *et al.*, 2024).

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced educators and students at all levels of education to immediately adapt to online learning which involves the use of ICT tools. The impact of this and the developments required to make it work could permanently change how education is delivered.

The COVID-19 pandemic also forced the world to accept and adopt the current use of ICT in learning. Although online and distance learning has been used before to maintain continuity in education, such as in the aftermath of earthquakes (Mackay *et al.*, 2012), the scale of the current crisis is unprecedented. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, many people and educational organizations see online education as an alternative pathway to the traditional mode of learning (Hodges, 2020), but now, online education is becoming the go to mode for both teaching and learning. The lockdown brought about a paradigm shift from the physical learning strategies to the online mode (Murphy, 2020). During the lockdown, schools were not allowed to open and it was difficult for students to learn physically. This made most schools move their operations and teachings online so as to ensure that the students were engaged.

Technology helps both teachers and students to easily access various materials in different formats. It also help save spaces that will usually be taken up by hardcopy materials (Skulmowski, 2020).

As a result of COVID-19, institutions and educational organizations are now having online classes via software such as Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, Zoom, Google Classroom, and so on. In Babcock University, the students are made to offer their General Education Courses (GEDS) online. This is achieved through the use of software platforms like Microsoft Teams, Google Meet and Google Classroom. The techniques used in online learning is a bit different from the physical learning because the students and teacher (s) are not physically in contact with each other. Even in the physical learning, ICT still play important roles in the post COVID-19 era as we now have interactive digital whiteboards replacing the traditional chalkboard. Students are also now allowed to bring in tablets and laptops into classes to give them the technological feeling that they crave for.

Technology in education has brought about a different type of learning technique for students. Because online teaching is technology based, learners have had to readjust themselves to the demands of online education. This entails that the students have gadgets like laptop, smartphones, tablets or desktop. In addition to this is the availability of stable internet

connection, this can be gotten by subscribing through a mobile network or connection to a WIFI network.

Online education require students to submit assignments, write quizzes and tests and even take exams online. Most times, the lecturer give assignments or quizzes with a deadline attached to it. This means that the students must be time conscious so as not to be timed out or marked out for late submission. The lecturers also send materials online which the students are required to download and read. These materials may include recorded videos and audios or attachments in form of notes and PowerPoints.

Some lecturers also require students to do presentations on topics either as an individual or as a group. As good as ICT is in education, it also has its downside which may include network lag, lack of seriousness from students part, students not understanding some teachings especially calculations, power outage leading to flat battery on devices and students not having enough data.

Research Questions

- i. Will ICT tools affect learning techniques in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students?
- ii. What are the various ICT tools used for learning in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students?

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design approach. The study population comprised a total of 11,000 students in Babcock University, Ilishan Remo. The research instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was used for collecting responses from the subject selected for the study which consisted of three sections.

Section A consisted of questions for the demographics. Section B included the ICT scale. The section C focused on learning technique scale.

The likert-scale was used to measure opinions, Strongly Disagree = 4, Disagree = 3, Strongly Agree = 2, Agree = 1. A reliability coefficient of 0.751 was obtained for the questionnaire. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was used to analyze the demographic section while the inferential was used to test the stated hypotheses. All tests were considered significant at the alpha level of 0.05.

Results and Findings

4.1. Demographic Presentation

Table 4.1 Frequency Distribution of Participant's Demographic Data

S/No.	Variable	Category	Frequency (N= 369)	Percentage
	Gender	Male	215	58.3
		Female	154	41.7
	Age	18 - 20 years	154	41.7
		Over 20 years	215	58.3
	Religion	Christianity	241	65.3
		Islam	128	34.7
	Ethnicity	Yoruba	246	66.7
		Igbo	77	20.9
		Hausa	46	12.5

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4.1 reveals the respondents demographic distribution. It was indicated that a majority of the respondent were male 215 (58.3%) while 154 (41.7%) were female. The table further revealed that 154 (41.7%) were within the ages of 18-20years while 215 (58.3%) were within the ages of 20 years and above. Hence, most of the respondents were within the ages of 20 years and above. It was also revealed that 241 (65.3%) of the respondents were Christians, while 128 (34.7%) were Muslims. Hence, most of the respondents were Christians. The table also showed that 246 (66.7%) of the respondents were Yoruba, 77 (20.9%) were Igbo, while 46 (12.5%) were Hausa. Thus, most of the respondents were Yoruba.

Research Question One: What are the learning techniques in post COVID-19 era using Babcock University students as case study?

Table 4.2: LEARNING TECHNIQUE SCALE

S/N	QUESTIONS	Mean (\bar{x})	St.D
1	I can remember best by listening to a lecture that includes information, explanations and discussions	3.33	.79741
2	I prefer to see information written on the board and supplemented by visual aids and assigned readings	3.34	.85
3	I like to write things down or take notes for visual review	3.42	.87
4	I prefer to use posters, models, or actual practice and other activities in class.	3.01	.64
5	I require explanations of diagrams, graphs, or visual directions	3.17	.75
6	I enjoy working with my hands or making things	3.13	.88
7	I am skilful with and enjoy developing making graphs and charts	2.33	.69

8	I can tell if sounds match when presented with pairs of sounds	2.79	.82
9	I can remember best by writing things down several times	3.34	.90
10	I can easily understand and follow directions on a map	2.88	.78
11	I do best in academic subjects by listening to lectures and tapes	3.04	.73
12	I learn to spell better by repeating words out loud than by writing the words on paper	2.95	1.02

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4.2 showed the respondents view on the learning techniques in Babcock University. The result was interpreted using the mean values which has a boundary of 2.5 ($1+2+3+4=10/4=2.5$) acceptance. Result shows that on the average the respondents were of the view that they can remember best by listening to a lecture that includes information, explanations and discussions ($\bar{x}=3.33$; $St.D=.80$), it was deduced that the respondents are of the view that they prefer to see information written on the board and supplemented by visual aids and assigned readings ($\bar{x}=3.34$; $St.D=.85$), they are of the opinion that they like to write things down or take notes for visual review ($\bar{x}=3.42$; $St.D=.87$) and they are also of the view that they prefer to use posters, models, or actual practice and other activities in class ($\bar{x}=3.01$; $St.D=.64$), they are the view that they require explanations of diagrams, graphs, or visual directions ($\bar{x}=3.17$; $St.D=.75$), they are of the opinion that they enjoy working with my hands or making things ($\bar{x}=3.13$; $St.D=.88$), they however, disagree that they were skillful with and enjoy developing making graphs and charts ($\bar{x}=2.33$; $St.D=.69$), it could be deduced from the result that the respondents can tell if sounds match when presented with pairs of sounds ($\bar{x}=2.79$; $St.D=.82$), they also can remember best by writing things down several times ($\bar{x}=3.34$; $St.D=.90$), they believe that they can easily understand and follow directions on a map ($\bar{x}=2.88$; $St.D=.78$), and also believe that they do best in academic subjects by listening to lectures and tapes ($\bar{x}=3.04$; $St.D=.73$), the table finally revealed that on the average, the respondents are of the view that they learn to spell better by repeating words out loud than by writing the words on paper ($\bar{x}=2.95$; $St.D=1.02$). it could be deduced from this result that the major learning techniques obtainable in Babcock University is that the respondents take write down notes to subsequently read and the students also prefer see information written on the board and supplemented by visual aids and assigned readings as they can remember best by writing things down several times.

Research Question Two: What are the types of ICT tools used in post COVID-19 era, using Babcock University students as case study?

Table 4.3: The ICT tools available and used for learning in Babcock University

SN	QUESTIONS	Mean	St.D
1	Google Classroom	3.72	.67
2	Google Meet	3.34	.94
4	Microsoft Teams	3.26	.87
7	Social Media (WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, Telegram)	3.26	.72
3	Edmodo	2.53	.91
5	Blackboard	2.07	1.08
10	We Transfer	2.04	.79
9	Dropbox	1.99	.91
8	Kahoot	1.66	.63
6	Trello	1.61	.69

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4.3 showed the respondents view on the types of the ICT tools available used in Babcock University. The result was also interpreted using the mean values which has a boundary of 2.5 ($1+2+3+4= 10/4 = 2.5$) acceptance. Result shows that on the average based on responses from the respondents, the most available ICT tool use in Babcock is Google Classroom ($\bar{x}= 3.72$; $St.D= .67$) and this is closely followed by Google Meet ($\bar{x}= 3.34$; $St.D= .94$), Microsoft Teams ($\bar{x}= 3.26$; $St.D=.87$), Social Media ($\bar{x}= 3.26$; $St.D= .72$), Edmodo ($\bar{x}= 2.53$; $St.D= .91$), while the least is Trello ($\bar{x}= 1.61$; $St.D= .69$).

Test of Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between ICT tools and learning techniques in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix on the relationship between ICT tools and learning techniques in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students

		LEARNING	ICT
LEARNING	Pearson Correlation	1	.411**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	369	369
ICT	Pearson Correlation	.411**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	369	369

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3 revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between ICT tools use and the leaning techniques in Babcock University ($r= .411$, $P< 0.05$). This invariably implies the ICT tools use determine the leaning techniques adopted by the students in Babcock.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that for Babcock University students, there is a relationship between ICT and learning techniques. It was recommended that Students should be exposed to more ICT tools that can aid their learning techniques and teachers should be obligated to make use of trending ICT tools in their classroom delivery in order to enrich student learning. Parents should provide ICT tools at home in order to foster a home environment that is conducive to meaningful private study and thereby increase the learning of their children.

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INTERNET ADDICTION AND EARLY PORNOGRAPHY CONTACT AS CORRELATES OF ADOLESCENTS' SEXUAL BEHAVIOR: IMPLICATION FOR COUNSELLING INTERVENTION

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Abstract

The study was designed to examine internet addiction and early pornography contact as correlates of adolescents' sexual behavior. The central purpose of this study was to find if there is any significant relationship between early pornography contact and Adolescent's sexual behavior and to ascertain the relative contribution of internet addiction and early pornography contact on adolescents' sexual behavior. Descriptive research design of the correlational type was adopted in which structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The population for this study was all newly admitted 100 level students of Babcock University Nigeria, 2018/2019 academic year. The sample consisted of two hundred (n=200) students; from which 55.5% (n=111) were males and 44.5% (n=89) were female. Data collected were analyzed using Descriptive Statistics (DS), Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA). The finding reveals that there is a significant relationship between internet addiction and adolescent sexual behavior at ($r=.189, P<.05$). More so, the analysis of variance shows a statistically significant composite contribution of internet use among adolescents at ($f_{2,197} = 13.379 < 0.05$). Also, pornography predicts adolescent sexual behavior more significantly than internet addiction. The study stipulates that internet addiction and its significant impact on adolescent's sexual behavior have raised a societal challenge that calls for attention. The need for rehabilitation and support centers in schools and colleges was highlighted, were adolescents traces of internet addiction could receive care and intervention. The need for parents, guardians and teachers to closely monitor the adolescents as they surf the internet was also highlighted.

Key words: internet addiction, early pornography contact, adolescents' sexual behavior

Introduction

Sexual predisposition, transition from virginity to active sexual life, unplanned pregnancy and other negative sexual behaviors prevailing among many adolescents have attracted the interest of researchers in various fields of human endeavors especially in behavioral sciences. Sexual behavior is an act exhibited by individuals to gratify their sexual pleasure (Chawla, &

Sarkar, 2019). Such behavioral displays may portray both biological and cultural influences and involve sexual arousal. Sexual behavior therefore represents an individual's sexual attitude or practice, be it heterosexual or homosexual activities which according to Arulogun, Ogbu, & Dipeolu (2016) are marked by some behavioral changes such as oral sex, body tattoo, multiple sexual partners, homosexuality and lesbianism. Nevertheless, one may not enumerate all the negative outcomes when an individual begins to masturbate for sexual feelings or involves in experimental sexual activity with his or her mates at a tender age. Hugging and squeezing of hands, kissing and torching are also some of the observed sexual behaviors of the adolescents (Maswikwa, Richter, Kaufman, & Nandi, 2015).

According to Aji, Aji, Ifeadike, Emelumadu, Ubajaka, Nwabueze, & Azuike, (2013). Adolescents' sexual behaviors are in the increase in recent times hence sexual curiosity, changes in hormonal secretion and other psychosocial development has also increased, but varies across diverse groups and cultures. These increases of adolescents' sexual behaviors are deviant to some traditional or cultural norms that place considerable importance on morality and also promote sexual relationship only for those in marital union.

Adolescent is derived from the Latin vocabulary "adolescere" which connotes "to grow up" (Mills, 2016). Adolescence is a distinctive and transitional stage of human growth and developmental between childhood and adulthood. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines an adolescent as any person between age 10 and 19. According to (WHO) the group of people who can be regarded as adolescents are people who fall under the age range of 10 and 19. Adolescents therefore, make-up of 16% of the world's population, and in sub-Saharan Africa, 23% of the population are adolescents (UNICEF, 2016). Thus adolescent is a stage of vulnerability and opportunity: vulnerability in the sense of been victims of exploitation, violence and abuses of all kinds that could possibly result to death. And opportunities in the expanse of personal identity, values and developmental growth such that will help the adolescent to navigate through life hazards and vulnerabilities thereby fulfill his or her potential goals. The Internet provides a fundamentally different environment for international marketing and requires a different approach. Now it is unrealistic to apply the same marketing strategies without making some modifications to be appropriate to the electronic edge. This paper touches on the effect of international Internet marketing (IIM)

The Internet in today's hi-tech age has become a more conversant environment for socialization, interaction, communication, and expression that had contributed greatly to the whole development of adolescents mostly in research and studies, self-expression and unabridged socialization. Kwon, Kim, & So, (2020) argued that the most challenging issue with respect to adolescents' internet use is its management and regulation, thus, internet platforms may have some social and unhealthy consequences among adolescents due to rare or no parental and guardian monitoring and private activities. This study observes that good number of adolescents in schools and colleges are hooked to the internet either on their phones, tablets, and iPod or even on their laptop computers, which makes parental or guardian monitory unrealistic, thus they can do whatever thing they like, visit which ever site of their choices and also enjoy some level of freedom and unabridged socialization. According to the World Internet Usage and Population Statistics 2020: 39.3% of Africans, 53.6% of Asians, 87.2% of Latin American and

Caribbean, 94.6% of Northern Americans use the internet. The report gathered by World Internet Usage and Population Statistics 2020 as referenced above shows a rapid internet growth user of 11.559 % in Africa and 5,395 % in Middle East between years 2000-2020. While the percentage of internet users around the world had grown rapidly one may deduce that more than 70% of these users are adolescents, no doubt such obsessive internet use may have negative significant effect on their sexual behavior and total wellbeing. Seyyed-Mohammad-Taghi Ayatollahi (2010) coincided that Internet addiction has negative effect on the behavioral and psychological development of adolescents. Similarly, Smutny, & Sulc (2018) see the internet as a fast-tracker of pornographic materials, hence unwanted pornographic video and pictures may pop-ups as soon as one connects the Internet.

Early pornography contact is an act of watching or been exposed to materials, images, pictures or video clips that are produced to create a sense of erotic arousal at a tender age (Ashraaf & Othman 2019). Pornography distorts an individual's natural thought pattern and behavior about sex and sexuality and also undermines his or her social functioning power (Fagan, 2009), subsequently fair judgment becomes impossible. Therefore this study postulates pornography as the portrayal of any erotic behavior in form of words, arts, pictures, videos or representations that are calculated to stimulate sexual feelings independent of the presence of viewer. Other pornographic representations and sexual activities include: pictures of stripped men and women, masturbation, oral sex, vaginal and anal penetration in an unconcealed manner thus alters both sexual attitudes and behaviors of an individual.

In their view Okafor, Efetobor, & Apeh, (2015) highlighted that internet or cyber pornography is becoming vogue among Nigerian youths. Consequently, good numbers of adolescents are voluntarily or involuntarily becoming victims. They linked the fast growing internet pornography among adolescents in Nigerian to the absence of concrete law against cybercrimes and abuse (Okafor et al., 2015). Little wonder Yamoah & Dei (2015) view Pornography as a catalyst that undermines adolescents' social stability and distorts their natural order of growth and development. Obviously, the Internet has significantly made pornography more easily available and accessible to different group of users especially adolescents (Beyens & Eggermont, 2014).

Adolescents' sexual behavior resulting from early espouse to internet pornography presents a serious global challenge today. Thus the extent to which free accessed internet pornography has negatively affected adolescents' sexual behaviors is alarming. In recent times, observation has shown a growing sexual behavior among adolescents that is characterized by but not limited to display of sexual body parts in public domain, transition from virginity to sexual activities, having multiple sexual partners, pressuring of peers into sexual activities and other socio-emotional problems. Adolescents are more vulnerable to unhealthy sexual activities and their ethical logics about sex and sexuality had become biased at such tender age. If this development is not urgently checked and reversed, it can adversely affect the wellbeing of many adolescents. Therefore, this study was aimed at investigating internet addition and early pornography contact as correlates of adolescents' sexual behavior.

Research Questions

Is there any significant relationship between Internet addiction and Adolescent Sexual Behavior

Is there any significant relationship between Early pornography contact and Adolescent's Sexual behavior

What is the significant composite contribution of Internet addiction and early pornography contact

What is the relative contribution of Internet addiction and Early pornography contact to Adolescent Sexual behavior

Methods

The study employed Descriptive research design of the correlational type. The population for this study was all newly admitted 100 level students of Babcock University Nigeria, 2018/2019 academic year. The sample consisted of two hundred (n=200) students; from which 55.5% (n=111) were males and 44.5% (n=89) were female. All the participants were less than one (1) month in the University community as at the time of study. Data collected were analyzed using Descriptive Statistics (DS) in determining the demographics of the respondents, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was as also used to answer questions one (1) and two (2) while Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used in answering questions three (3) and four (4).

Result and Discussion of Findings

Table1 Demographics of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
		Total= 200	
Gender	Male	111	55.5
	Female	89	44.5

Table 1 shows that the respondents were more of men (111; 55.5%) while the female were (89; 44.5%). This shows that more men participated in the study than female.

Answering Research Question

Research question 1 (RQ1): is there any significant relationship between Internet addiction and Adolescent Sexual Behavior. This questions was tested using Pearson product moment correlation and the result is presented in the table below

Table 2 Summary of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient showing relationship between Internet addiction and Adolescent Sexual Behavior

Variable	Number	Mean	Std. dev.	R	Sig	Remark
Internet addiction	200	28.1150	4.51149	.189	.007	Significant
Adolescent Sexual Behavior	200	14.0550	2.88681			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result of the analysis reveals that the correlation (r) is at $P < .05$ ($r = .189$, $P < .05$). This means that there is a significant relationship between internet addiction and adolescent sexual behavior. This finding agrees with [Dwulit & Rzymiski](#) (2019) that the Internet was the most often used form of accessing photographic picture and literatures, thus 76.5%, of their respondents admitted browsing online pornography using private or multiple internet modes. The prevalence rate of internet use and its exposure by adolescent has become higher, little wonder the present study found significant relationship between internet addiction and pornographic use among adolescents. However, it is possible that the high prevalence of pornography among adolescent today could be as a result of internet facilities that are available to them without significant restriction, supervision or even guidance. In fact, one may not necessarily desire to log on to pornographic sites before he or she is intimidated by unwanted nude pictures mostly of women. That is to say that the internet presently lures one to see such picture or video clip, in some cases unwanted sex videos are also seen.

Research question 3 (RQ3): is there any significant relationship between early pornography contact and Adolescent's Sexual behavior. This question was tested using Pearson product moment correlation; the table below presents the result.

Table: 3 Summary of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient showing relationship between early pornography contact and Adolescent's Sexual behavior

Variable	Number	Mean	Std. dev.	R	Sig	Remark
internet use among adolescents	200	28.1150	4.51149	.315	.000	Significant
adolescent and internet pornography	200	13.1050	2.49703			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result of the analysis reveals that the correlation (r) is at $P < .05$ ($r = .315$, $P < .05$). This result indicates a significant relationship between early pornography contact and adolescent sexual behavior. This finding is in agreement with the findings of (Kar, 2015) who found that online pornography addiction had a significantly adverse effect on social and sexual behavior among University students. Also, there are other literatures suggesting that adolescents can learn sexual behaviors from watching the behaviors shown in sexually explicit videos, pictures or other materials (Alexy, Burgess, & Prentky, 2009, Haggström-Nordin et al., 2006). These findings are simply saying that there is a relationship between adolescents' pornography viewing and

sexual behavior. Thus, adolescents' sexual orientation can be negatively impacted by *watching videos and pictures created to arouse sexual interest*. Hence, adolescents tend to imitate what they see because of the peculiarity of their stage in human development.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3 (RQ3): what is the significant composite contribution of Internet addiction and early pornography contact? This question was tested with multiple regressions and the result is presented in the table 4 below.

Table 4 **Model summary of the R, R square and adjusted R in the multiple regression analysis**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.346 ^a	.120	.111	4.25459

a. Predictors: (Constant), Pornography And Adolescents Sexual Behavior , Adolescent And Internet Pornography

The correlation coefficient resulting from the multiple regression analysis discloses that there is a moderate correlation ($R = .348$) between the predictors and the criterion variables. The coefficient of determination is relatively mild ($R^2 = .120$) shows a weak strength in predicting adolescent and Internet Pornography. The composite contribution is further interpreted by the ANOVA Summary below.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	484.356	2	242.178	13.379	.000 ^b
	Residual	3565.999	197	18.102		
	Total	4050.355	199			

A. Dependent variable: internet use among adolescents

B. Predictors: (constant), pornography and adolescents sexual behavior , adolescent and internet pornography.

The analysis of variance is very significant ($.000, f_{(2, 197)} = 13.379 < 0.05$). This illustrates that the composite contribution of internet use among adolescents is statistically significant hence it can be assumed that the predictor variables could actually predict adolescents' sexual behavior. This finding indicates that increase in internet usage could also increase adolescent sexual behavior. This finding corroborates (Landry, et. al.2017) that found a statistically significant positive association between high-frequency internet use and increased sexual behaviors over a period of time. This result also predict that when an adolescent watches or observe unusual behaviors there may be some likelihood for such an individual to internalize such behaviors be it normal or abnormal behaviors.

Research Question 4 (RQ4): what is the relative contribution of internet addiction and early pornography contact to adolescent sexual behavior. This question was tested with multiple regressions and the result is presented in the table 4.8.

Table 5 the beta (β) coefficient in the multiple regression analysis showing relative contributions Internet addiction and early pornography contact to Adolescent Sexual behavior contributions

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	17.992	2.037		8.833	.000
Internet Addiction And Early Pornography Contact And Adolescents' Sexual Behavior	.530	.122	.293	4.336	.000
	.226	.106	.145	2.143	.033

From the table 5 above, the (β) weightings of the two predictors' variables are given in the standardized coefficient column, the constant is 17.992 relative to each other, adolescents' sexual behavior and internet pornography has a positive effect on adolescents' internet pornography. ($\beta=.293$) and this is statistically significant (.000, < 0.05), pornography and adolescents sexual behavior has a positive effect on adolescent internet pornography. ($\beta=.145$) and this is statistically significant (0.033, < 0.05). From the result presented, it can be concluded that both predictor variables had statistically significant effect on adolescent sexual behavior. There different beta values in the result above represent their relative contributions to adolescent sexual behavior. Drouin & Miller (2016), agreed with the findings of the present study, when they noted significant relationships between internet addiction, online erotica use, and online risky sexual behaviors.

Summary of Findings

There is a significant relationship between internet addiction and adolescent sexual behavior

There is a significant relationship between early pornography contact and adolescent sexual behavior.

The composite contribution of internet addiction and early pornography contact among adolescents is statistically significant hence it can be assumed that the predictor variables could actually predict adolescents' sexual behavior

Pornography predicts adolescents' sexual behavior more than internet addiction

Conclusion:

This study has shown evidences that Internet addiction and early pornography contact have significant relationship with adolescents' sexual behavior. Furthermore, the study reveals that due to lack of parental monitoring or insignificant restriction on internet web adolescents are exposed to all forms of online pornographic videos, pictures and materials and some of them have even become addicted to practices shown in those materials.

Recommendations

Treatment and rehabilitation centers are needed in school, colleges, Universities and communities to support adolescents who for one reason or the other are addicted to on line pornography, and as a result their sexual orientation and behaviors are adversely effected

The result of this study has shown that constant use of the internet and early pornographic contact can negatively shape one's sexual attitudes and beliefs. Therefore, the need for close monitoring of adolescents by parents, guardians at home, and teachers at schools and colleges is recommended.

Social activities should be provided to engage adolescents meaningfully and also channel their sexual energy positively; doing that may reduce the time adolescents spend on internet activities.

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THE IMPACT OF SATELLITE TELEVISION PROGRAMS ON THE ACQUISITION AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

It is a consensus among linguists that language acquisition occurs in the context of societal interaction. Hence, a child's cognitive development will largely be influenced by the adults through whom he acquires language and gets acculturated. This tends to limit the sources of acquisition to the immediate environment of the child. However, today's global world creates a different situation, especially in many Nigerian homes. The proliferation of Satellite television, almost limitless possibilities in the film industry, and majorly in animations has created a global society within the homes of most elite families. Children's cartoons have become so realistic and interactional, and children's exposure to television has become so regular and significant that their language acquisition/language learning is impacted by it. Employing the perspectives of Vygotsky's Interactionist Theory of language learning, this paper explores the impact of the virtual global world to which children are exposed through satellite television children programs. The paper adopted the descriptive survey research design. The study sample comprises twenty children consisting of 2 children from each of the selected 10 families. A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the 20 children. It is found that children exposed to regular viewing of children's cartoons acquire a cognitive ability that surpasses the physical exposure to adult language use in their immediate society. Recommendations are thereby proffered.

Keywords: Satellite-Television, Language Acquisition, Language Learning, Cartoons

Introduction

Like any other natural language, the English language is a social phenomenon that has relevance only in social settings. It is either acquired in society as a first language or learnt as a second or foreign language. Scholars have established that “It is impossible to imagine the development of society without language and the development of language without society” (Mamadaliyeva, 2021). Hence, Vygotsky (1978) posits that language can only be acquired through interaction in a society. Thus, language acquisition occurs in a package that includes the culture and collective knowledge of society. In other words, society and language are mutually indispensable. Language is thus a very complex human phenomenon which has proved challenging to define, as several definitions have been found inadequate. Crystal (2010) defines language as a system of conventional, spoken or written symbols by which human beings communicate as members of a social group and participants in its culture. Hence, the definition submits that language occurs in a society. Therefore, children acquire the language of the society along with all the features of pronunciation, grammar, lexical items and cultural perspectives of the society. Simply put, they speak like they are spoken to.

The Nigerian child will thus speak like a Nigerian. When the Nigerian child begins to switch between speaking like a Nigerian child and speaking like an American, for example, there is a need to question the theories of language acquisition and learning and their postulations. For instance, David requested a biscuit, and his mother refused to give him one. He responded by saying, “Aw awww! He turned away, drooping his shoulders with arms dangling and back slouched in a typical cartoon pose of dejection. Her mother did not understand the pose and fiercely instructed David to “stop walking like that and walk normally”. David has acquired some socio-linguistic characteristics that her mother was not aware of. Such is the situation in many families where Satellite television has created an extended society for the Nigerian child who is exposed to a tangible amount of television viewing. In other words, like many Nigerian children from elite homes, David has acquired linguistic and cultural characteristics outside the linguistic characteristics of the society in which he has acquired language.

Review of Literature

The use of English in the world and, by implication, in Nigeria has a significant bearing on our learners as world citizens. The English language, though a mother tongue to native speakers, is a second and foreign language to many people in the world, of which Nigeria is inclusive (UBE, 2010). As a result of the numerous functions the language performs in Nigeria, it has continued to grow steadily on a daily basis. For instance, English is used in education, not just as a teaching subject but also as the language of instruction in Nigerian schools from upper primary to tertiary institutions (NPE, 2004). It is a compulsory subject required to study any course in any

institution of learning in Nigeria. It is used in the media, Nigerian politics, commerce and international frontiers.

For learners of the English Language as a second or foreign language, access to the use of the language in society is rare. This is, however, changing with Nigerian children as they are exposed to the language in use via satellite television. Poštič (2015) observes that increasing numbers of Bangladeshi students spoke English with an almost pure American accent, including intonation. They found that this resulted from their viewing of American programs on television. The channels available on TV have been multiplied greatly by the introduction of cable and satellite television, which allows a variety of TV programs to be viewed round the clock, day and night. For the children, cartoon network is an irresistible choice (Tamba, 2022)

Children in the ages range between zero and ten years are typically drawn to cartoons on TV. According to Singleton (1989), this is the period when a child has the chance to reach a near-native competence in the pronunciation of English. Clark (2000), in a study on the pedagogical value of cartoons, found that cartoons engage learners' attention, create a conducive atmosphere for learning, and thus improve their ability to think and discuss. Doring (2002) explains that language learners exposed to cartoons can produce very productive and interesting oral answers. Scheffler and Baranowska (2023) also found in their study that watching videos significantly improved the recognition of how words are pronounced. The value of cartoons in teaching is further underscored by Bahrani and Sim (2012), who posit that children with a low ability to learn language can be significantly improved through exposure to cartoons. Thus, through satellite television, especially cartoons (which are children's favourite choices), English learners are attracted to the speakers' language and are also stimulated to speak the language. (Haque 2013).

Theoretical Framework

Perspectives of Vygotsky's interactionist theory of language learning are employed in this study. Lev Vygotsky was a Russian psychologist best known for his sociocultural theory who believed that social interaction plays a critical role in children's learning. Through such social interactions, children go through a continuous process of learning. Vygotsky sociocultural theory of human learning describes learning as a social process and the origination of human intelligence in society or culture (1978). The central theme of Vygotsky's theoretical framework is that social interaction plays a fundamental role in the development of cognition. Vygotsky believed that children acquire language as a result of engaging in social experiences. The interactionist approach (sociocultural theory) combines ideas from sociology and biology to explain how language is developed. According to this theory, children learn language out of a desire to communicate with the world around them and language emerges from and is dependent upon social interaction. Vygotsky was of the view that learning has its basis in interacting with other people.

The apparent social interaction a typical Nigerian child from an elite home is expected to be involved in includes his immediate family and peers at home and in school. In a typical setting, all of these speak the Nigerian variety of English. This paper observed, however, that the social

interaction that such a child is involved in includes an extension into the social environment created on television cartoons and other children's programs on cable television and according to the interactionist theory of language acquisition, children who are exposed to this extended social interaction on cable television, should acquire language from it.

Statement of the Problem

Satellite or cable television has become very common in Nigeria with the introduction of cheaper decoders and cheaper viewing packages. Most elite homes thus have at least one of such decoders, and many homes have one dedicated to the viewing pleasure of the children who are drawn naturally to the cartoon networks. Coupled with the fact that most elite homes feature busy parents, children are often kept engaged in front of the television, which they often view for hours on end. One of the results of this is that Nigerian children from elite homes develop in a community which is extended into the virtual society on television. Since language is acquired in society, one must ask: for a child like David, who lives with his parents and attends a local daycare, where did the exclamatory expression "Aw awww!" and the drooping pose come from? In view of this, this paper interrogates the extended society on satellite televisions as a source for the acquisition of British and/or American English among Nigerian children.

Significance of the Study

Findings from this study are significant for developing methods of improving English language skills in Nigerian children, especially in achieving mutual intelligibility among British, American and Nigerian English speakers. It could also be effectively employed in incorporating cartoons into the teaching and learning of the English Language among Nigerian children.

Research Questions

The study was designed to proffer answers to the following research questions (henceforth "RQ").

RQ1: Do children spend enough time before the television to acquire a language or its features?

RQ2: Are lexical features of British and/or American English noticeable in the use of language by the children studied?

RQ3: Are phonological features of British and/or American English evident in the use of language by the children studied?

RQ4: Are grammatical features of British and/or American English noticeable in the use of language by the children studied?

RQ5: Do the children code switch between the British /American and the Nigerian varieties of English?

Research Methodology

A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The instrument used for this study was a self-designed questionnaire tagged “Impact of Satellite Television Programs on Acquisition and Learning of English as a Second Language in Nigeria”. The instrument was validated by research experts whose corrections were strictly adhered to. The questionnaire was in two parts- part A required the respondents to supply their bio-data, while part B comprised open and closed-ended items. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire to enhance good responses from the respondents. The analysis was done using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Data Analysis

RQ 1: Do children spend enough time before the television to acquire a language or its features?

Question 1. Do your children watch programs on cable television?

Figure 1. Children watch Satellite television.

Figure 1 shows that 100% of the respondents' children are exposed to satellite television, affirming that most children from elite homes have their social environment extended into the environments created on TV programs.

Question 2. From what age have they been watching cable TV?

Figure 2. Age of children on the first day behind the screen

Figure 2 shows that 80% of the respondents have allowed their children to watch television by age 1. 15% claimed that their children started between 2 and 3 years, 5% claimed they started

between 4 and 5 years, and none started as late as 6 years. This indicates that children get exposed to television at the same time considered most crucial to language acquisition.

Question 3. How many days of the week do they watch television?

Figure 3. Number of Days of TV Viewing

Figure 3. shows that 35% of the respondents place the average number of days their children watch TV in a week at less than three days, while 45% of them posit that their children watch TV more than 3 days in a week, and 20% reveal that their children watch TV every day. This shows that children watch television for a significant number of days in the week, indicating that the TV could have an impact on their developmental processes.

Question 4. What is the average number of hours they spend watching TV per day?

Figure 4. Daily Exposure to the TV

Table 4 shows that 45% of the respondents stated an average viewing time of 1 hour for their children, 35% opted for 2 to three hours, 25% picked 4 to 5 hours, and five percent picked over five hours. Since children of 80% of respondents spend 2 to five hours per day watching TV, the time spent watching in front of the screen and the virtual society it creates is significant enough for them to acquire language features from this source.

Question 2. Does the average time spent watching TV increase during the holidays?

Figure 2. More Television on Holidays

95% of respondents agree that children do more of television viewing during their holidays, while only five percent of them disagree. The implication of this is that even more exposure to television viewing occurs during school holidays.

The preceding shows the extent to which children are exposed to television, especially cartoons, which take up more of the time they spend viewing TV. This provided an affirmative response to research question 1. Thus, children spend enough time watching satellite television to be able to acquire a language or features of a language.

RQ 3: Are lexical features of British and/or American English noticeable in the use of language by the children studied?

Question 2.1. Do your children use English words you are not familiar with?

Figure 6: Lexical Evidence of Acquisition

Figure 6 shows that 90% of the respondents have observed lexical items in their children's diction that were novel to them as parents and which they have traced to some of the cartoons they watched on TV. 45% of them agreed with an emphatic yes, while another 45% stated that they sometimes observe such novel lexical items. 10% of them did not observe such new words in the diction of their children. This shows that the extended societies of the children made them acquire new words in the English Language.

Question 2.2.: Do they know the names of animals/plants that you do not?

Figure 7: foreign Nature Awareness

Figure 7 shows that 5% of the respondents are sure that their children knew such names of Animals and plants. 40% said they did sometimes, and another 35% affirmed that they did. However, 20% of the Parents posit that their children did not know the names of animals they

were unaware of. Since many cartoon programs children watch have animal characters, many of which are geared towards creating awareness of nature and its preservation, children are exposed to names and characteristics of animals and plants. Since this data shows evidence of awareness of animals and plants beyond the experience available in the immediate environment of respondents' children, it shows that acquisition and learning are taking place through their television viewing.

Question 2.3.: Do they talk about things you are not familiar with?

Figure 8: Novel Experiences

Figure 8 shows that 65% of respondents have observed that their children discussed ideas and things that they, as parents, were not familiar with. An additional 25% of respondents agree that their children sometimes do the same. 10%, however, did not know of their children discussing such novel experiences. Since language is also a tool of acculturation, this shows that the children had experiences outside their immediate social experience.

The foregoing shows that children have acquired words and expressions that their parents are unfamiliar with. This implies that they have experiences beyond that which their parents have exposed them to in their homes. This indicates that their social experiences and, consequently, their acquisition of language are not limited to their immediate home environment.

RQ 4: Are phonological features of British and/or American English evident in the use of language by the children studied?

Question 3.1. Have you heard them speak in an American or British accent?

Figure 9: British/American Accent?

Figure 9 shows that 30% of the respondents believe their children use either the British or American accent in their speech, 55% believe their children do so sometimes, and 5% were

unsure. However, 10% of the respondents believe their children did not speak with American or British accents. Accent is one of the most evident traces of a different variety of a language. The percentage of parents found to have noticed that their children could speak with some accent here indicates that Nigerian children under this study might be capable of speaking the English Language with an accent that they acquired outside their homes and immediate society.

Question 3.2.: Do they speak like the cartoon characters they watch on TV?

Figure 10: Cartoon Characters as Models

According to Table 10, 65% of the respondents agree that their children sometimes speak like their favourite cartoon characters, and another 25% agree that their children mimic the characters. Only 10% of the respondents feel that their children did not mimic their cartoon characters. This trend shows that the children, in acting their favourite characters in plays, practice speaking like them, thus building their skills in English speech with the accent of the characters.

Since children mimic and use the British or American speech mannerisms of their cartoon characters when they play. The children thus have acquired phonological features of these varieties of English since the cartoon networks use these varieties of the English Language.

RQ 5: Do the children code switch between the British /American and the Nigerian variety of English?

Question 4.1: Do they change the tone of their English speech at different times?

Figure: 11: Code Switching

Figure 11 shows that 85% of respondents agreed that their children switch between their everyday speech and British/ American accents, and another 5% say their children did so sometimes. 10% did not agree that their children sometimes switch their accents.

This also indicates an acquisition that could be traced to television viewing. More importantly, it shows that they can be kept apart and children can switch between them like different languages.

Discussion and Recommendation

Findings from this study show that children spend much time watching cable television. Such viewing extends their experiences beyond their immediate environments into those created on television. They thus acquire English language features, such as American accents, which are foreign to their homes but used frequently on their favourite programs on cable TV. The study also shows that these children had started watching TV from their formative ages, during which their language acquisition device was still active. This points to the possibility of acquiring the language(s) or varieties of language(s) they are exposed to on TV. Acquiring language, however, requires substantial exposure to the language. The study finds that most children watch TV more than three days a week. This is a significant exposure to the language of their TV program if the number of hours spent watching TV is substantial for each day. Findings of the study show that most of the children spend a significant length of time watching TV each day. The fact that the time spent watching TV increases for almost all children during holidays underscores the adequacy of the length of time. Thus, It is not surprising that the parents' responses show evidence of such language acquisition.

It must be noted that the use of language cannot be separated from culture. It is thus recommended that because the children could acquire foreign cultures along with the language, parents must ensure adequate and consistent parental guidance for their children even when they watch programs rated for general view. Since language acquisition is found to be possible through exposure to television programs, it is recommended that the types of TV programs that interest children should be explored in the teaching and learning process, especially in teaching a second or foreign language.

Conclusion

Satellite television is an extension of the social realities of Nigerian children, especially those from elite homes. Since language is acquired or learnt in society, the several hours of viewing programs on television provide a platform for the acquisition of the English language. Children spend enough time watching television several days of a week. Many would spend even more time in front of the television if allowed. This is usually because of their interest in cartoons and other television shows they find very irresistible. While attention has not been paid to specific satellite television programs in this study, findings have shown that generally, children get so involved in the settings, actions and lines spoken in the shows that they become, for them, an extended reality with which they interact and acquire the English language.

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THE ROLE OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES IN ACADEMIC CAREER DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The paper examines the potentials of emerging technologies (ETs) in academic career development. Technology has become an important tool for education and career advancement. With the advancement of technology, digital tools and platforms have become increasingly prevalent in education, offering various opportunities for academic professionals to enhance their careers. The emergence of digital technologies such as Artificial intelligence, social networks, Machine learning, videoconferencing tools and electronic databases have broadened the opportunities for teachers and students to advance their career prospects and research activities. Data were sourced from systematic review of publications from various notable databases that relates to use of emerging technologies in academic career advancement including; Scopus, Web of science, Google scholar, and Researchgate. Our findings from the reviews indicates that emerging technologies have broken distance or physical presence barriers that often limit access to training and other career development activities. Thus, there are now limitless access to instructional materials, academic resources and platforms that can be leveraged upon to advance

academic career development at any time and place. The evidence from the reviews also shows that emerging technologies have the potential to greatly impact academic career development in various ways such as: research publication, electronic/distance learning, virtual training, collaborations, meetings, mentoring, and other professional development programmes. However, digital gap, poor digital literacy, ethical issues, and lack of supportive infrastructures such as quality internet and constant power supply remains a challenge to the use of emerging technologies for academic career development in Nigeria especially in rural areas. The paper concludes that emerging technologies has become a Catalyst for Academic Career Progression.

Keywords: Emerging technologies, Artificial intelligence, Mobile technology, Internet, Internet , Virtual Reality, Career development.

1. Introduction

Technology has become very important part of human life. Digital technology availability has increased dramatically in recent years, and it now permeates practically every area of our life. Nearly everything today is being influenced by disruptive technologies. The world is fast embracing digital way of life due to high penetration of technology across the globe. The Coronavirus pandemic accelerated the use of technologies particularly for online education and career development and guidance and services (Haleem, Mohd and Rajiv, 2022). People including students, researchers, and other academic professionals are now under greater pressure to leverage the gains of technology to advance their career and improve their productivity (Edeh, Ugboaja, Ugwuja, Igwe, Daniel and Richard-Nnabu, 2022). Recent advancements in technology, including machine learning, learning platforms, virtual reality, and distributed ledger technologies like blockchain, have made it possible to make many more significant changes to the way career and faculty development programs are run. Emerging technologies provide easy access to vast amounts of information and educational resources that support employment chances of academic professionals. Online databases, digital libraries, e-books, academic journals, and educational websites enable students and researchers to access up-to-date information and enhance their knowledge in various fields (Robinson and Hullinger, 2008; Zhou and Zhang, 2008).

Emerging technologies offers many opportunities for academic career development including digital discussion forums, virtual classrooms, and collaborative tools that enable individuals to connect with peers and experts from diverse backgrounds, exchange ideas, engage in group projects, and develop valuable networks, which can lead to research collaborations, mentorship opportunities, and career advancement. More so, digital technologies allow individuals to showcase their skills, achievements, and projects through online portfolios and digital credentials. These platforms enable students and professionals to create a comprehensive digital profile that can be easily shared with potential employers or academic institutions, enhancing their career prospects and demonstrating their expertise. Studies have also shown that digital technologies offer avenues for online career courses, career guidance and mentorship (Kumi-Yeboah, Sallar, Kiramba, and Kim, 2020; Oliveira et al, 2019; Robinson and Hullinger, 2008; Zhou and Zhang, 2008). Digital platforms connect students with mentors, professionals, and alumni who can provide valuable insights, advice, and guidance regarding career choices,

internships, and job opportunities. These connections and mentorship relationships can greatly contribute to students' academic and professional growth. For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of remote and flexible learning models. Digital technologies enable students to access educational resources and participate in virtual classrooms from anywhere, providing flexibility in managing their academic and personal commitments. Remote learning also opens doors to international collaborations and interdisciplinary opportunities, broadening students' horizons and enriching their academic careers. In summary, emerging technologies offer numerous prospects for academic career development, including access to information and resources, online learning platforms, collaboration and networking opportunities, research tools, digital portfolios, remote learning options, and career guidance. Embracing these technologies can empower teachers and students to enhance their employability skills, expand their knowledge, and achieve their career goals in the increasingly digital world (Kumi-Yeboah, Sallar, Kiramba, and Kim, 2020).

The increased use of technology necessitates a reevaluation of both the services offered and the methods through which they are delivered. Navigating emerging technologies and effectively utilizing them for academic career development requires a certain level of digital literacy to effectively use various tools and platforms, which some individuals may lack thereby hindering their ability to leverage digital technologies for their career advancement. This paper provides a comprehensive understanding of how digital technology is shaping academic career development. The highlights underscore the transformative potential of emerging technologies in academic career advancement, while also acknowledging the challenges associated with their use. The paper could serve as a valuable resource for researchers, educators, and academic professionals seeking to navigate the digital landscape and harness its potential for career advancement in academia.

2. Academic Career Development

A career is a person's "journey" through lifetime learning, employment, in-depth training, and the acquisition of new skills. It can be characterized as a type of work or vocation that typically requires some formal education or specialized training (Careers360 website, 2023). It could simply be referred to what you do for a living. Working experience, constant learning, productivity and professionalism often contributes to good career building and success. Academic career development is the process by which employers as well as scholars working in research, teaching, and/or administrative roles in academic or education contexts manage various tasks, behaviors, and experiences within and across jobs in a given period, with implications for scholars' work-related identity (Hannes; Cort, Tara and Daniel, 2019). Career development helps professionals develop skills for managing their careers throughout their lives and for understanding the nature of work and themselves (Bridgstock, 2009). Academic career development events help staff and students become more adept in navigating their professions and the working world, including how to get employment and advance in their jobs. (Bridgstock, Grant-Imaru and McAlpine, 2019). Training, professional certification and research are core part of academic career development. Not only do trainings expose academic practitioners to trends and new realities in their fields, it also affords them the opportunity to improve their employability skills and employment chances. Research is also seen as key component of academic career development. In fact, not only does research increase the visibility of an

academic career professional, but it forms the basis for performance and promotion appraisals of staff for most educational institutions across the world.

Today, many scholars are relying on the opportunities provided by emerging technologies to promote their research works and also engage in research collaborations. Digital platforms have made it much easier for researchers to achieve more visibility for their research publications across the world. Digital tools like video conferencing tools assist individuals and institutions to organize virtual academic workshops, seminars and conferences for professional development. Using electronic apps platforms such ZOOM App and other virtual meeting enable academics to engage in multiple career development events from the comfort of their homes. This reduces the risks, time and cost associated with travelling to attend physical events. Digital technologies help teachers and students to keep up with their skill updates and learning to be employable in fields and professions that are changing quickly (Bridgstock, Grant-Imaru and McAlpine, 2019). Considering the growing impact of digitalization, it has become more important than ever for individuals and organizations in the academic industry to improve their digital skills and invest more on technology infrastructures to enhance individual and faculty career development programmes. The elements of Academic career development are depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1:
Elements of

Academic Career Development

3. Academic Career Development Framework

Academic career development frameworks provide guidance and support to individuals pursuing careers in academia. These frameworks typically outline the various stages of an academic career and offer strategies and resources to help individuals navigate each stage successfully. According to University of StrathClyde Academic career development Framework guideline, the Academic Career Development Framework is designed to assist academics in their early careers in carrying out the duties of an academic member of staff. It strives to support early career academics in realizing their potential and building a long-term academic career, encouraging

them to become high achievers and high performers (University of StrathClyde Academic Career development Framework guideline, 2023). The University of StrathClyde Academic career development Framework guideline indicates that it aims to assist academic staff to:

- establish a career development strategy with suitable mentoring from seasoned academic colleagues that will help them excel in their roles as fast as feasible and allow them to carry out the entire spectrum of academic responsibilities related to those roles.
- Obtain regular feedback on their performance and progress against their career development plan

Take part in approved learning experiences including the postgraduate certificates in academic practice.

- Establish the range of skills and experience on which they can continue to grow a successful academic career and which will support the achievement of their career potential.

Improve their leadership and research skills to engage in quality leadership and research.

(University of StrathClyde Academic Career development Framework guideline, 2023)

4.0. Overview of Emerging Technologies

Emerging technologies (ETs) are vital resources for addressing pressing worldwide issues like sustainable development, healthcare access, and climate change. Not only are technologies like blockchain and quantum computing exciting ideas of the future, but they are also essential to building more open and effective systems. ETs improve industries by opening up new job opportunities, increasing productivity, and facilitating improved human-machine cooperation. AI, for instance, is enhancing human capabilities and opening up new career prospects rather than merely replacing occupations. These technologies have transformed various aspects of human life, including communication, business, education, healthcare, entertainment, and more (Danil et al, 2019) and expand access to career supporting resources. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development of the United Nations includes decent education as one of its core tenets. Its goal is to guarantee that every student receives an inclusive, equal education. In order to accomplish this, digital technologies have become a crucial instrument (Haleem, Mohd and Rajiv, 2022). The way people work, learn, and engage in civic life is being dramatically changed by the development of digital technologies. Career professionals have found it difficult to adjust as digital technologies become more widespread and offer chances to increase access to high-quality study and employment prospects worldwide (Brookings, 2023). It plays an integral role in academic career planning, management and development.

Emerging technologies in education open the door for new a pedagogical method that place a greater emphasis on student participation and broadens the opportunities for staff career development (Beebe, 2004). In order to meet the ongoing need for new skills among academic staff and students alike, a wide range of digital platforms and tools have arisen, including digital

badges, bootcamps, and learning management systems, all of which facilitate access to trainings and employability opportunities for stakeholders in academic sector. The most recent wave of educational innovation represents a more fundamental change in the way education and skills data are obtained and communicated in the labour market. Emerging technologies make it easier to obtain educational and labor market information, convey career information, and promote career management skills (Vuorinen and James, 2011). They are effective tools that can help academic professionals advance their careers in a number of ways, including by making it simpler for teachers to connect with mentors, attend online workshops and seminars, collaborate on research projects, and take professional certification program. In addition to being a tool, digital technologies are also a potent force for career advancement in the education industry (ELGPN, 2010). Many stakeholders in academic sector are relying on use of many digital tools and platforms learn and grow their careers. Digital technologies provide potential for academicians and students to engage in research and online education (Tulinayo, Ssentume, and Najjuma, 2018). They enable the creation, storage, processing, transmission, and display of information through services or activities that use electronic methods. All dimensions of human activity have been impacted by and restructured by digital technologies. They are deployed in certain ways that interrupt current activities, while in other ways they have a more incremental influence and enhance current activities (Ciarli, et al, 2021). Digital technologies are ubiquitous and its prospects can be leveraged by professional educators and students to promote their careers and academic profiles. Digital platforms like LinkedIn, Researchgate, Academia.edu, Google scholar, Twitter, Facebook and many electronic databases have become a strong career advancement tools for many scholars and students to share and grow their academic profiles and attract attentions to their works, skills and services. These digital tools and platforms can also help employees reach their full potential on a personal and professional level, as well as deliver the best results and success in their jobs.

4.1. Key Emerging Technologies for Academic Career Development

Some of the emerging technologies with potential impact on Academic Career Development are highlighted in figure 2.

Figure 2: Emerging technologies with potential impact on Academic

Career Development

Internet: The Internet is a global network that enables the connection of computers and devices worldwide. It facilitates the exchange of information, communication through email, instant messaging, and video conferencing, access to websites, online services, and much more.

Mobile Technology: Mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, have become integral to modern life. They provide access to the Internet, communication channels, applications, and a wide range of services. Mobile technology has revolutionized industries like e-commerce, social media, and mobile banking.

Cloud Computing: Cloud computing allows the storage, management, and processing of data and applications on remote servers accessed via the Internet. It offers scalability, flexibility, and cost-efficiency, empowering businesses and individuals to store and access their data from anywhere at any time.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): AI encompasses the development of intelligent systems that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. This includes machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, robotics, and more. AI is used in various fields, such as virtual assistants, autonomous vehicles, fraud detection, and personalized recommendations.

Internet of Things (IoT): The IoT refers to the network of interconnected devices embedded with sensors, software, and connectivity to exchange data. These devices can include smart home appliances, wearable devices, industrial sensors, and more. IoT enables automation, monitoring, and control of physical objects, improving efficiency and convenience.

Big Data: Big data involves the collection, storage, and analysis of large and complex data sets. It encompasses techniques for processing, interpreting, and deriving insights from vast amounts of structured and unstructured data. Big data analytics has applications in areas like business intelligence, healthcare, marketing, and scientific research.

Blockchain: Blockchain is a decentralized and distributed ledger technology that enables secure and transparent transactions and data storage. It provides a tamper-proof record of transactions and is primarily associated with cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin. However, it has broader applications in supply chain management, smart contracts, and secure data sharing.

Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR): VR immerses users in a simulated environment, while AR overlays virtual elements onto the real world. Both technologies have found applications in gaming, entertainment, training simulations, design, and marketing, offering unique user experiences and visualizations.

These are just a few examples of the vast array of emerging technologies shaping our world. The continuous advancement and integration of these technologies have the potential to bring about further innovation and transformation across various industries and aspects of daily life.

5. Benefits of Emerging Technologies in Shaping Academic Career Development

Digital technologies have a significant impact on academic career development, offering numerous prospects for students and professionals alike. Here are some key areas where digital technologies are enhancing academic career development:

Access to information and resources: Emerging technologies provide easy and instant access to vast amounts of information and educational resources. Students and researchers can explore a wide range of online materials, research papers, e-books, and educational videos to enhance their knowledge and skills. This easy access to information promotes continuous learning and keeps individuals up-to-date with the latest developments in their field.

Collaborative learning and networking: Disruptive technologies enable collaboration and networking among academics and students across geographic boundaries. Online platforms and tools facilitate virtual discussions, group projects, and knowledge sharing. Through online forums, social media, and professional networking platforms, individuals can connect with peers, experts, and potential collaborators, expanding their academic network and fostering collaborative opportunities (Onyema et al, 2021).

Professional development: The rise of online learning platforms and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) has provided new avenues for academic career development. Students and professionals can access high-quality courses and certifications from renowned institutions and industry experts. Also, Emerging technologies have made it possible to attend virtual conferences, webinars, and workshops remotely. This flexibility allows individuals to acquire new skills, fill knowledge gaps, and enhance their credentials while balancing other commitments. It also expands learning opportunities, enables networking with experts in the field, and allows individuals to stay updated on the latest research and industry trends, contributing to their academic and professional growth (Onyema et al, 2020; Nwobodo et al, 2015).

Research and publication opportunities: Emerging technologies have revolutionized the research and publication process. Online databases, digital libraries, and academic search engines enable researchers to access a vast array of scholarly articles and publications. Moreover, digital tools aid in conducting literature reviews, data analysis, and research collaboration. Online publishing platforms and open-access journals have also expanded the reach and visibility of research, increasing opportunities for academic recognition and impact.

Online presence and visibility:

Advanced technologies allow individuals to build their academic profile and establish an online presence through personal websites, academic profiles, and social media platforms. This digital presence enhances visibility and facilitates professional networking. Academics can showcase their research, publications, and achievements, attracting potential collaborators, mentors, and

job opportunities. Additionally, active engagement on social media platforms can help researchers stay connected with the academic community, participate in discussions, and share their expertise.

Enhanced communication and dissemination: Revolutionary technologies have transformed academic communication and dissemination. Webinars, video conferencing, and online collaboration tools enable real-time communication and remote participation in conferences, seminars, and workshops. These technologies eliminate geographic barriers and provide opportunities for global interactions and knowledge exchange. Additionally, digital platforms and social media provide channels for disseminating research findings to a wider audience, including policymakers, practitioners, and the general public.

E-learning platforms and online courses: Emerging technologies have revolutionized education through e-learning platforms and online courses (Onyema et al, 2020b). Educators and students can now access high-quality courses from renowned institutions worldwide, allowing them to acquire new skills, broaden their knowledge, and enhance their academic qualifications conveniently and at their own pace.

Career guidance and professional development: Innovative technologies provide access to career guidance resources, job portals, and professional development platforms (Vuorinen, 2006; Nwobodo et al, 2015b). These resources offer information on career pathways, job opportunities, resume building, interview preparation, and skill development, empowering individuals to make informed career choices and enhance their employability.

Data analysis: Futuristic technologies have transformed the research process especially data analysis. Advanced software tools and data analysis platforms enable researchers to collect, store, analyze, and visualize data more efficiently. This enhances the quality and depth of research, allowing for innovative findings and contributing to academic career development.

Online publishing and dissemination: Digital platforms have made it easier for researchers and academics to publish and disseminate their work. Open-access journals, preprint servers, and academic social networking platforms enable researchers to share their findings widely, increasing visibility and citation rates. This, in turn, can enhance their academic reputation and career prospects.

Career exploration and job opportunities: Digital technologies offer resources and platforms for exploring diverse career paths within academia and beyond. Online job portals, professional networking platforms, and academic career websites provide access to job opportunities, postdoctoral positions, and funding grants. Digital platforms also allow individuals to showcase their skills and experiences, increasing their chances of finding suitable positions and advancing their academic careers.

Overall, digital technologies have opened up new avenues for academic career development by enhancing access to information, promoting collaboration, facilitating learning and research, and expanding networking opportunities. Embracing these technologies can empower individuals

including educators and students to thrive in their academic pursuits and adapt to the evolving landscape of education.

6. Challenges of using Emerging Technologies for Academic Career Development

Emerging technologies have undoubtedly transformed various aspects of our lives, including academic career development. While these technologies offer numerous benefits, they also present certain challenges. Some of the challenges associated with using innovative technologies for academic career development include:

Technological barriers and accessibility issues: While emerging technologies have become increasingly ubiquitous, access and affordability remain significant challenges for many individuals, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. Not everyone has equal access to digital technology, particularly in developing regions or marginalized communities (Heitner and Jennings, 2016). Limited access to high-speed internet, computers, or other necessary digital tools can create barriers to fully leveraging the potential of these technologies for academic career development. This digital divide can create disparities in academic career development opportunities, limiting the progress of those who lack access to necessary resources.

Technical Skills and Literacy: Effectively utilizing emerging technology for academic career development requires technical skills and digital literacy. Some individuals may lack the necessary knowledge or training to navigate digital platforms, use online resources, or employ digital tools effectively.

Information Overload: The vast amount of information available through digital technology can be overwhelming. Sorting through and evaluating the credibility and relevance of online resources can be time-consuming and challenging. Additionally, the constant flow of information can be distracting, making it difficult to focus on specific academic goals.

Quality and Credibility of Online Content: The internet contains a wide range of content, varying in quality, accuracy, and reliability. Distinguishing credible and authoritative sources from misleading or inaccurate ones can be challenging. Relying solely on digital resources without proper evaluation can impact the credibility and rigor of academic work.

Digital Distractions and time Management: Emerging technologies provides numerous distractions that can hinder academic career development. Social media, online games, and other forms of digital entertainment can divert attention away from productive activities, leading to procrastination and reduced focus on academic goals. Managing these distractions and maintaining focus on academic career development goals can be challenging. It requires discipline, effective time management strategies, and the ability to prioritize tasks in the face of competing digital demands.

Isolation and Lack of Human Interaction: While emerging technologies enables remote collaboration and networking, it may also contribute to feelings of isolation. Engaging primarily with screens and digital interfaces can limit face-to-face interactions, which are essential for building relationships, mentorship, and effective communication within academia.

Privacy and Security Concerns: Engaging with digital technology involves sharing personal information and data. The potential for data breaches, online scams, and privacy violations can raise concerns about the security of academic work, research, and personal information (Onyema et al, 2021b).

Technological Dependencies and Technical Issues: Reliance on digital tools and platforms can make individuals vulnerable to technological failures or disruptions. Technical issues such as connectivity problems, system crashes, or software glitches can disrupt workflow, hinder progress, and cause frustration (Obodoeze et al, 2017).

Maintaining a work-life balance: Emerging technologies can blur the boundaries between work and personal life. With constant connectivity and the expectation of being reachable at all times, it can be challenging for teachers and students to strike a balance between their academic pursuits and personal well-beings. The pressure to be constantly available and engaged can lead to burnout and negatively impact career development.

Online presence management: Maintaining a professional online presence is crucial for academic career development. However, managing one's online presence requires careful attention to privacy settings, online reputation management, and engaging with social media in a strategic manner. This can be time-consuming and challenging, particularly for those unfamiliar with digital platforms and their nuances.

Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach that includes providing equitable access to digital resources, promoting digital literacy and skills training, encouraging critical thinking and information evaluation, fostering a balanced approach to digital usage, and prioritizing human connection and support within the academic community.

7. Conclusion

Emerging technologies offer immense prospects for academic career development, providing access to resources, promoting collaboration and networking, enhancing research capabilities, facilitating publication and dissemination, enabling skill showcase, and offering opportunities for professional growth. Embracing these technologies can greatly benefit students and professionals in their academic journeys and career advancement. However, measures have to be put in place to address its limitations.

8. Future work

We will focus on investigating the influence of specific emerging technology tools or platform on the professional development and research output of academic staff of tertiary institutions in Southeast Nigeria.

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SPOUSAL COMMUNICATION, OPENNESS AND EXTRAVERSION AS PREDICTORS OF MARITAL INSTABILITY AMONG MARRIED TEACHERS IN SAGAMU LOCAL GOVERNMENT, OGUN STATE

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Abstract

Marital instability has been a huge problem in our society from the problem of divorce, single parenting, abusive relationships, rebellious children because of lack of proper training by both parents; these problems have fueled the passion to uncover the correlation of personality types and spousal communication as predictors to marital instability.

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The research instrument was validated and reliability test was done using Cronbach alpha analysis. The population is comprised of all married teachers in public schools in Sagamu local government in Ogun state. There are a total of 924 teachers in the 24 public schools, of which 108 out of the 924 teachers are either widowed, divorced, separated or single. A sample size of 300 was generated using Yamane Formulae.

The findings showed that personality types and spousal communication do not significantly contribute to marital instability in young couples in Ogun State. $(6,274)=30.950p<.005$). Also, there was no statistically significant contribution between openness and marital instability (Beta = .029, $t = .484$, $p >.05$) and extraversion (Beta = -.049, $t = -.1.024$, $p >.05$). Lastly, there was a significant contribution of spousal communication to marital instability among young couples in Ogun State. The result revealed significant results (Beta = -.608, $t = 12.796$, $p < .005$).

Based on these findings, it could be concluded that openness, extraversion and spousal communication are predictors of marital instability. The study proposes that marital relationship with good and effective communication improves stability in marriage.

Keywords: Openness, Extraversion, Spousal communication and Marital instability

Introduction:

Marriage is one of the most important relationships between a man and a woman. It involves emotional and legal commitment that is important in any adult life. Marriage is the oldest social institution ordained by God as well as the culture of many societies as a social contract between two individuals to become husband and wife and start a family. Dessislav (2019) observes that the family is the most basic unit of society and building block for national development. Just as there cannot be any society without families, there cannot be sustainable development without stable families and these can be fostered in an environment that is free of marital instability. In the past, marital instability among couples was rare as they were not as widespread as they are today. This is due to interference by various factors such as industrialization, technological development, expansion of cities and incursion of western lifestyles into the Nigerian society. Marriage and family life have undergone major changes during the past few decades globally Gardner, (2020) as the marriage institution is witnessing instability globally at an unprecedented rate Malone-Colon, (2021).

According to Alan Booth, marital instability is defined as the gamut of activities from thinking about and discussing divorce to actually filing for either separation or divorce. It is used to describe interpersonal difficulties within the marital relationship. Marital instability may however mean different things to different scholars but is usually used to refer to the process whereby marriages break down through separation, desertion or divorce Lee, (2020). The fragility of the marital bond is a notable feature of the contemporary world. Marital instability is always an undesirable human tragedy which causes hurt and suffering to couples. It is an experience, which involves serious disruption of life at many levels. Many people who have been through the experience of marital instability liken it to the experience of bereavement Asa & Nkan, (2018). Marriage instability has hindered the growth and progress of many homes and children in Nigeria Omoniyi-Onafunke, (2022). Marital instability is always a human tragedy that is desired by no one. It causes hurt and suffering to its victims. It is an experience which involves serious disruption of life at many levels. Marital instability has become a thing associated with the contemporary family institution. This however, is not to say that it had never once occurred in marital situation of the past but that the rate at which it occurs in contemporary society is quite alarming.

Garba (2020) observes that the rate of marital instability has increased particularly in urban areas where rich people entice people's wives with their money and couples are exposed to more outside experiences. This is common in our contemporary marital institution than before. Many other factors may be responsible for the high rate of marital instability in the country. For instance, Tolorunleke (2019) avers that communication, cultural background, family type, educational attainment, childbearing, religious affiliation, type of marriage, income and age of marriage are some of the major factors responsible for marital instability. This study will examine whether personality types and spousal communication play a role in marital instability among young couples in the study area.

Personality refers to a collection of emotional, thought and behavioural patterns that are unique to each individual and relatively stable over time. Personality has been conceptualized

from a variety of theoretical perspectives and according to numerous sources. Sullivan (1953) highlighted the repetitive nature of behavioural patterns in addition to the contribution of Allport (1961), who regarded the dynamic psycho-physiological systems as responsible for individuals' typical behaviour and thoughts. Eysenck (1975) regarded personality (viz. temperament and intellect) as being observable physical characteristics of body shapes. Informed by these different perspectives, personality, for the purpose of this research, is regarded as an intra-psychic construct consisting of an integrated and dynamic organization of an individual's psychological, social, moral and physical characteristics, determined by the reciprocal interaction with the social environment.

Psychologists define personality as a dynamic concept describing the growth and development of a person's whole psychological system. Other than looking at part of the person, personality looks at some aggregate whole that is greater than the sum of the parts (Robbins, 2020). Personality is a combination of thoughts, emotions and motivation of individuals. It is an interpersonal dynamic structure which includes physical and psychological systems and the component provides individuals' thoughts and behaviour characteristics Allport, (1961).

Allport (1937) had earlier defined personality as a dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his unique adjustments to his environment. It is made up of the characteristic thoughts, feelings, and behaviours that make a person distinctive or unique. This arises from within the individual and remains fairly consistent throughout life. Personality is also defined as the dynamic organization of those traits and characteristic patterns of behaviour that are unique to the individual Callahan, (1996). It has a long-lasting feature which is not easily affected by the external interferences. Wood (2018) referred to personality as the characteristics that distinguish persons based on their unique thoughts and actions.

One of the foremost researchers in the structure of personality was Raymond Cattell who conceptualized personality as being made up of sixteen distinct personality traits Cattell, (1955). All of these theories are based loosely on Gordon Allport's trait theory of personality which identified 171 personality traits Allport, (1937). Traits have been described as generalized personality dispositions that account for regularities in the functioning of a person across situations and over time Pervin, (2015). Although Cattell's 16-factor theory of personality (16PF) reduced Allport's 171 traits to a more manageable 16, it was later found that this structure could not be reliably replicated. Eysenck (1975) introduced a more parsimonious theory consisting of only three factors. Additional research determined that this structure did not sufficiently account for variances in personality, and the five-factor model was introduced. This study adopts the five-factor model of personality.

The five-factor model is a trait-based theory of personality which is based on five dimensions and is popularly known as the Big Five: Extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience Costa & McCrae, (2010). Each of these dimensions of personality encompasses a wide range of traits. Extraversion refers to a state where individuals show more concern towards what is happening outside. It is the opposite of introversion which refers to a state when an individual is concerned only with his/her own life

and nothing else. Agreeableness is a personality trait which teaches the individual to be adjusted in almost all situations. Conscientiousness requires the individual to be sensitive to his/her conscience. Conscientious people tend to be trustworthy, self-disciplined and achievement oriented. Neuroticism refers to one's tendency to experience negative thoughts and feelings such as anxiety, hostility, impulsivity, depression and low self-esteem. Openness to experience is a trait that makes individuals to seek new knowledge, skills and experiences. People who score high on openness are quite broadminded and modern in their outlook as compared to individuals who score low on the same parameter. Such individuals are conservative, reluctant to changes and have a traditional approach in life.

Thus, people with different personality traits can have different attitudes toward different aspects of life that influence marital quality and satisfaction. Personality traits may also have important role in determining the quality of marriage among newly-wed or young couples. For example, both (low) neuroticism and (high) conscientiousness in the five-factor model predict higher quality intimate relationships Malouff, Thorsteinsson, Bhullar, & Rooke, (2021). For the five-factor model traits that reflect social behaviour more directly, agreeableness has a consistent positive association with relationship quality, whereas extraversion has a weaker and less consistent positive association (Malouff *et al.*, 2021), but some scholars found a negative association. There is disagreement on the role of personality types on marital quality.

Spousal communication, which simply refers to communication between couples, is an important means of interpersonal interactions among married people. Communication refers to a process of delivering and accepting messages. Effective spousal communication is therefore crucial for strong and healthy relationships which eventually give birth to marital stability. When communication between the couples begins to deteriorate, it means that the marriage is headed down the road to divorce. A marriage without effective communication is likely to crumble since communication is a livewire of marriage relationships or any other meaningful relationship Eseré, (2018). Problems escalate when there is no communication, and many problems are resolved when there is effective communication. For sure, communication is the key to successful marriage, and without communication no marriage can survive in this divorce-filled world we live in Jolin, (2021). Most marriages are nowadays ending in divorce as a result of lack of communication. According to Idowu and Eseré (2017), more than half of the failed relationships are due to the fact that there was a severe lack of communication between couples. In order to have a long and lasting relationship with someone, one must have excellent communication skills.

Eseré, Yusuf and Omotosho (2019) observe that marriage without effective communication is likely to crumble because communication is fundamental to any relationship, especially marital relationships. Ineffective communication in marriage, which refers to the inability of the spouses to efficiently communicate with each other, can lead to numerous marital problems such as weak emotional bonding and excessive marital conflicts which causes marital instability Eseré & Idowu, (2018); Mamak, (2020). Effective spousal communication is therefore crucial for strong and healthy relationships which eventually give birth to marital stability.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing rate of divorce and domestic violence among married couples resulting from marital instability is a source of concern to stakeholders in Nigeria which is witnessing a high rate of marital dissolution. These occurrences can harm the social, psychological, emotional, academic and economic lives of the persons affected as well as their children. Marriage is the major avenue whereby the society is populated. Thus, marital instability produces negative multiplier effects on the Nigerian society. The rate at which couples are experiencing marital instability and divorce is quite terrifying. This calls for a deep analysis of the new unacceptable way of life in order to understand their causative factors especially spousal communication and personality trait differences.

Marital instability has hindered the growth and progress of many homes and children and the society at large the effect of these cannot be over emphasized from drug addiction, armed robbery, commercial sex workers and many other criminal activity

When communication between couples becomes strained, their relationship may suffer if it is not checked in time. However, it appears that there is a dearth of empirical data on the possible predictive roles of personality types and spousal communication on marital instability among young couples in Nigeria. Besides, many studies have shown that personality types and spousal communication are important predictors of marital quality or state. However, little is known about their combined impact. Consequently, this study aims at investigating personality types and spousal communication as predictors of marital instability among young couples in Ogun State. The following hypotheses were formulated:

HO₁: There is no significance combined contribution of openness extraversion and spousal communication on marital instability among young couples in Ogun State.

HO₂: The second hypothesis states there is no significant contribution of openness and extraversion to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State.

Research Design

This study adopts the descriptive research design using the survey which will enable the researcher to collect data from a sample of the target population without manipulating either of the independent or predictor variables but measuring them as they pre-exist among the participants in this study. This is because the independent or predictor variables being investigated has already occurred and the researcher will only be interested in determining their influence on the dependent or criterion variables.

In this design, personality type and spousal communication are the independent variables, while marital instability is the dependent or criterion variable. The design will allow the researcher not only to determine the influence of each of the independent variables on the dependent variable, but also to study the joint or combined influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Results:

HO₁: There is no significance combined contribution of openness, extraversion and spousal communication on marital instability among young couples in Ogun State.

Table 1: Model summary and multiple regression coefficients for combined contribution of openness, extraversion and spousal communication on marital instability and spousal communication to marital instability.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	30.589	2.180		14.029	.000
Openness	.089	.060	.071	1.491	.137
Extraversion	- .068	.066	-.049	-1.024	.307
Spousal communication	-.581	.044	-.620	-13.214	.000
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean	F	Sig.
Regression	1094.531	3	364.84	61.184	.000
Residual	1633.98.2	274	5.963		
Total	2728.512	280			
R = .633, R ² = .401, Adj.R ² = .388, Std Error = 2.44201					

Dependent Variable: Marital Instability.

Predictors: (Constant), Spousal Communication, openness, extraversion.

This table revealed that with all the predictor variables entered into the model at the same time, there were significant results ($F_{(3,274)} = 61.184, p < .005$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that there is a significant combined contribution of personality type and spousal communication. This model is statistically significant as indicated by a large F value (61.184) and a p value of .000. This means that the independent variables in the model are collectively related to the dependent variable. The R-squared value of .401 indicates that 40.1% of the variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables in the model. The adjusted R squared value of .388 takes into account the number of independent variables in the model. The coefficient of determination (R) is .633, which means that there is a moderate positive correlation between the independent and dependent variable.

HO₂: The second hypothesis states there is no significant contribution of openness and extraversion to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State.

Table 2:Regression coefficients for contribution of Openness and Extraversion to marital instability.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	22.276	2.666		8.354	.000
Openness	.037	.076	.029	.484	.629
Extraversion	-.061	.084	-.044	-.729	.466
Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	53.352	2	10.666	1.096	.363
Residual	2675.181	272	9.728		
Total	2728.512	280			
R = 140, R ² (Adj).002, Std.Error=3.11896					

Dependent variable: Marital instability

The table above revealed non-significant results. The null hypothesis is therefore upheld, leading to the conclusion that there is no significant contribution of personality types on marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State. Specifically, openness had no significant contribution to marital instability (Beta = .029, t = .484, p > .05). Extraversion (Beta = .044, t = -.729, p > .05) had no significant contribution to marital instability. The regression model did not show statistical significance in predicting the dependent variable. This indicates that these personality traits do not have a significant impact on the dependent variables.

In conclusion, based on the results of this regression analysis, it does not appear that these personality traits, as measured by this model have a significant impact on the dependent variable. Further research may be needed to explore other potential factors that influence the dependent variable.

HO₂: There will be no significant contribution of spousal communication to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu Ogun State.

Table 2: Regression coefficients for contribution of spousal communication to marital instability.

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig
(Constant)	26.273	.643		40.844	.000
Spousal Communication	-.570	.045	-.608	-12.796	.000
Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	1009.070	1	1009.70	163.134	.000
Residual	1719.442	279	9.728		
Total	2728.512	280	6.163		
R = .608, R ² = .370, R ² (Adj) = .368, Std Error = 2.48251					

Dependent variable: Marital instability

The table above revealed significant results (Beta = -.608, t = 12.796, p < .05). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. It is subsequently concluded that there is a significant contribution of spousal communication on marital instability among teachers in Sagamu Ogun State.

The regression model shows statistical significance in predicting the dependent variable. The coefficient for spousal communication is statistically significant at p < .001, indicating that it has a significant impact on the dependent variable in this model. The negative beta value for spousal communication (-.608) suggests that as spousal communication increases, the dependent variables decrease. The t value of -12.796 further supports the significance of this relationship.

The regression model explains a substantial amount of the variation in the dependent variable as shown by the high F value and the large sum of squares for regression, this indicates that the independent variable, spousal communication is a strong predictor of the dependent variable.

Discussion of Findings

This study aimed at examining personality types and spousal communication as predictors of marital instability. The findings of this research revealed that with all the predictor variables entered into the model at the same time, there were significant results. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that there is a significant combined contribution of openness, extraversion, spousal communication on marital stability. This also shows that there is a joint contribution of the independence variables was significant. This agrees with the submission of Engel et al (2022). The findings of the work conclude that there is no significant contribution of these personality types to marital instability among teachers in Sagamu local government in Ogun State. Specifically, openness had no significant contribution to marital instability had no significant contribution to marital instability. Openness dimension could likely be described as curious, open minded, and cultured, whereas an

individual who has a low score on openness would likely be more narrow, unreflective, artistically insensitive, conservative, and conventional in his/her behaviour.

In conclusion, based on the results of this regression analysis, it does not appear that the personalities traits, as measured by this model, have a significant impact on the dependent variable. This is supported by the work of Dyrenforth et al. (2010) and Orths, (2013) specifically high levels of neuroticism were found to be negatively correlated with indicator of relationship dissatisfaction, conflict, abuse, and even relational termination. Further research may be needed to explore other potential factors that influence the dependent variable

The findings revealed significant result. It is subsequently concluded that there is a significant contribution of spousal communication on marital instability among teachers in Sagamu Ogun State. In conclusion, based on the results of this regression analysis, spousal communication has a significant impact on the dependent variable. This is supported by the work of (2008), communication is the key to a strong, healthy relationship. it allows partners to feel love and care.

Overall, the result suggest that personality traits such as openness and extraversion may have some impact on spousal communication but not necessarily on marital instability.

Conclusion

Based on the finding and discussion above, it could be concluded that personality types and spousal communication have significant relationship to marital instability. Hence, openness, extroversion and spousal communication combined together could be said to be predictors on marital instability.

Recommendation

Based on the summary and conclusion drawn from the major findings, the following recommendations are made;

There is need for self-awareness before going into marital relationship where individuals would be aware of their personality types.

There should be pre-marital counseling opportunities for pre- marital couples to be aware and equipped for the marital relationship.

The art of active listening should be encouraged and taught as a life skill to listen carefully, control the criticism, stick to the topic, give in sometimes and don't always be the focus.

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INFLUENCE OF SCHOOL EMPLOYEES' BEHAVIOUR ON STUDENTS' COMPLIANCE TO SOCIETAL NORMS IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN OGUN STATE NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Inability to comply to societal norms has brought some negative influences on the total life of students, which directly and indirectly affect the country's economy. Therefore, this study assessed the influence of school employee's behaviour on students' compliance to societal norms in selected Universities in Ogun State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and used a multi-stage sampling technique to select the 393 participants for this study. The information collected from the respondents were sorted, coded, using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics of frequency distribution mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the data and provide answers to the research questions. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 5 percent level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) The results of this study revealed that there is no significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' compliance to societal norms in the selected universities ($\beta = .038, t = .755, f = 0.570, p = .451 > .05$). The study further revealed a significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty ($\beta = .115, t = 2.281, f = 5.202, p = .023 < .05$) and moral ($\beta = .106, t = 2.098, f = 4.401, p = .037 > .05$). The study concluded that whatever change we expect in our students behaviour must start from the staff and significant others. It was recommended that parents and guardians should bridge up the communication gaps between them and their youngsters so as to understand and appreciate their nature, aspirations and yearnings. This will help in accommodating them and assist them in channeling their behaviour on the right paths.

Keywords: Employees' Behaviour, Students Compliance and Societal Norms

Introduction

Nigeria society have norms, values, principles, morals and cultural ethics which the people conform to and in relation to one another. There are diverse ethnic groups in Nigeria. The norms were appreciated among Nigerian people across the geographical regions, among the people and culture. These values, principles, and morals are transferred from one generation to

another. Okobia, and Okafor (2016) state that societal norms compliance creates a peaceful and conducive environment within the economic life, and in the industrial activities of Nigerian. The social group addresses behavioural issues and discipline individuals who go contrary to the rules and regulations. The Obas or the leaders of the society are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that the culture, the rules and regulations are preserved. Okobia, and Okafor (2016)

Strickland (2018) stated that A norm is a standard or pattern of behaviour that is considered desirable within a society or group of people in a community. It represents what is the 'normal' way of behaving in a given context. While behaviour encompasses the actual actions and conduct of individuals or group in a given society. Chineyemba, (2023) stated that good parents do not always produce good children, but devoted, dedicated, hardworking mothers, and fathers can weigh the balance in favor of decency and moral character woven into the behaviour of a child. This determines how well that child will fit into the society. Chineyemba, (2023) further claimed that Nigerians believed that wealth comes from hard work. People who possessed wealth that could not be accounted for was viewed with suspicion, the community frowns at such a person. The value of wealth is linked with accountability and transparency. It is also believed that people cannot be poor when they are hardworking (Abiona, 2016).

Regarding conduct of members of the society, Ocheje, (2017) maintained that the factors constraining the effectiveness of justice in the fight against corruption has to do with compliance to the laws. The society is moving toward freedom for individual sexual gratification and all manners of sexual self-expression that negates the acceptable standard. This has led to the prevalence of underage children becoming mothers; this has pervaded our societal moral values. Chineyemba, (2023) ascertained that dignity of labour as a cherished value has been infested with corrupt virus of quick way to success as no one wants delay in success.

The success highway code does not include hard-work anymore for most people. This accounts for the thriving illegal business called '419, Yahoo yahoo' or internet fraud and the like. Academic praise among students has become a thing of past. There are organized crimes, in our ivory towers, an organized examination by the principal or proprietor of the school to influence the enrolment. Miracle Centre Syndrome (MCS) where candidates pay exorbitantly to people who help them write their examinations is eroding the value of study has eroded the educational system of her pride. The government is not free from this allegation of erosion of our values. Insincerity, dishonesty, unfaithfulness, cheat, corruption, bribery, favoritism, irresponsibility, irresponsiveness, pen-robbery, embezzlement, harassment, organized crime and gambling, deceit, lies, exploitation, and more, have characterized the activities of the government because moral principles are no longer recognized in our country (Abiona,et..al , 2016).

Schools are the nursery of the state and where students spend most of their time. Belle (2017) observed that overpopulated learning environment; violent discipline measures from school heads; incompetent school administrators and faculties; lack of freedom to choose what course to study; discrimination; poor association from friends and corrupt teachers; are some of the factors militating against students' inability to comply to societal norms (Belle, 2017).

It is common knowledge that students are not identical in behaviors, opinions, and views. (Dagdag 2018) noted that students vary regarding physical, intellectual, social-emotional, moral, spiritual, and cultural background. There is need for teachers to acquire more skills, knowledge and values as the demand of their task and responsibilities increases, hence it is expected that

school employees inculcate the consciousness of moral values, principles, honesty, discipline, responsibility that will enhance holistic education to student as they progress in their academic pursuit (Aslam, Mohammed & Muhammad 2021).

Employee behaviour is embedded in both positive and negative behaviours. Every employee is expected to be faithful in the discharge of their responsibility. Honesty, punctuality, and regularity to work are virtue expected of school employee. Diligence in the discharge of responsibilities cannot be overemphasized. The above virtues can be listed among the positive behaviour of school employees. On the other hand, employees can display negative behaviour such as lying, lateness to work, absenteeism, stealing of the school property, dishonesty, bribery and corruption, which affect negatively affect the image of the school (Obijuru, Oguejiofor & Emenike, 2017).

Standards for healthy living create a good sense of atmosphere in the school environment. This healthy living build on rules or principles create a harmonious society, for this reason schools executives set expectations about acceptable behaviour. A positive behaviour toward maintaining high standards for work ethics usually creates a decent environment in which people take pride in the work; parents, students and community derive joy to belong. Duggan (2023) states in contract of employment there is this relationship that employers have the obligations to pay the employee agreed pay for duties and activities performed and to provide employee with job activities intellectually. School managers and educational personnel look at an employee's behavior to determine his or her ultimate productivity and contributions to the school or management objectives. In many cases, a person's behaviour is affected by his attitude.(Leonard, 2018).

Bureau (2023) School Administration Guide sees compliance as having to do with students actually obeying the rules and working towards achieving the behavioural goals factored in the rules and regulations. This principle of life virtue known as honesty and moral behaviour has been studied by other scholars. Tawiah, Amuah, Appiah, & Annan, (2022), in their study affirmed that honesty and dishonesty:, trustworthiness, frankness, authenticity, integrity, candour, probity, rectitude and incorruptibility just to mention a few. The study also revealed that, some students were found not to be honest (cheating in examination, leaving school without exeat, covering up for wrongdoing, not obeying schools' rules and regulations and so on. Employers can promote good employee behaviour with incentives. The work also revealed that in a school setting employer can contribute to positive or negative attitude in employees using incentives.

Concept of school Employee Behaviour

In every educational system, school employee is core because it is important as the establishment of the institution itself. The need for human engagement in various capacities is inevitable hence the human capital is the key to the success of educational goal achievement. School is an arena in which a variety of behaviours play out, each with a different consequence for the individuals within the organization and on the organization as a whole. Every organization has its norms and expected behaviours, language, principles and postulations by its

members, and also the employees that are in the workplace to perform at a suitable pace in order to achieve the organization's goals and objectives (Abiona et al., 2020).

Biscobing (2016) concept of compliance as a state of either being in accord with established guidelines, rules or specifications, or the process of becoming towards others and having Social norms dictate the extent to which individuals engage, and expect others to engage in some acts. Telzer (2018) maintains that people are strongly influenced by social norms even when they explicitly reject such norms, also Brennan, Eriksson, Goodin, and Southwood (2020) argue that norms have a function. Norms function to hold us accountable to each other for adherence to the principles that they cover.

Statement of Problem:

Inability to conform to societal norms has brought some negative influences on the moral life of students. These immoral behaviours directly affect the country's economy. Also, foreign investors find it scary to invest in the economy of the country because of the deplorable level of immoral and dishonesty in the country. This study aimed to examine the influence of school employees on students' compliance to societal norms in three selected Universities in Ogun State.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study was to examine the influence of school employee's behaviour on students' compliance to Honesty and Moral in selected Universities in Ogun State. The specific objectives are to:
ascertain the influence of school employees' honesty on student compliance to societal norms in the selected Universities

determine the extent to which school employees' morals influence students' compliance to societal norms in the selected Universities

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There will be no significant influence of School employees' honesty on students' discipline selected Universities.

Ho2: There will be no significant influence of school employees' moral on students' compliance to societal norms moral

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design using the survey which enable the researcher to collect data from a sample of the targeted population without manipulating either of the independent or dependent variables but measuring them as they existed among the participants in this study.

Population

The population of this study is 24000 students from the three selected universities in Ogun State. Which are as follows: Onabisi-Onabanjo University Ago-Iwoye State University, University of Agriculture Abeokuta and Babcock University Ilishan Remo. With the stratum of 300L and 400L female and male students of the three selected Universities which are considered as the respondents. This level of students were used for the study in order to reduce the difficulties that may associate with large population study.

Instrumentation

The following instrument was used for data collection in this study: Demographic Data Inventory (DDI), School Employees' Behaviour Questionnaire (SEB Q) and Societal Norm Compliance Questionnaire (SNCQ)

The Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) is a four-item instrument developed by this researcher to measure the demographic such as age, gender, level and university.

SECTION A

This section elicited responses on demographic variables of participants like such as Sex, age, level and university.

SECTION B

This section measures school employees' behaviour

Section B: Statement: from Higher Extent (5) High (4) Low Extent (3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1). Was used to assess the influence of school employees' behaviour on student compliance to societal norm by students of the three universities in Ogun State using the employees.

Section B1: Employees' Honesty

This section measures the influence of school employees' behaviour on students' compliance to societal norms. It is self-constructed by the researcher. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert-style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).

Section B2: Employees' Moral behaviour

This section tries to elicit information from students on the academic and non-academic staff behaviour to societal norms Compliance. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).

Section C 1

This section measures students' honesty.

This section measures Students' behaviour on honesty. It is self-constructed by the researcher. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Strongly agree with 5points to undecided with 1 point.

SECTION C1: students' moral.

This section elicited information from the students on their **moral** norms. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).

SECTION C2: Students' moral

This section tries to elicit information from students on their moral. It consist of 5 items on a 5 scale Likert- style response ranging from Higher Extent (5) High(4) Low Extent(3) Lower Extent (2) No Extent (1).This section contains the presentation and interpretation of results of data analysis. Preliminary analyses were conducted on data using descriptive statistics as presented in Tables 1 to 4.

The result of the analysis of the demographic variable as regards the gender of the respondents reveal that 237 (60.3%) were female and 157 (39.7%) were male. In terms of age, 292 (74.3%) aged 21-24 years, 53 (13.5%) aged 16-20 years, and 48 (12.2%) aged between 25 and 29 years.

Results:

Hypothesis One: There will be no significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty in the selected Universities

Table 1: Summary of Analysis of variance on influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty in the selected Universities

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	13.919	1.556		8.945	.000
Employees beh.	.050	.022	.115	2.281	.023
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	91.470	1	91.470	5.202	.023 ^b
Residual	6875.125	391	17.583		
Total	6966.595	392			

R = .115, R Square = .013, Adj. R Square = .011, SE = 4.193

a. Dependent Variable: Students honesty

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employees behavior

Employees' behaviour has a beta value of .115 and t-value of 2.281 significant at .023 alpha level. The calculated value of $f = 5.202$ significant at $.023 < .05$ alpha level indicated a significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' honesty in the selected Universities. Therefore, the earlier set null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate one was accepted. The implication of this result is that school employees' behaviour will have an influence on the honesty behaviour or attitude of students in the universities.

Hypothesis Two: There will be no significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' moral in selected Universities

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of variance on influence of school employees' behaviour on students' moral in the selected Universities

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	12.301	1.352		9.099	.000
Employees beh.	.040	.019	.106	2.098	.037

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	58.418	1	58.418	4.401	.037 ^b
Residual	5189.801	391	13.273		
Total	5248.219	392			

R = .106, R Square = .011, Adj. R Square = .009, SE = 3.643

a. Dependent Variable: Students moral

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employees behavior

Employees' behaviour has a beta value of .106 and t-value of 2.098 significant at .037 alpha level. The calculated value of $f = 4.401$ significant at $.037 < .05$ alpha level indicated a significant influence of school employees' behaviour on students' moral in the selected Universities. Therefore, the earlier set null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate one was accepted. The implication of this result is that school employees' behaviour will have an influence on the moral behaviour or attitude of students in the universities.

Conclusion

Within the academic community, social norms have a significant impact on how students, teachers, and other stakeholders interact and behave. These standards are a collection of unspoken guidelines and expectations that direct behavior, interaction, and communication within the educational setting.

As Nigeria continues to struggle with quality education and degree attainment, higher education administrators and policymakers seek additional evidence on the strategies and interventions designed to improve students' behavioral outcomes. This study provided a critical examination of the research on the influence of school employee's behaviour on students' compliance to societal norm.

The results of this study showed that school employees' behaviour has a significant influence on students' compliance to societal norms in the selected universities. However, employees' behaviour was found to have an influence on students' honesty and moral behaviour.

It is therefore concluded that whatever change we expect in our students behaviour must start from the staff and significant others. Since, societal norms emphasized the ability to understand the values in society about the views of good-bad, right-wrong, what individuals should and should not do in community group, it is therefore important for every parents and leaders act right in all their doings.

Recommendations

In the light of these findings, the following recommendations are hereby made towards solving the problems identified in this study.

Public enlightenment programmes should be mounted by the government [Federal, State and Local] to broaden the knowledge of the populace especially parents and significant others to understand what lies behind compliance to societal norm, young people's risk-taking behaviour and social support outside the family.

Parents and guardians should bridge-up the communication gaps between them and their youngsters so as to understand and appreciate their nature, aspirations and yearnings. This will help in accommodating them and assist them in channeling their behaviour into the right paths. Parents and teachers should also serve as good models and see to the needs of the youngsters.

It is equally recommended that educational needs in Nigeria should be comprehensively reviewed towards meeting the demands of the citizens. Training programmes should be directed at improving the students' overall life engagement in Nigeria.

It may be important to include in addition to other academic trainings, programmes aims at helping students develop emotional intelligence and resilient behaviour to enable them become a better being.

It is recommended that emotional intelligence study should be incorporated into the curriculum of the schools across the federation. In this regard, competent psychologists should be involved in the review of the curriculum for education in Nigeria.

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SUPPORT SERVICES ON QUALITY OF EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION (ECE) PROGRAMS IN KWARA STATE, NIGERIA: A MIXED-METHOD APPROACH

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of support services on the quality of early childhood education (ECE) programs in Kwara State, Nigeria. The research utilized a mixed-methods approach, combining interviews with 20 participants and a survey of 364 respondents to gather comprehensive data on the topic. The interviews provided qualitative insights into the perceptions and experiences of key stakeholders, including parents, teachers, administrators, and policymakers, regarding the role of support services in ECE. The survey, on the other hand, collected quantitative data to assess the availability, accessibility, and effectiveness of support services in ECE programs. The findings reveal that support services such as health services, nutrition services, parental involvement, professional development for teachers, and monitoring and evaluation play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State. Participants highlighted the importance of access to healthcare, nutritious meals, and opportunities for parental engagement in improving children's learning outcomes. Additionally, professional development for teachers and regular monitoring and evaluation were identified as key factors in ensuring the effectiveness of ECE programs. The study underscores the importance of prioritizing support services in ECE programs to enhance their quality and impact on children's development. The findings have implications for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders involved in ECE, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and policies to improve support services and ultimately enhance the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria.

Keywords: Support Services, Early Childhood, Education, Quality

INTRODUCTION

Early Childhood Education (ECE) plays a crucial role in laying the foundation for a child's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development. Quality ECE programs are essential for ensuring that children receive the necessary support and stimulation during their formative years (Adesuyi-Fasuyi, 2023; Lewis et. al., 2024; Yusuf, Abdulkareem & Popoola, 2023). The quality of ECE programs is influenced by various factors, one of which is the availability and effectiveness of support services. Support services encompass a wide range of interventions and

resources that are designed to enhance the quality of education provided to young children. The services include teacher training and professional development, access to educational materials and resources, parental involvement programs, health and nutrition services, and infrastructure support, among others. The support services on the quality of ECE programs has been a subject of increasing interest among researchers and policymakers (Aghnaita & Norhikmah, 2023; Alam et. al., 2020; Seymour, 2023; Sosu & Pimenta, 2023).

Despite the recognized importance of early childhood education (ECE) in laying the foundation for lifelong learning and development, the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State, is often hindered by inadequate support services. These support services encompass various aspects such as infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum development, parental involvement, and community engagement (D'Souza et. al., 2023; Gyekye-Ampofo, Opoku-Asare&Andoh, 2023; Velandia et. al., 2024).

Kwara State, located in North-Central Nigeria, is home to a diverse population with varying socio-economic backgrounds. The state has made significant strides in promoting access to ECE programs, but there remain challenges related to the quality of these programs. Understanding the impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State is crucial for informing policy decisions and improving the overall quality of early childhood education in the state (Ajadi, 2021). However, there is a lack of comprehensive empirical evidence on the specific impact of these support services on the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State, Nigeria (Kamilu, Baba & Abdulkareem, 2022). This gap in knowledge hinders the formulation of effective policies and interventions aimed at enhancing the quality of ECE in the state. This study aims to empirically investigate the impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State, Nigeria via mixed-methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have highlighted the positive impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs (Ajadi, 2021; Modise et. al., 2023; Rashid & Akkari, 2020; Yusuf, Abdulkareem & Popoola, 2023). For instance, Ogunkoya (2023) found that access to health and nutrition services in ECE programs led to improved cognitive development and academic achievement among children. Similarly, research conducted by Okunaiya and Olajide (2023) demonstrated that parental involvement in ECE programs was positively correlated with children's social and emotional development. Agarry (2022) study conducted a comprehensive assessment of support services available for ECE programs in Kwara State, Nigeria, and their impact on program quality. Findings revealed that while there were some support services in place, such as teacher training workshops and provision of learning materials, their effectiveness varied. The study identified challenges such as inadequate funding and lack of coordination among stakeholders, which hindered the provision of quality support services.

The study of Ekure (2022) explored the role of school programs in enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State via quantitative approach. Through interviews and surveys with ECE teachers and administrators, the study identified support services such as mentoring programs for teachers, parental engagement initiatives, and community outreach activities. The findings

highlighted the positive impact of these support services on program quality, including improved. Study by Olayonu (2022) examined the role of parental involvement as a support service in ECE programs in Nigeria. The study found that parental involvement positively correlated with the quality of ECE programs, leading to improved outcomes for children. This suggests that efforts to increase parental involvement can contribute significantly to enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria.

Another study by Haq and Roesminingsih (2024) investigated the impact of infrastructure and facilities on the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria. The study found that the availability of adequate infrastructure and facilities, such as classrooms, play areas, and learning materials, significantly influenced the quality of ECE programs. This highlights the importance of investing in infrastructure and facilities to improve the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria. Furthermore, a study by Joet. al. (2020) examined the impact of teacher training and professional development on the quality of ECE programs. The study found that teachers who received adequate training and professional development opportunities were more effective in delivering high-quality ECE programs. This underscores the importance of investing in teacher training and professional development to enhance the quality of ECE programs. In addition to these studies, research examined by Kamiya and Nomura (2023) highlighted the importance of government policies and regulations in shaping the quality of ECE programs. Adequate funding, regulatory frameworks, and quality assurance mechanisms are essential for ensuring high-quality ECE programs that meet the needs of children and families.

The current study is anchored on Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory. The theory is a comprehensive framework that helps us understand how various environmental systems influence an individual's development (Elliott & Davis, 2020). The theory consists of several interconnected layers, each representing a different level of influence. These layers include the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem. The microsystem is the immediate environment in which the child lives, such as family, school, and peer group. In the context of early childhood education, the microsystem includes the child's home environment and the early childhood education setting. The interactions between the child and these immediate environments play a crucial role in shaping the child's development (Nolan & Owen, 2024). For example, positive relationships with parents and teachers can foster a sense of security and support healthy development. The mesosystem refers to the connections between different parts of the child's microsystem. In early childhood education, the mesosystem includes the interactions between the family and the ECE setting. For example, effective communication between parents and teachers can enhance the child's learning experiences and overall development. The macrosystem refers to the broader cultural context in which the child lives, including societal norms, values, and beliefs. In early childhood education, the macrosystem influences the curriculum, teaching practices, and educational goals. For example, cultural beliefs about child-rearing and education may shape the expectations and practices within ECE settings. The chronosystem recognizes the importance of time in shaping development. This includes historical events, life transitions, and developmental stages. In the context of early childhood education, the chronosystem could include changes in educational policies, advancements in research on child development, or societal shifts that impact early childhood education practices (El Zaatari&Maalouf, 2022).

Research Questions

1. What are the key support services that contribute to the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State, Nigeria?
2. How do the availability and accessibility of support services affect the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State?
3. What are the challenges faced by early childhood education providers in delivering high-quality services in Kwara State?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: This study utilized a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative aspect involves a survey questionnaire administered to ECE teachers, while the qualitative aspect includes semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders such as government officials, ECE policymakers, and community leaders.

Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques: For qualitative part, the population of the study consists of parents/guardians of children enrolled in ECE programs, government officials responsible for education policy, ECE policymakers, and community leaders in Kwara State, Nigeria. For the quantitative part, the population of the study consists of 7,236 ECE teachers in Kwara State, Nigeria. Stratified, purposive and convenience techniques were used to select 20 participants (parent/guardians of enrolled children, ECE administrators and officials of Ministry of Education). In the same vein, Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table was used to determine the sample size of 364. Furthermore, the stratified, purposive and simple random techniques were adopted to select participants in ECE schools across the senatorial zones in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Instrumentation: A modified version of Yusuf, Abdulkareem and Popoola's (2023) interview protocol, dubbed the "Interview Protocol on Early Childhood Education (IPECE)," was used to gather information from participants about their views on the issues and problems related to the caliber of early childhood education programs in Kwara State. In order to gather quantitative data from participants, a structured questionnaire named "Early Childhood Education Questionnaire (ECEQ)" was modified. The questionnaire covers themes on support services offered for Early Childhood Education programs and consists of both closed-ended and Likert-scale items. Also, experts' inputs from the Departments of Early Childhood Education and Educational Management and Counselling from Kwara State University and Al-Hikmah University were taken into consideration to ensure the validity of the interview protocol and questionnaire. This was done to make sure that the survey's questions matched the study's research questions. Lastly, a pilot test was carried out with a small sample of 3 participants for the interview procedure and 50 respondents for the survey, respectively, to ensure the reliability of both the questionnaire and the interview protocol. This makes it possible to address any

doubts, misinterpretations, or problems with the questions, guaranteeing that the final versions of the protocol and questionnaire are unambiguous and simple to read.

Procedure for Data Collection: To maintain anonymity and confidentiality, informed consent was acquired from participants and respondents for the survey and interviews, respectively. The informed permission form also helps the researcher to follow moral principles and norms, putting the participants' privacy and well-being first. The participants were interviewed utilizing an audio tape recorder, jotter, laptop, biro, and digital camera. Depending on the accessibility of the participants, the survey was conducted via phone interviews, in-person meetings, and online platforms (Google Form). To guarantee uniformity, data gathering was carried out with the aid of qualified researchers.

Method of Data Analysis: To obtain deeper insights, a theme analysis was conducted on qualitative data obtained from open-ended interview questions. Additionally, using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22), descriptive statistics (such frequencies and percentages) were used to assess quantitative data. This thorough research design combines qualitative and quantitative viewpoints for a nuanced analysis, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the impact of support services on the quality of ECE programs.

RESULTS

Qualitative Approach

Transcription and data codification are indeed crucial components of qualitative research, especially in studies focusing on complex phenomena such as the impact of support services on the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State, Nigeria. Transcription involves converting audio recordings of interviews into written text, capturing verbal responses, non-verbal cues, and contextual information. This process is essential for capturing rich data and facilitating in-depth analysis. The aim of transcription is to accurately represent the interviews, preserving nuances of speech and meaning. Data codification, on the other hand, involves systematically organizing and categorizing interview data to identify patterns, themes, and insights. This process is crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the phenomena under study. In the present study, the transcription of interviews with key stakeholders in early childhood education programs in Kwara State produced a 15-page document. This transcription serves as a valuable resource for analysis and interpretation. Similarly, data codification in the study focusing on support services on the quality of early childhood education programs helps to systematically organize interview data from key stakeholders. This process facilitates the identification of patterns and themes that contribute to a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The tables depicting the codes assigned and general themes of the study are given below:

Table 1: Code Assigned to Participants

S/N	Participant	Code Assigned
1	Schools	S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, S10
2	Parents	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5
3	Officials from Ministry of Education	M1, M2, M3, M4, M5

Table 2: General Theme on Support-Services and Quality of ECE Programs in Kwara State, Nigeria

Theme One: Key Support Services for ECE Programs
<p>Teacher Training Infrastructural Service Curriculum Implementation Service Learning Material Service Health and Nutritional Service Psychosocial Service</p>
Theme Two: Availability and Accessibility of Key Support Services
<p>Availability of Support Services Accessibility of Support Services</p>
Impact of Support Services on Quality of ECE Programs
<p>Teachers' well being Increase in Pupils 'Achievement</p>
Theme Three: Challenges Associated with ECE Programs in Kwara State
<p>Inadequate Infrastructure Inadequate Qualified Teachers Inadequate Funding Limited Access</p>

Figure 1: General Model on Impact of Support Services on the Quality of ECE Programs in Kwara State, Nigeria

RESULTS

In view of the interview conducted with the participants, majority of the participants agreed that teacher training, infrastructural, curriculum implementation, learning material, health and nutritional, and psychosocial services are the key support services that are provided for ECE programs in Kwara State. Some of the views of the participants are given below:

According to S1 & S8, they opined that:

I believe that teacher training and professional development are crucial for enhancing the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State. Teachers need continuous training to keep up with the latest teaching methodologies. Curriculum development and implementation play a significant role in ensuring that children receive a well-rounded education. A well-developed curriculum can cater to the diverse needs of children."

The view of S3 is that:

Parent and community involvement are essential for the success of early childhood education programs. When parents are actively involved, children tend to perform better academically and socially. Health and nutrition services are critical for the overall well-being of children in Kwara State. Access to healthcare and nutritious meals can significantly impact a child's ability to learn and thrive. Psychosocial support is vital for

children who may be experiencing emotional or behavioral challenges. Providing a supportive environment can help children develop essential social and emotional skills. Infrastructure and learning materials are fundamental for creating a conducive learning environment. Schools need adequate facilities and resources to support quality education."

P1 and M1 opined that... "Monitoring and evaluation are necessary to assess the effectiveness of early childhood education programs. Regular assessments can help identify areas for improvement and ensure that programs are meeting their goals." S7 is of the view that... "Policy and regulatory support are essential for creating a conducive environment for early childhood education. Clear policies and regulations can help ensure that programs meet quality standards."

The figure below depicts the key support services for ECE programs in Kwara State.

Figure 2: Perception on Key Support Services for ECE programs

The views of participants regarding how availability and accessibility of support services affect the quality of ECE programs are given below:

According to S9... "The availability of support services such as teacher training and professional development can significantly enhance the quality of ECE programs in Kwara State. When teachers are well-trained, they can provide better support to young children." S8 opined that... "Accessibility to support services is crucial. If parents and communities can easily access these services, they are more likely to be involved in their children's education, which can improve the overall quality of ECE programs."

P1 and S7 are of the view that:

"Curriculum development and implementation should be accessible to all ECE programs in Kwara State. A standardized curriculum ensures that all children have access to

quality education. Health and nutrition services should be readily available to children in ECE programs. Access to these services can improve children's overall health and well-being, which can positively impact their learning.'

S4 opined that...Psychosocial support should be easily accessible to children who need it. When children have access to support services, they can better cope with emotional or behavioral challenges, which can improve their overall development."

The view of M1 and P4 are:

"Accessibility to support services is crucial for ensuring that all children in Kwara State have access to quality ECE programs. If these services are not easily accessible, some children may miss out on important educational opportunities. The availability of a standardized curriculum that is accessible to all ECE programs in Kwara State is essential for ensuring consistency and quality in early childhood education. The level of availability and accessibility of health and nutrition services can significantly impact children's health and well-being, which in turn affects their ability to learn effectively in ECE programs."

The view of M2 is that..."The availability of support services is low. However, accessible infrastructure and learning materials are crucial for creating a conducive learning environment in ECE programs. The level of availability of these resources directly affects the quality of education provided."

The figure below shows perceived availability, accessibility and impact of support-services on ECE programs.

Figure 3: Perception on Impact of Support Services on Quality of ECE programs

According to S7, he opined that:

“Parental involvement can be a challenge. Some parents may not be actively engaged in their children's education, which can impact the quality of services provided. Cultural beliefs and practices can also pose challenges. Some communities may have different views on early childhood education, which can affect the implementation of quality programs. Health and nutrition issues can impact the quality of services. Without access to proper health and nutrition services, children's overall well-being and ability to learn may be affected. Lack of government support and policies can hinder the delivery of high-quality services. Without adequate support, ECE providers may struggle to meet standards and provide quality education.”

S1: "Limited funding is a significant challenge for ECE providers. Without adequate resources, it is challenging to maintain high-quality services and meet the diverse needs of young children."

M2: "Monitoring and evaluation processes can be challenging to implement effectively. ECE providers may struggle to assess the quality of their services and identify areas for improvement."

P2: "Limited access to health and nutrition services can be a challenge for ECE providers. Ensuring that all children have access to these services can be difficult, particularly in rural areas."

S7: "Limited availability and accessibility of support services, such as monitoring and evaluation processes, can hinder ECE providers' ability to deliver high-quality services."

S8: "Limited funding is a significant challenge for ECE providers. Without adequate resources, it is challenging to maintain high-quality services and meet the diverse needs of young children."

These views highlight some of the key challenges faced by ECE providers in delivering high-quality services in Kwara State, Nigeria. These challenges include limited funding, difficulties in implementing monitoring and evaluation processes, and limited access to health and nutrition services. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving the quality of ECE programs and ensuring that all children have access to high-quality early childhood education.

Figure 4: Perception on Challenges Associated with ECE programs

Quantitative Approach

Table 3: Perception on Availability of Key Support Services for ECE Programs

S/N	Item	N	SD	D	A	SA	Remark
1	Health and Nutritional Service	356	14	33	201	108	Agreed
2	Psychosocial Service	356	28	25	191	112	Agreed
3	Learning Material Service	356	11	05	158	182	Agreed
4	Curriculum Service	356	31	18	134	173	Agreed
5	Teaching Service	356	17	32	161	156	Agreed

The table indicates that a majority of participants agree that health and nutritional services are adequate, while a smaller number disagree or strongly disagree with this statement. Also, the table suggests a range of perceptions regarding psychosocial services, learning material service, curriculum service and teaching service with a significant number of participants expressing agreement or strong agreement, but also a notable minority expressing disagreement or strong disagreement.

Table 4: Perception on Quality Support Services for ECE Programs in Kwara State

S/N	Item	N	SD	D	A	SA	Remark
1	Curriculum and Pedagogy	356	09	36	209	101	Agreed
2	Instructional Materials	356	26	21	193	116	Agreed
3	Facilities	356	154	173	21	08	Disagreed
4	Teachers	356	203	114	39	10	Disagreed

The above table suggests high number of participants who agree or strongly agree with the quality of curriculum, pedagogy, and instructional materials is a positive indicator for ECE programs in Kwara State, suggesting that these programs are likely providing a high-quality educational experience for young children. In contrast, high number of participants who strongly disagree with both the quality of teaching and facilities suggests a significant issue or concern in these areas.

Table 5: Perception on Challenges Associated with Support Services for ECE Programs in Kwara State

S/N	Item	N	SD	D	A	SA	Remark
1	Inadequate Qualified Teachers	356	02	14	128	212	Agreed
2	Limited Access	356	12	32	171	151	Agreed
3	Inadequate Funding	356	28	21	181	126	Agreed
4	Inadequate Infrastructure	356	-	19	235	102	Agreed
5	Inadequate Learning Materials	356	-	-	169	187	Agreed

The number of participants who agree or strongly agree that children have limited access to ECE programs also highlights a perceived issue in Kwara State. Limited access can be due to various factors such as geographical location, affordability, and availability of ECE facilities. Also, high number of participants agreed that funding, inadequate access to learning materials and inadequate infrastructure for ECE programs in Kwara State is insufficient.

DISCUSSION

In view of the first research question, which based on key support services that contribute to the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State, Nigeria. Evidence from interviews and survey conducted reveal that access to healthcare services, including regular check-ups and immunizations, is crucial for ensuring the well-being of young children in ECE programs. Results indicate that training and professional development opportunities for teachers are critical for improving teaching practices and staying updated with current trends in early childhood education. In addition, evidence from both methods indicate that psychosocial social service, learning material service and infrastructural service are key services that are needed for

ECE programs. The findings coincide with the study of Ajadi (2021) who found that access to health services, including regular check-ups and vaccinations, positively influenced children's attendance and participation in ECE programs. The study of Yusuf, Abdulkareem and Popoola (2023) highlighted the importance of providing nutritious meals and snacks to children in ECE programs, as it was found to positively impact their health and cognitive development. Ogunkoya (2023) found that parents who were actively involved in their child's education, such as attending parent-teacher meetings and volunteering in school activities, had children who performed better academically and socially.

The second research question was based on how the availability, accessibility and impact of support services affect the quality of early childhood education programs in Kwara State. Evidence from the interviews conducted reveal that support services, such as learning material, psychosocial and health and nutrition services are available and accessible for children in schools. In contrast, evidence from survey indicate that some of the quality of the support services such as infrastructure and teachers are very low. Ekure (2022) explored the availability and accessibility of early childhood care and education (ECCE) services in Nigeria. The study found that while there has been an increase in the number of ECCE centers in the country, many children still lack access to quality ECCE services, particularly in rural areas. The study of Okunaiya and Olajide (2023) examined the availability and utilization of ECE facilities in Nigeria. Findings indicate that while there is an increase in the number of ECE facilities, many are underutilized due to factors such as location, affordability, and quality of services. Olayonu (2022) assessed the availability and accessibility of ECE. Results revealed that while there is a high availability of ECE centers, many are not accessible to children from marginalized communities, emphasizing the need for inclusive policies. The finding is also in tandem with ecosystem theory, which provides a comprehensive framework that helps us understand how various environmental systems influence an individual's development (Elliott & Davis, 2020).

The third research question of the study was based on challenges faced by early childhood education providers in delivering high-quality services in Kwara State. Evidence from interview and survey reveal that challenges such as limited access, inadequate qualified teachers, and inadequate learning materials hindered ECE programs. Wong et. al. (023) examined the challenges facing early childhood education, including issues related to funding, infrastructure, and teacher quality. The study found that while there has been some progress in expanding access to ECE in Nigeria, significant challenges remain in ensuring quality and equitable access for all children. Von Suchodoletzet. al. (2023) examined an overview of the development of early childhood education, highlighting key milestones and challenges. The study emphasized the need for increased investment in ECE, particularly in terms of funding, infrastructure, and teacher training, to improve the availability and accessibility of ECE services in the country.

CONCLUSION

The study on the impact of support services on the quality of early childhood education (ECE) programs in Nigeria, with a focus on Kwara State, provides valuable insights into the factors that contribute to the effectiveness of ECE programs. Through empirical evidence and participant views, several key findings have emerged. Firstly, the availability and accessibility of support

services, such as teacher training, curriculum development, health and nutrition services, infrastructure, and psychosocial support, play a crucial role in enhancing the quality of ECE programs. These services are essential for creating a conducive learning environment and meeting the diverse needs of young children. Secondly, the level of availability and accessibility of these support services significantly impacts the quality of ECE programs. Limited availability and accessibility can hinder the effectiveness of programs and negatively impact children's learning and development. Thirdly, challenges such as the lack of trained and qualified teachers, limited access to resources, funding constraints, parental involvement, cultural beliefs and practices, and inadequate government support pose significant barriers to delivering high-quality ECE services. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including increased investment in ECE, improved teacher training, better infrastructure, and greater community involvement and awareness. In conclusion, the study highlights the importance of support services in enhancing the quality of ECE programs in Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State. By addressing the challenges and ensuring the availability and accessibility of support services, stakeholders can work towards improving the overall quality of early childhood education and promoting the holistic development of young children.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

There is need to enhance teacher training programs to ensure that ECE teachers are well-equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to deliver high-quality education.

Government need to implement strategies to increase parental and community involvement in ECE programs, such as parent education workshops and community outreach programs.

There is need for government to develop and implement a robust and culturally relevant curriculum that meets the needs of young children in Kwara State, with a focus on play-based learning and holistic development.

There is need to ensure that all ECE programs have access to adequate health and nutrition services, including regular health check-ups and nutritious meals for children.

Government must ensure Implement psychosocial support programs for children and families in ECE programs, including counseling services and support groups.

Government and other stakeholders need to Invest in improving infrastructure and providing adequate learning materials in ECE centers to create a conducive learning environment.

Implementation of regular monitoring and evaluation processes to assess the quality and effectiveness of ECE programs, and use the findings to make improvements.

Government need to allocate more funding to ECE programs to ensure that they have the resources needed to provide high-quality education and support services.

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TRAINING AS A PANACEA TO JOB PERFORMANCE. A STUDY OF SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN OGUN STATE. NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Job performance among university lecturers has always been a major challenge. This paper therefore explores training as a panacea to job performance. A study of selected universities in Ogun State using the descriptive survey design. A sample of 363 lecturers was selected through the stratified random sampling technique. Instruments used for data collection were the Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) and Training and Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). Three hypotheses were formulated and tested by means of the simple linear regression analysis at the .05 level of significance. Results revealed a significant influence of training on teaching quality ($\beta = .267, t = 14.006, p < .0005$), research productivity ($\beta = .203, t = 12.174, p < .0005$) and performance of administrative tasks ($\beta = .187, t = 9.317, p < .0005$) among university lecturers in Ogun State. It was subsequently recommended, among other things, that universities should prioritize and invest in comprehensive training and development initiatives for lecturers.

Keywords: *training, panacea, job performance, teaching quality, research productivity*

Introduction

Job performance among university lecturers has always been a major challenge. It is believed that employee's job performance is crucial and instrumental to the growth, profitability and achievement to organizational objectives. Job performance among university lecturers is a topic of great significance, as it directly impacts the quality of education and academic outcomes. Ogun State, located in Nigeria, is known for its thriving higher educational institutions. The state is known for its significant number of universities, making it an appropriate area of focus for this study. Understanding the factors that influence job performance among university lecturers in Ogun State is crucial for improving educational standards and fostering professional growth.

According to Ojo (2019), job performance is a multidimensional phenomenon whose elements include effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, quality and behaviour. It is clear that when workers' skills, attitude and knowledge are improved upon, it leads to efficient and

effective delivery on the job. Job performance has been found to predict important outcomes for individuals and organizations. Understanding the complexities of job performance is vital for organizations to effectively manage and enhance employee productivity and organizational success.

University education can, therefore, be considered a platform on which the future development of a nation rests (Hassan, 2017). According to Hassan (2015), university in Nigeria was established to create and spread knowledge and skills among students and other members of the societies. To attain this goal, there is need for adequate and efficient staff. Thus, it is crucial to train and develop staff in order to adapt to the new dynamism in technology in achieving the stated goals of university education. Training is at the heart of employee utilization, commitment, improved productivity, motivation and growth, and very essential for improved organizational productivity. The effect of staff training and development on employee's productivity and job performance has attracted considerable interest in analytical and empirical literature. Employee's training and development has been recognized as a crucial part of any competent management (Stephen, 2020). Staff development or human resource development refers to the improvement in knowledge, skills, attitudes and endowment of the labour force so as to bring about sustainable economic growth.

Training is very vital to job productivity and organizational performance. While few individuals may have the requisite skills, knowledge, abilities and competencies needed to fit into a specific job function, some others may require extensive training to acquire the necessary skills to be able to fit in a specific job function and also make significant contribution to the organization's performance. Lack of staff training and development may therefore lead to failure in accomplishing defined task.

Onasanya (2015) asserts that staff development as a form of specialized education aimed at giving the employee a particular or specialized knowledge, skill and attitude which he must possess to effectively perform in a given position while development is concerned with specific programmes designed to prepare and groom a worker with particular education and training for higher responsibilities. For instance, in the universities, there is need for a continuous and regular involvement by academic and non-academic personnel in staff development programmes that will enhance their skills and knowledge in order to be effective and efficient in task delivery. Such programmes include seminars, workshops among others.

Training is critical for enhancing employee competencies and capabilities, directly influencing job performance. In the context of universities, where the quality of education and research output heavily relies on faculty performance, investigating the impact of training and development on job performance becomes imperative. Chênevert, Vandenberghe, and Doucet (2020) observe that universities are increasingly operating in a competitive environment where attracting and retaining talented faculty members is crucial. Effective training and development programmes can serve as a strategic tool for universities to enhance faculty job satisfaction, productivity and ultimately, the competitive advantage of the institution. Research by Aggarwal and Thakur (2020) emphasizes the positive relationship between employee job performance and organizational effectiveness. By investigating the determinants of job performance, particularly

staff training and development, this study contributes to the understanding of factors influencing the overall effectiveness and success of universities in Ogun State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested in this study.

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of training on teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of training on research productivity among university lecturers in Ogun State.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of training on performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Methods

Design and Participants

This study adopted the descriptive survey design which enabled the researcher to collect data from a cross-section of the target population without manipulating the predictor variable (staff training and development) but measuring them as they pre-exist among the participants. The population of the study comprises of all the 5,930 academic staff of both the private and public universities in Ogun State, Nigeria. A sample of 375 lecturers, determined by the Taro Yamane's formula, was selected through the stratified random sampling technique.

Instrumentation

The instruments used for data collection in this study included Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) that measured type of university, gender, age, rank and work experience and a questionnaire, and a questionnaire titled "Staff Training and Development and Job Performance Questionnaire" (STDJPQ). The STDJPQ consists of 37 items in a 4-point Likert scale format. It has two sections. The first section measures Job Performance, while the second section measures Staff Training and Development. The Job Performance sub-scale consists of 20 items, while the Training sub-scale consists of 15 items. The response format on this instrument ranges from 1 = strongly disagree to 4 = strongly agree. Sample items on the scale include the following:

- *Actively engaging students in the learning process during lectures and classes.*
- *The university does not provide financial support or grants for staff to pursue further education or professional certifications.*

A pilot test was carried out using test–retest method of reliability assessment by administering the instruments on 20 respondents from one public and one private Universities (Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-Ode and Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo respectively) at interval of two weeks to determine the stability of the items constituting the questionnaire. The responses of these 20 respondents on both occasions were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. The correlation coefficient obtained from the instruments yielded 0.73 and 0.76 for Job Performance sub-scale and Staff Training and Development sub-scale respectively. These reliability coefficients indicate that the reliability of the instrument is substantial and good enough for use for this study. In order to ascertain the content validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was given to three other experts in the fields of personnel psychology, management science and test and measurement for scrutiny and vetting. These experts made valuable corrections and suggestions which were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument.

Method of Data Analysis

The demographic data of participants were analyzed by means of frequency counts and percentage. Each of the hypotheses was tested using simple linear regression analysis at the .05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant influence of training n teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Table 1: Coefficients of the Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Influence of Training on Teaching Quality

	B	Std Error	β	T	Sig.
(Constant)	9.416	4.362		21.042	.000
Staff training and development	.119	.0184	.267	14.006	.000

Dependent Variable: Teaching Quality

Table 1 revealed significant results ($\beta = .267$, $t = 14.006$, $p < .0005$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant influence of staff training and development on teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of training on research productivity among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Table 2: Coefficients of the Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Influence of Training on Research Productivity

	B	Std Error	β	T	Sig.
(Constant)	5.783	5.185		21.042	.000
Staff training and development	.126	.016	.203	12.174	.000

Dependent Variable: Research Productivity

Table 2 revealed significant results ($\beta = .203$, $t = 12.174$, $p < .0005$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant influence of staff training and development on research productivity among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant influence of training on performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Table 3: Coefficients of the Simple Linear Regression Analysis for Influence of Training on Performance of Administrative Tasks

	B	Std Error	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	10.581	3.447		21.042	.000
Staff training and development	.142	.022	.187	9.317	.000

Dependent Variable: Performance of Administrative Tasks

Table 3 revealed significant results ($\beta = .187$, $t = 9.317$, $p < .0005$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant influence of training on performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers in Ogun State.

Discussion:

The outcome of this study revealed that the majority of respondents performed their jobs well and at a high level. This implied that there might be additional elements, such as school motivation and tone that improve lecturers' job performance. Ghalawat, Kiran & Kumari (2020) discovered that the majority of teachers are highly productive in their teaching, which lends credence to this study. Since the main goal of teaching is to bring about desired change in learners, the study also found that using effective teaching methods results in better performance from students. According to the study, secondary school teachers use a variety of instructional strategies to encourage students to learn. Research suggests that using a combination of instructional methods, including lectures, discussions, cooperative learning, hands-on activities, and technology integration, can enhance student engagement.

The study's findings showed that university lecturers at a few chosen universities in Ogun State, Nigeria, had a good degree of training and development. From this, it can be concluded in

general that university lecturers have good, encouraging, and satisfactory levels of training and development. According to Habib, Zahra & Mushtaq (2015) training boosts self-efficacy and improves job performance. Thus, this study lend support to that of Ibrahim, Boerhannoeddin, & Bakare (2017) who reported that training helps staff members develop better abilities, attitudes, and knowledge to perform better. Enhancing employee knowledge, skills, abilities, competencies, and behavior through training has been demonstrated to benefit organizations and employees by improving performance.

Summary

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the impact of training on various aspects of job performance among university lecturers in selected universities in Ogun State.

Conclusion

Firstly, the study found a significant positive influence of training on teaching quality among university lecturers in Ogun State. This implies that when lecturers undergo training programmes, they are better equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills and resources to deliver high-quality teaching. This finding underscores the importance of investing in continuous professional development for educators to enhance the overall educational experience for students.

Secondly, another significant finding of the study is the positive impact of training on research productivity among university lecturers. This suggests that training initiative not only contribute to improved teaching quality but also stimulate research output among academic staff. By providing opportunities for research-focused training and skill development, universities can foster a culture of innovation and academic excellence, thereby enhancing their research capabilities and scholarly output.

Finally, the study revealed a significant positive influence of training on the performance of administrative tasks among university lecturers. Effective administrative skills are essential for managing academic responsibilities, coordinating activities and ensuring efficient operation of academic departments or units. By investing in training programmes that target administrative skills development, universities can enhance the overall efficiency and effectiveness of their academic operations. In a nutshell, these findings highlight the multifaceted benefits of training initiative in the context of higher education institutions. By investing in continuous learning and professional growth opportunities for academic staff, universities in Ogun State can not only improve teaching quality and research productivity but also enhance administrative performance, ultimately contributing to the overall advancement and success of the institutions. Furthermore, these findings underscore the importance of incorporating training and development programmes as integral components of institutional strategies aimed at enhancing job performance and fostering a conducive environment for academic excellence.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made/

Universities should prioritize and invest in comprehensive training initiative for staff. This programme should be designed to address the specific needs and challenges faced by academic staff in their respective roles. Furthermore, universities should consider expanding the range of training offerings to cover a broad spectrum of topics, including pedagogical techniques, research methodologies, academic writing, time management and leadership skills.

Universities should foster a supportive environment that encourages continuous learning and professional growth among academic staff. This can be achieved by establishing mechanisms for ongoing assessment of training needs, providing access to diverse learning opportunities, such as workshops, seminars, conferences, online courses and mentoring programmes. Additionally, universities should recognize and reward faculty members who actively engage in professional development activities and demonstrate improvements in teaching, research and administrative performance as a result.

To ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of training effort, universities should integrate this initiative into their institutional policies and practices. This may involve incorporating training requirements into faculty development plans, allocating dedicated resources for training programmes in the annual budget and establishing clear guidelines for evaluating the impact of training on job performance. Moreover, universities should involve academic staff in the decision-making process regarding the development and implementation of training initiatives to ensure relevance and acceptance from stakeholders.

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**ORGANISATIONAL SUPPORT AND WORKLOAD AS CORRELATES TO
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF UNIVERSITY EMPLOYEES IN OGUN STATE,
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of organizational support and workload on the psychology well – being university employees in Ogun state. The study adopted the descriptive research design of survey type and a total of 325 university employees were selected as samples through the stratified random sampling technique for or the study. A research question and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument used were Demographic Data Inventory (DDI). Organisational Support Questionnaire (OSQ), Workload Sub-Scale of the Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS – W), Ryff’s Psychological Well-Being Scale — Short Form (PWBS-SF). The results showed that organizational support accounted for a large fraction (74.6%) of the variation in psychological well-being. Additionally, workload accounted for significant portion (30.2%) of the variance in psychological well-being. The study discovered a significant combined influence of organizational support and workload on psychological well-being of university employees. Together, organizational support and workload jointly accounted for a substantial portion (81.8%) of the variance in psychological well-being. The result of findings on also revealed significant results (Beta = .864, $t = 29.577$, $p < .0005$). This however indicated that an increase in organizational support is associated with an increase in psychological well-being. Ho is therefore rejected. The result of also revealed that organizational support contributed 74.6% of the variance in psychological well-being (Adj. $R^2 = .746$). The result also revealed that workload contributed 30.2% of the variance in psychological well-being (Adj. $R^2 = .302$). The result of findings revealed significant results (Beta = -.551, $t = 11.369$, $p < .0005$). This however indicated that an increase in workload is associated with a decrease in psychological well-being. Ho is therefore rejected. The result of findings on table 5 revealed significant results ($F_{2, 295} = 669.651$, $p < .0005$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. These findings were adequately discussed in relation to the positions of other researchers and appropriate recommendations were made.

Introduction

In the dynamic and demanding environment of higher education institutions, the well-being of university employees is a critical factor affecting their job performance and overall satisfaction. Organizational support and workload are two fundamental aspects that significantly influence the well-being of employees within academic settings. It is essential to understand the intricate relationship between the support provided by the organization and the workload employees experience concerning their well-being.

The correlation between organizational support, workload, and employee well-being is a complex and crucial area of study, particularly within the unique context of university settings. Universities serve as hubs of knowledge creation and dissemination, where the well-being of employees directly impacts the quality of education and research outcomes. Exploring how organizational support and workload levels correlate with the well-being of university employees is essential for creating a supportive work environment that enhances employee satisfaction and productivity.

This research aims to investigate the impact of organizational support and workload on the well-being of university employees, seeking to uncover insights that can inform strategies and interventions to promote a healthier and more positive work environment. By examining these factors within the specific context of university settings, this study intends to contribute valuable knowledge to the field of organizational psychology and human resources management. Ultimately, understanding the dynamics of organizational support, workload, and employee well-being can pave the way for enhancing the quality of work life for university employees and fostering a culture of well-being and success within academic institutions.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There will be no significant influence of organizational support on the psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun state.

HO₂: There will be no significant influence of workload on the psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun state.

HO₃: There will be no significant combined influence of occupational stress factors (organizational support and workload) on the psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun state.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive survey design to collect data from university employees in Ogun State, focusing on the influence of organizational support, workload, and psychological well-being. The data was collected through questionnaires, allowing the researcher to determine both the joint and relative influence of these variables on the dependent variable. The respondents provided first-hand information about their experiences and perceptions.

Population

The population of the study comprised of the academic and non-academic university employees working in the federal, state, and private universities located in Ogun state. The total number of participants was 325 university employees.

Sample and sampling technique

A sample of 325 university employees, representing 5% of the population, was selected using stratified random sampling. The sample was divided into three strata based on university type in Ogun State, Nigeria: Federal, State, and private universities. A university was selected from each stratum using simple random sampling, with the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta being the only federal university. The sample was then proportional simple random sampling, ensuring equal representation of university employees and ensuring equal probability of inclusion.

Instrumentation

Four instruments were employed to carry out the study. Demographic Data Inventory, Organizational Support Questionnaire, Workload Sub-Scale of the Job Satisfaction Scale, and Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale. These instruments were appropriate because they have been found to have high degrees of reliability and validity and have been found to be suitable for quantifying the variables of this study, namely, organisational support, workload and psychological well-being. These scales were efficient for collecting data from a large number of participants in a standardized manner. They were also appropriate for capturing a broad range of experiences and perceptions across a large sample.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher obtained an introduction letter from the Department of Education, Babcock University and proceeded to visit the chosen universities with her research assistant to obtain authorization and familiarization for the study. As a result of efficient coordination, distribution and collection, the 325 questionnaires were retrieved.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of frequency count, and percentage, mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were analyzed using simple linear regression analysis and multiple regression analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1

HO₁: There will be no significant influence of organizational support on psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun State.

Table 1: Model Summary and Coefficients of the simple linear regression analysis for influence of organizational support on psychological well-being

		<i>B</i>	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22.383	1.143		19.588	.000
	organizational support	.646	.022	.864	29.577	.000
Model		Sum of Squares	<i>Df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	Sig.
1	Regression	3379.450	1	3379.450	874.770	.000 ^b
	Residual	1143.520	296	3.863		
	Total	4522.970	297			
$R = .864$, R Square = .747, Adjusted R Square = .746, Std. Error of the Estimate = 1.96551 Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-Being						

Table 1 revealed significant results (Beta = .864, $t = 29.577$, $p < .0005$). This however indicated that an increase in organizational support is associated with an increase in psychological well-being. Ho is therefore rejected. Table 1 also revealed that organizational support contributed 74.6% of the variance in psychological well-being ($Adj. R^2 = .746$).

Hypothesis 2

There will be no significant influence of workload on psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun State.

Table 2: Model Summary and Coefficients of the simple linear regression analysis for influence of workload on psychological well-being

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	Sig.
	<i>B</i>	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	63.607	.694		91.594	.000
workload	-.507	.045	-.551	-11.369	.000
Model	Sum of Squares	<i>Df</i>	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	Sig.
1 Regression	1374.725	1	1374.725	129.253	.000 ^b
Residual	3148.245	296	10.636		
Total	4522.970	297			

$R = .551$, R Square = .304, Adjusted R Square = .302, Std. Error of the Estimate = 3.26128
Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-Being

Table 2 revealed significant results (Beta = $-.551$, $t = 11.369$, $p < .0005$). This however indicated that an increase in workload is associated with a decrease in psychological well-being. H_0 is therefore rejected. Table 3 also revealed that workload contributed 30.2% of the variance in psychological well-being ($Adj. R^2 = .302$).

Hypothesis 3

There will be no significant combined influence of organizational support and workload on psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun State.

Table 3: Model Summary and Coefficients of the multiple regression analysis for influence of organizational support and workload on psychological well-being

		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	30.189	1.205		25.063	.000
	Organizational Support	.572	.020	.765	29.027	.000
	Workload	-.263	.024	-.287	-10.872	.000
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3706.550	2	1853.275	669.651	.000 ^b
	Residual	816.420	295	2.768		
	Total	4522.970	297			
R = .905, R Square = .819, Adjusted R Square = .818, Std. Error of the Estimate = 1.66359						
Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-Being						
Predictors: (Constant), Workload, Organizational Support						

Table 3 revealed significant results ($F_{(2, 295)} = 669.651, p < .0005$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Table 5 revealed that whereas organizational support is positively associated with psychological well-being (Beta = .765), workload is negatively associated with psychological well-being (Beta = -.287). Table 5 also showed that both organizational support and workload jointly contributed 81.8% of the variance in psychological well-being ($Adj. R^2 = .818$).

Discussions

The analysis here shows that increase in organizational support is positively related to increase in psychology well-being. The value provided supports this relationship. In addition, the rejection of the null hypothesis shows enough evidence to conclude that organisational support influences psychological well-being because organisational support accounts for about (74.6%) of the variability observed in Psychological well-being scores as denoted by the adjusted R-squared value of 0.746). This highlights the importance of organisational support as it contributes to and fosters positive psychology well-being outcomes. This suggests that enhancing organisational support systems can have profound impact on promoting psychological well-being among

university employees. These findings underscore the critical role of organizational support in enhancing the psychological well-being of employees.

These findings align with existing research indicating that supportive work environments contribute positively to employees' mental health. This finding corroborated Akintayo and Oyewole (2020) who investigated the influence of perceived organizational support on the well-being of university employees, and found that a supportive work environment mitigates the negative effects of stress and enhances psychological well-being.

The second hypothesis was rejected, there's enough evidence to suggest that there is a significant relationship between workload and psychological well-being, since table 2 shows and that workload accounts for 30.2% of the variation observed in Psychological well-being, the 0.302 means that workload is a statistically significant predictor of psychological well-being. The implication is that changes in workload = changes in Psychological well-being. This also highlights the importance of managing and understanding workload to support psychological well-being outcomes. This finding agreed with that of Denedra and Rahyuda (2019) who found that heavy workload has always been linked to a negative impact on employees' psychological and physical health. This finding also agreed with Akinbode (2018) who found that factors such as heavy workload, among others, contribute significantly to the stress levels among academic and non-academic staff, and increased stress level has been known to decrease psychological well-being. Thus, high stress levels caused by high workload may have negative effects on the psychological well-being, physical health and work performance of individuals.

The third hypothesis revealed that the null hypothesis was rejected and this suggests that there is a meaningful relationship btw the variables being studied. It was found out that organisational support has a positive relationship of (Beta = 0.765), while workload has a negative association of (Beta = 0.287) with psychological well-being. This implies that higher level of organizational support are linked with improved psychological well-being, while increased workload is tied to lower psychological well-being. Table 5 also indicates that both organisational support and workload together explain a huge portion of (81.8%) of the variability observed in Psychological well-being scores and this is shown by the adjusted R-squared value of 0.818). By understanding these relationships, university authorities can focus on enhancing support systems and managing workloads to positively influence the psychological well-being of their employees. Adefemi (2022) who found that both high organizational support and optimal workload positively influenced job performance and psychological well-being, and that employees who benefited from supportive work environments and had manageable workloads exhibited higher levels of engagement, motivation, and psychological resilience.

Conclusion

The findings from this study provided valuable insights into the factors influencing the psychological well-being of university employees in Ogun State, Nigeria. The participant's level of psychological wellbeing in the study confirmed the significant positive impact of organizational support on psychological well-being. A higher level of support from the organization was strongly associated with increased psychological well-being among employees.

This highlighted the importance of fostering supportive work environments to enhance the mental health and overall well-being of university employees. Importantly, the study revealed that both organizational support and workload collectively exerted a substantial influence on employees' psychological well-being. While organizational support positively contributed to psychological well-being, the negative impact of workload cannot be overlooked. Together, these factors explained a significant portion of the variance in psychological well-being among university employees.

Recommendations

The recommendations provided focused on three key areas that universities should prioritize for the well-being of their employees. First, it is crucial for university authorities to establish and enhance supportive systems that create a positive work environment. This involves implementing mentorship programs, counseling services, and fostering open communication and mutual respect. Investing in training programs for managers to improve their leadership skills can further contribute to a supportive workplace culture.

Secondly, addressing workload concerns is essential. University authorities should implement effective workload management strategies by conducting assessments to identify workload issues, redistributing tasks evenly, and providing resources and support to manage workload demands. Promoting work-life balance initiatives such as flexible work arrangements can also help in creating a manageable workload for employees.

Lastly, university authorities should prioritize stress management programs to help employees cope with occupational stress effectively. These may include stress awareness workshops, relaxation techniques training, and resilience-building activities. Encouraging a culture of self-care and emphasizing the importance of mental and physical health can further support employees in reducing the negative impact of stress on their overall well-being. By focusing on these recommendations, they can create a more supportive and healthy work environment for their employees.

By prioritizing employee well-being, organizations can create a win-win situation that benefits both the employees and the organization as a whole.

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FLEXIBILITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF LIBRARY DESIGN IN LAGOS STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract

Libraries, whether in educational institutions or public spaces, serve as crucial centres for knowledge dissemination and personal development, offering diverse materials and services to meet the needs of users and promote societal advancement. Specifically, university libraries are at the heart of academic life, where they gather, sort, and distribute informational resources. They also offer tailored services that align with their parent institutions' goals, aiding in the achievement of students' and faculty members' educational and research objectives. This study aims to carry out a comparative study of the flexibility and functionality of library design in Lagos state Nigeria. The objectives of this paper are: to study different definitions from several authors to have a broad base understanding of the usage, and to examine the concept of flexibility and functionality in architecture. Which are crucial for adapting the evolving user needs and market fluctuations, involving both active and natural flexible elements in design. Libraries, as dynamic centres in the twenty-first century, require flexible spaces with mobile furnishings to accommodate changing technological and user demands. Both psychologically and physically, flexibility plays a vital role in library design, allowing for a willingness to change and adaptability in the face of evolving needs. Libraries must consider layout and service flexibility to effectively respond to population growth, demographic shifts, and changing service requirements. The design of libraries involves considerations such as appropriate furniture, green initiatives, and accessibility features, aiming to enhance functionality, attractiveness, and energy efficiency. Academic libraries, seen as essential components of educational institutions, require careful design for individual flexibility, variety, and personalization. The architectural vision and management of building processes are crucial for achieving effective library functionality.

Keywords: Flexibility in library, functionality in library, library architecture, library design and user experience.

1.0 Introduction

This article embarks on a comprehensive exploration of library design in Lagos State, Nigeria, delving into the nuanced aspects of flexibility and functionality. A library is characterized as a (Oni & Adomi, 2023) communal area that is heavily staffed with knowledgeable professionals. It's an establishment that excels in the acquisition, organization, preservation, and dissemination of documents, and it promotes the application of science, culture, and education Gu & Tanoue, (2022). Zheng et al., (2022) said that the library is depicted as a communal space where educators and learners engage in study. The university library, with its high concentration of staff and substantial foot traffic, is a prime example of such a venue. Jahangir et al., (2021) recognized that university libraries are seen as the core of universities due to their pivotal role for students and researchers. Additionally, it's stated that the primary duty of university libraries is to foster research setting that aids students and researchers in expanding their understanding. In order to efficiently use information in the academic community, services such as collection, storage, and dissemination are required. Librarians and library personnel provide these services in the circulation, acquisition, cataloguing, serial, and reference departments to meet the needs and interests of their clients. Khairunnisyah et al., (2023) described the school library as one of the educational tools that schools use to assist instruction, thus it is important to treat it seriously. The duties of the school library include providing knowledge, promoting moral education, executing thoughtful instruction, and assisting students in developing their entire selves. Dobrovolska et al., (2022); Lisbdnetwork, (2014) said that a library is characterized as a place where items of literary, musical, artistic, or reference nature (like books, manuscripts, records, or films) are kept for utilization but are not available for purchase. American Library Association, (2022) & Library, (2019) said that a library is a collection of resources in various formats, organized by information experts or other professionals who provide convenient access to these resources in physical, digital, bibliographic, or intellectual forms. It also offers tailored services and activities aimed at enlightening, educating, or entertaining a variety of audiences, while also fostering personal development and societal progress. Hence, a library can be defined as a building, room, or institution that contains a collection of books, documents, music, and sometimes tools or artwork, which people can borrow at no cost (American Library Association, 2022). Britannica, (n.d.) said that a library is described as an assembly of books intended for reading or studying, and the building or area that accommodates this collection. Also the same source (Britannica, n.d.) said that the term "library" originates from the Latin term "liber," translating to "book." In languages such as German, Russian, and the Romance languages, the term is derived from a Greek word that has been Latinized, known as "bibliotheca" (Britannica, n.d.). Moses, (2021) indicated that libraries have traditionally promoted education and helped to expand literacy by providing instructional materials, book collections, electronic resources, periodicals, and multimedia goods. Temboge and Ga'anda, (2022) said that university libraries bear the duty of collecting, processing, structuring, and distributing informational resources; moreover, they also offer services that align with the library's goals and objectives. Libraries deliver a range of services to fulfill the mission of their parent institution, particularly catering to the needs of their users (Temboge & Ga'anda, 2022). Yadi and Dinata, (2022) said that a library is a compilation of books and periodicals. While it could be seen as a personal collection, it's more typically recognized as a substantial assortment that is funded and managed by a city or institution (Yadi & Dinata, 2022). It serves individuals who, on average, may not have the means

to purchase a vast quantity of books on their own (Yadi & Dinata, 2022). Adler, (2020) said that a university library is set up, managed, and sustained to support the university in five key areas - facilitating teaching and learning; conducting research and creating new insights; distributing and publishing research findings; preserving knowledge and concepts; and implementing outreach initiatives. Zheng et al., (2022) said that a university library, being a common public space, houses an extensive array of books, leading to a high fire load. It often has a high concentration of people and significant foot traffic. Therefore, the circumstances surrounding safe evacuation during a fire are of great concern. Hugar and Bardez, (2023) said that libraries grant unrestricted access to a broad range of informational resources, including books, newspapers, magazines, and digital content. Therefore, public libraries across Indian states are proactive in fostering literacy and education (Hugar & Bardez, 2023). Moreover, they conduct reading schemes, storytelling events, and literacy campaigns to instill a love for reading in both children and adults.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Flexibility in library design

Nasir, (2024) said that in the field of Architecture, flexibility denotes the ability of a structure or space to be suitably modified and that this allows a building to evolve over time in response to the changing needs of the user, adapt to market changes, and prolong the lifespan of the project. Nasir, (2024) said that Architecture that is unable to adjust to changes risks becoming stagnant and outdated. Flexibility can manifest as active flexibility, like movable walls, or inherent flexibility, such as multipurpose spaces, open-concept offices, large floor-to-ceiling heights, and service voids with high capacity (Nasir, 2024). This could involve contemplating relatively simple design options; for instance, it might be quite easy to add or remove a bay to increase or decrease the size of a linear structure, but modifying a circular building could be extremely challenging without compromising the integrity of the design (Nasir, 2024). Napolitani, (2020) in her introductory remarks, said that library in the 21st century have evolved into vibrant hubs. She stresses that the unpredictability of future technological shifts and the swift alteration in the requirements of library patrons cannot be overlooked and necessitates enhanced adaptability of spaces, with movable fixtures and furniture that can be reconfigured in conjunction with their incorporated technical setup (Napolitani, 2020). Bal and Izak, (2021) said that flexibility can be viewed from both a psychological and physical perspective. Psychologically, it could be described as a “readiness to change or make concessions.” Furthermore, on a physical level, it is defined as “the attribute of bending effortlessly without snapping” and “the capacity to be modified with ease.” These two facets of flexibility are significant because they suggest a dual interpretation of the concept, not just in terms of a person’s or organization’s willingness and capability to adapt, but also in the sense of being able to move without breaking (Bal & Izak, 2021). State, (2024) said that layout and service requirements change so quickly that a new library facility must be planned with flexibility in mind. When examining a community's needs and service supply, variables such as population growth, demographic changes, and service delivery may result in additional space requirements or extension plans that must be incorporated into the conceptual and physical design. It is not feasible to forecast all future demands, but an approach to the design that provides flexibility and adaptation will make it easier to modify the

function of the library space (State, 2024). This approach to library design seeks to produce a more integrated and adaptable community resource.

2.2 Functionality in Library Design

AlSaggaf and Jrade, (2023) said that Site Layout Planning (SLP) is defined as the organization of materials, amenities, and machinery within the confines of a construction project area. The main objective of SLP is to create a site that facilitates construction operations effectively throughout the duration of the project, while ensuring a safe and almost dispute-free environment both within the site and in its immediate vicinity (AlSaggaf & Jrade, 2023). Choy and Goh, (2016) discuss appropriate furniture and that furnishing in the library may significantly improve the attractiveness and functionality of the areas. This, in turn, improves its appeal to encourage students to fully utilize the spaces, and referral services. The Digital Library Reference Model characterizes digital library as “An entity, possibly virtual, that extensively gathers, administers, and safeguards rich digital content for an extended period, and provides its user communities with specialized features on that content, of quantifiable quality and in accordance with established policies” (Yadav, 2023). Gu and Tanoue, (2022) go on to suggest that conventional libraries still serve the same essential purposes; and in addition, to increase the functions of today's conventional libraries, this type of service idea has to be expanded toward multifunctionality and omnipotence in today's reasonably advanced science and technology. Franklin and Da Cruz Duran, (2021) remarks that the library may be unexpectedly identified across the course of documented time given its persistent presence in the history of written civilization, even if it collects many features, modes of operation, and interactions between players. Alison, (2016) said that functional design can be an activity, a product, or both. Functionality, as a result, represents designs that operate effectively and assist users in completing their given tasks and as a process, it refers to a collection of methods driven by the concept that provide good outcomes. Alison, (2016) further said that usefulness necessitated understanding who utilized a place, why, and how to best support users' duties in the area's design. Samrgandi, (2020) mentioned that people form their ideas based on how the system functions, which is determined by intuition and experience. That is to say, they base their decisions on how well they can resolve a problem. Chauhan et al., (2023) said that the library may need to work with various suppliers for each, pay for expenses independently, and maintain them independently. The majority of Traditional Integrated Library Systems (ILSs) were created using outdated monolithic design, which combines all software functions into a single code base (Chauhan et al., 2023). Esan and Ifijeh, (2023) said that academic libraries need to continuously offer resources, services, and facilities that will draw customers in order to be relevant, especially in the age of information explosion. One method to achieve this is by improving the building's design and functioning. Esan and Ifijeh, (2023) additionally mention that the provision of wheelchair ramps for easy access, installation of outlets for charging devices, internet access, enough furniture for sitting and reading, enough cloakroom lockers, sufficient ventilation, central library location, availability of parking, and other features can all be considered functionalities of a university library. Simply said, library building functionality is the library's capacity to carry out the purposes for which it was first intended (Esan and Ifijeh, 2023).

2.3 Library Architecture

Moses Onosemuode, (2021) said that the library building, with its ideal types, model libraries, and unique character, has developed into a unique architectural form associated with modernism and societal modernization, symbolizing the expansion of "library-ness." A specialized discourse on library architecture and design has emerged as a result of books, articles, suggestions from users and library associations, professional conversations (Moses Onosemuode, 2021). Yadav, (2023) said that enlisting green libraries are to provide information on energy efficiency, sustainable construction, and the requirements of a library and further say the green library was founded in the 1990s. Therefore, green library is gaining popularity in the field of library and information science; and a librarian was also developing a library intending to use the least amount of electricity while maintaining environmental friendliness and energy efficiency (Yadav, 2023). In order to fight global warming and climate change, several libraries are thinking about constructing ecologically friendly buildings and green libraries are invariably sustainable and considerate of the environment (Yadav, 2023). Flores et al., (2021) said that since academic libraries serve as the focal point of the whole educational institution, they are an essential component of library administration and should be treated with great care. It goes beyond just drafting a floor plan and involves more than just the actual arrangement of the library; and it must be able to offer fresh chances for cooperation, place a strong emphasis on individual flexibility and variety, and allow for personalization (Flores et al., 2021). Oyebola et al., (2019) discussed that architecture serves as the main conduit for system attributes such as performance, adaptability, and security, all of which cannot be realized without a cohesive architectural vision. Architecture is a tool for preliminary analysis to ensure that a design strategy will result in a satisfactory system; and hence, by constructing a robust architecture, we can pinpoint design hazards and alleviate them early in the development cycle (Oyebola et al., 2019). Mondal, (2021) stated that the construction and evolution of a library building hinge on the administration of building development and construction procedures. These processes vary across different environments due to factors such as the scale, functions, location, materials utilized, cost, and the intended use of the buildings (Mondal, 2021). Likewise, building processes are influenced by the extent of financial commitment, the management of the construction process, architecture, construction methods, and environmental factors related to location, politics, economics, and culture (Mondal, 2021). Brunskill, (2020) said that library architectural design addresses the need to increase privacy in large, open spaces. The design of a space significantly influences how comfortable patrons feels; and privacy, in this context, relates to visibility and the ability to make noise without being overheard (Brunskill, 2020). The literature suggests that privacy in open spaces can be improved by placing dividers or partitions between group of tables arrangements and by varying the type and height of furniture in quiet spaces. Secondly, the information discusses the need to isolate noisy zones from quiet zones (Brunskill, 2020). Libraries need to balance the requirement for quiet study environments with the need for spaces that accommodate group work and socializing; and one of the strategies is to position noisy spaces near other sources of noise and to isolate quiet spaces from these noise sources (Brunskill, 2020). Thirdly, the available information in literature suggests the creation of reservable private study rooms; while these rooms can cater to students needing spaces free of distractions and patrons with mobility issues or limited time to study (Brunskill, 2020). Lastly, the available information highlights the need to improve outreach around library spaces; and

currently, patrons have limited options for learning about the available spaces, often resorting to exhaustive circuits around the buildings to discover what's available (Brunskill, 2020). Therefore, Brunskill suggests a need for more effective signage and online information about the spaces. Jessica, (2022) said that "Today's library embodies a multitude of roles," and Jennifer Charzewski, (the lead architect at Liollo - an architecture firm based in Charleston) further articulates that "A library serves as a meeting spot, a museum, a park, a school, and a community hub." Consequently, as they commence new constructions and refurbishments, library designers are placing a high priority on flexibility to accommodate potential future needs (Jessica, 2022).

2.4 User Experience

Temboge and Ga'anda, (2022) said that user satisfaction refers to the way users assess whether a product or service fulfills their needs and meets their expectations. In the context of libraries, user satisfaction is the measure by which users evaluate the sufficiency of the library's information resources and services provided to them, and whether these services align with their expectations (Temboge & Ga'anda, 2022). Bell, (2018) said that the Metaverse is a shared virtual space that aims to create a sense of presence and immersion that is not possible with traditional online interactions; and users can interact with each other and with virtual objects within this space, creating a highly realistic and immersive experience. Yadav, (2023) said that podcasts provide a flexible and easy way for users to publish their work on the Internet; and it will help researchers to identify ways that the technology can be exploited to maximize the users' learning experiences. Samrgandi, (2020) said that user experience widely accepted that academic libraries have emerged as hubs for evaluating the effectiveness of virtual environments. Bell, (2018) stated that universities have made concerted efforts to align their library services with a positive user experience and furthermore, it was expressed that the user experience aids in understanding how an individual forms a bond after interacting with a system. Universities have dedicated themselves to making information and resources accessible through the spaces on library websites (Bell, 2018). The concept of library user experiences has been around for as long as libraries themselves; and this is inevitable, as humans naturally have experiences when interacting with their immediate environment (Bell, 2018). Every time members of the user community interact with the library at any point of contact - be it the entrance, the website, the book stacks, the service desk, or the virtual chat function - an experience occurs (Bell, 2018).

3.0 Methods

A systematic review of journals between 2020 and till date (2024) with several PDF files downloaded from the ResearchGate, Elsevier, Taylor and Francis and other online articles. These were grouped into thematic formats for critical analysis which forms the base of this qualitative analysis. The executive summary of literature (ESTOL) helped in this critical analysis.

Table 1: Executive summary of literature

S/n	Author	year	Country of origin	Aim	Methodology	Gap Identified
1	Mondal, Hafijull	2021	India	Evaluate the Planning, Principle & Standards In The Perspective Of 21st Century	Qualitative analysis	lack of comprehensive and systematic guidelines for planning, designing, and constructing library buildings that meet the diverse and dynamic needs of the users and the society in the 21st century.
2	Esan, Adedoyin Oluwatosin Ifijeh, Ajelomohie Blessing	2023	Nigeria	to find out the influence of library building aesthetics and functionality on the patronage of university library	descriptive analysis	the lack of empirical studies on the relationship between library building aesthetics and functionality and library patronage in Nigeria.
3	Flores, Roana Marie De Leon, Simon V. Valerio, Marita G.	2021	Philippines	to provide a modified conceptual framework that can be applied to academic libraries in designing and repurposing spaces for better user experience.	Systematic literature review	the lack of a comprehensive and organic framework for library space design that can be applied to academic libraries
4	Demeter, Michelle	2023	Chicago, Illinois	to review of designing libraries for the 21 st Century	Book review	transformation of library spaces from traditional book repositories to multifunctional, user-centered environments that support a range of scholarly activities.
5	Oso, Olutoyin Olukemi	2023	Nigeria	to investigate experience of academic libraries in South-West Nigeria	descriptive survey	<u>is the challenge academic libraries face when handling book donations that come with conditions or strings attached.</u>

4.0 Results

Table 2: Findings

s/n	Objectives	Elsevier	Taylor Francis	& ResearchGate	Others	Total
1	Flexibility in library	0	0	1	3	4
2	Functionality in library	1	1	6	0	8
3	Library architecture	0	0	4	1	5
4	User experience	0	0	4	1	5
Ratings		1	1	15	5	22

The table presents a comparative analysis of different objectives related to library services, as assessed by different sources. Four objectives are listed: flexibility in the library, functionality in the library, library architecture, and user experience. Each objective is evaluated by four sources: Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, ResearchGate, and others.

For the objective of flexibility in the library, ResearchGate and the "Others" category gave the highest rating, with three and four points respectively, while Elsevier and Taylor & Francis didn't assign any points. In terms of functionality in the library, ResearchGate and the "Others" category again gave the highest rating, with six and eight points respectively. Elsevier and Taylor & Francis each awarded one point. Library architecture received the highest ratings from ResearchGate and the "Others" category, with four and five points respectively, whereas Elsevier and Taylor & Francis didn't assign any points to this objective. For user experience, ResearchGate and the "Others" category again provided the highest ratings, with four and five points respectively, while Elsevier and Taylor & Francis didn't give any points.

Figure 1: Showing objective analysis.

The chart provides a visual representation of the prioritization of different objectives related to a library. It uses a horizontal bar chart format, with the objectives listed on the x-axis and the scores given to each objective on the y-axis. The highest priority is given to “Functionality in Library” with a score of 8, indicating that it is considered the most important aspect. This suggests that how well the library serves its intended purpose, such as supporting the activities of its users, is of paramount importance. “Library Architecture” and “User Experience” both have a score of 5, suggesting that these aspects are also considered important, but not as critical as functionality. Library architecture refers to the physical design of the library, while user experience involves how users interact with the library and its services. The least priority is given to “Flexibility in Library” with a score of 4. Despite its lower score, flexibility is still a significant aspect of library design. It refers to the ability of the library space to adapt to changing needs and advancements in technology.

Figure 2: Flexibility analysis.

The chart is a bar graph titled “Flexibility in Design” and it compares the level of design flexibility among four different entities: Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, ResearchGate, and Others.

Elsevier and **Taylor & Francis** both have a flexibility score of 0, indicating no flexibility in their design, while the **ResearchGate** has a slightly higher flexibility score of 1, suggesting a low level of design flexibility and the group labeled as **Others** has the highest score of 3, indicating a high level of design flexibility.

Figure 3: Functionality analysis.

The chart is a horizontal bar graph titled “Functionality in Library”. It compares the level of library functionality among four different entities: Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, ResearchGate, and Others.

Elsevier has a high functionality score of 60, indicating a significant level of functionality in their library design while **Taylor & Francis** has a functionality score of around 10, suggesting a moderate level of functionality and **ResearchGate** has a low functionality score of less than 5, indicating limited functionality in their library design and lastly the category labeled as **Others** does not have a visible bar, suggesting that the functionality level might be negligible or not available.

Figure 4: Library architecture analysis.

The chart titled “Library Architecture” compares the number of resources or documents available from four different sources: Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, ResearchGate, and Others.

Elsevier has the highest number of resources, with a total of 4, **Taylor & Francis** has significantly fewer resources, with only 1 while both **ResearchGate** and **Others** do not have any resources according to the chart.

Figure 5: User experiences analysis.

The chart titled “User Experience” compares the user experience ratings for four different entities: Elsevier, Taylor & Francis, ResearchGate, and Others.

Elsevier has the highest user experience rating of 4, indicating a positive user experience while **Taylor & Francis** has a user experience rating of 1, suggesting a less positive user experience compared to Elsevier and both **ResearchGate** and **Others** have a user experience rating of 0, indicating a poor or non-existent user experience.

Bal and Izak, (2021) expresses in their finding that the concept of flexibility in architecture is crucial for adapting to evolving user needs and market fluctuations, involving both active and natural flexible elements in design. Demeter, (2023) said that libraries, as dynamic centers in the twenty-first century, require flexible spaces with mobile furnishings to accommodate changing technological and user demands. Napolitani, (2020) & Nasir, (2024) said that flexibility, both psychologically and physically, plays a vital role in library design, allowing for a willingness to change and adaptability in the face of evolving needs. Libraries must consider layout and service flexibility to effectively respond to population growth, demographic shifts, and changing service requirements Bal & Izak, (2021); State, (2024). The design of libraries involves considerations such as appropriate furniture, green initiatives, and accessibility features, aiming to enhance

functionality, attractiveness, and energy efficiency Choy & Goh, (2016); Esan & Ifijeh, (2023); Yadav, (2023). Academic libraries, seen as essential components of educational institutions, require careful design for individual flexibility, variety, and personalization; and the architectural vision and management of building processes are crucial for achieving effective library functionality Oyebola et al., (2019); Mondal, (2021).

Napolitani, (2020) expatiates that the COVID-19 pandemic necessitated swift adaptation to lockdown measures and remote work, highlighting the critical importance of flexibility in both library spaces and pandemic management. Therefore, in response to the increasing dynamism of libraries in the 21st century, flexibility in spaces and services has become essential to meet evolving needs. Moreover, Napolitani, (2020) stressed that despite pandemic challenges, scholarly articles have been successfully produced, underscoring the significance of user-oriented and creative approaches in library spaces. Technological integration plays a crucial role in enhancing flexibility and adaptability in library environments, particularly in light of COVID-19's impact on pharmaceutical information dissemination and research (Napolitani, 2020). The JEAHIL journal has experienced success and popularity, evidenced by high download and viewing statistics, highlighting the role of sponsorship and advertising in supporting its operations. Furthermore, data analysis is valuable in understanding readership and engagement with the journal, contributing to its ongoing success.

Chauhan et al., (2023) said in his findings, he highlights the potential benefits and limitations of Future of Library Is Open (FOLIO), a Library Service Platform (LSP), compared to Traditional Integrated Library Systems (TLSs): Therefore, the benefits of FOLIO consolidate multiple software services onto one platform, reducing the need for libraries to manage and maintain several software subscriptions. Its technology and architecture offer futuristic capabilities, particularly in managing e-resources, surpassing current TLSs. While FOLIO deployments are currently limited, literature suggests that adoption of new technologies is gradual but necessary for libraries to remain relevant in a changing world. FOLIO offers a promising solution for libraries facing budget constraints and the challenge of managing multiple software applications. Its flexibility, features, and sustainability make it a viable option for shaping the future of libraries. However, careful consideration of its limitations, such as technical requirements and localization support, is necessary before implementation. Overall, open-source software like FOLIO presents a compelling alternative to traditional TLSs for libraries seeking to streamline their operations and adapt to evolving technological landscapes.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The future of library design and management hinges on the concept of flexibility and functionality, both in physical spaces and in the services offered. This flexibility allows libraries to adapt to changing user needs, technological advancements, and unforeseen circumstances like the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the adoption of open-source platforms like FOLIO can help libraries streamline their operations and remain relevant in a rapidly changing world. However, the successful implementation of these changes requires careful planning,

consideration of potential limitations, and a commitment to ongoing adaptation and improvement.

5.2 Recommendations

The crucial role of flexibility and functionality in library design and management, especially in response to evolving user needs and challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic. Key points include the need for adaptable architecture, psychological and physical flexibility, consideration of factors like technology integration and academic requirements, and exploration of innovative solutions like FOLIO for library systems. Overall, libraries must prioritize flexibility to effectively serve their communities in a dynamic environment and emphasis on flexibility encompasses architectural elements like mobile furnishings, psychological adaptability to change, and technological integration to meet evolving demands. Academic libraries are highlighted as requiring personalized designs, while innovative solutions such as FOLIO offer promising benefits but require careful consideration of limitations. In essence, libraries must embrace flexibility to remain relevant and resilient in the face of shifting needs and technological advancements.

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TEACHER COMPONENT AND PARENTAL PARTICIPATION IMPACTS ON SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC OUTCOME IN IFO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined teacher component and parental participation impact on senior secondary school student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design type. 250 respondents comprising of fifty (50) teachers and two hundred (200) students were sampled using stratified sampling technique. The instruments used in the study for data collection were “Teacher Component and Parental Participation Impact on Student Academic Outcome” (TCPPISAO) and student academic outcome Test (SAOT). Four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The Data that was collected were analysed with simple percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. The sub-variables that enhanced student academic outcome are teacher components, classroom management, class control, teaching experience and instructional skills while the other variable of parental participation and teacher certification are not great determinants of student academic outcome. This study can be used to enlighten the educational stakeholders and planners on the need for qualified teachers to enhance adequate teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogun State and Nigeria at large. Ogun State students can make great academic growth if their parents are consistent in their support to attain academic goals and aspirations.

Introduction

Academic outcome is the assessment of education goal. That is, the extent to which a student or school has achieved their educational objective. Rafiei (2019) perceived academic outcome as one of the potent measures used to rate any educational system. It connotes the extent to which students have learnt a given task. The impact on teachers could be beneficial or a barrier to learning and teaching. According to Orimoloye (2015) held that the quality of education in Nigeria was deteriorating and thus militating against achieving the national policy on education

(FRN, 2014). Teachers' component is an important factor to be considered in ascertaining students' academic outcome as far senior secondary school is concerned.

Celebi et al (2020) opined that teachers' component in students' academic outcome cannot be over stressed. Therefore, teacher's components such as use of instructional materials, students' assessment among others are crucial to the achievement of educational goals and objectives. Accordingly, Igoni (2020) concluded that the most significant component influencing students' learning is the teacher. Teachers stand in the contact of the transmission of knowledge, values and skills in the learning process. If the teacher is not effective, students under his learning programme cannot achieve academically. Secondary education is believed to be a weak connection in the education lane in many developing countries, even though an increasing number of children are going on to secondary schools (Kanishka and Sharma, 2006). As there are so many substandard schools today, the stakeholder should continue to orientate the general public on the great needs of investing in education because many schools are still endowed with ineffective in the quality of learning which is greatly affecting the students' academic outcome both at internal or external examination.

The role of a parent over a child at any given time cannot be over emphasized. The home background is very important to a child's growth and success in life. Parents are the most immediate relation of a child (Etheridge 2017). This is because parent in the home are children's first teacher, he gradually learns how to speak, listen, write and read which latter develop the child to achieve in totality. Oyewole and Oloyede (2019) stated that the influence of democratic parenting style on students' academic performance emphasizes the important role of parents in their children's academic outcome.

Nigeria in the recent times has made the growth of secondary education in the state a challenging process. Parents and all stakeholders in education sector have variously commented on the outcome of secondary school students. Investigation and reports from examining bodies like West Africa Examination Council(WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) revealed that a high percentage of secondary school students continue to perform poorly most especially in mathematics, English studies chemistry, physics and economics which are core subjects This is confirmed with the release of WAEC result for May/ June 2013 as quoted in the daily newspaper, "the West African Examination Council (WAEC) released results of the May/ June 2013 west African senior secondary certificate examination, with about 30% of the candidates making credit in English and Mathematics. Details of the results showed that the results of 81,573 candidates representing 5.29% were withheld. Despite the laudable efforts at improving students' outcome, it appears there has not been appreciable improvement over the years. The recent discussion of educational stakeholders is focused on educational standards while the nation's concern becomes more consistent following the recent result of students in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination.

Apparently, when untrained teachers engaged students for West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), it is certain for the students to have poor grade in the examination. According to Nkeyemudim and Frank (2023), the government should find all possible means to retain experienced teachers who are willing to serve in order to contribute their

wealth of experience to improve the system. The Baguada Seminar Reports on Quantities and Qualities in Nigerian Education (NERC, 1980) as cited by Purwanto (2020) stated that the low quality of teachers will affect the competitiveness and quality of students also stated.

If teachers are apathetic, uncommitted, uninspired, lazy, unmotivated, immoral and anti-social, the whole nation is doomed. If teachers are ignorant in their disciplines and impact wrong information, this will lead to goal unachieved. The fact that substandard education contributes greatly to cases of examination malpractice that is now rampant in public examinations, as unpreparedness and fear of failure implore candidates into finding ways and strategies to cheat during an examination. Ogunsaju (2004), stated that the academic standard in all Nigerian educational institutions has fallen considerably below societal expectations.

Biseth et al. (2021) supported this when he stated that the decline in the quality of education cannot be avoided by anyone who is aware of the important role of education as a means for societal transformation growth and development. It is very vital to have enough and adequate human resources in terms of teacher's components for the teaching of all subjects in the school curriculum. Without the teachers as implementing component, the goals of education cannot be achieved. In order to achieve an equal society as stated in the Nigerian National Policy of Education (FRN, 2020), schools should be properly and uniformly equipped to promote sound and effective teaching. Suitable textbooks, qualified teachers, libraries which are adequate also should be provided for schools.

Scarcities of these, will constrain educational system from responding more fully to new demands. Teaching is not just a matter of teacher's talking and students listening, effective teaching involves interactive communication ways that are skillfully directed. In developed and developing countries, the quality of any worker in any organization is generally measured through obtained certificates as summed up by output (Asuku, 1999; Dahie et al, 2018). It has been proved that in many countries, teachers' certifications that are considered to be tally with student learning have become desirable targets of teacher education reform. Some of these reforms call for the professionalization of teacher education by upgrading it to graduate programmes, and regulating it through mechanisms of certification, and promotion that is conformed with standards (Darling-Hammond, Berry and Thorenson, 2001; Darling Hammond, Chung and Frelow; 2002; [Frank and Nkeyemudim 2023](#)).

The classroom is that space bounded by the wall and roof, which a teacher houses his students for the purpose of giving instruction to such students. In other words, it is a shelter for both teachers and learners so as to engage in educative interactive activities. Classroom management and control dictates the kind of relationship that exists between the teacher and the student during instructional activity and this ultimately determines the performance of students in school (Ahan, 2001). Management of classroom is one way to improve the learning of a student and to prevent problem in the academic outcome of the student, finding on classroom management has proven that a well-structured Classroom tends to improve student academic outcome (David-West 2017).

The student academic outcomes do not tally with great efforts and funds expended by the government and parents because of high level of failure in the external examinations. All educational planners and stakeholders are greatly worried about why the sector is producing graduates with poor results. The concern question is whether or not teachers in the public secondary schools are the most significant component of quality outcome in schools. Thus, this study will examine the following: teacher intending skills, teacher sex, teaching experience, teacher certificate, classroom management, teacher classroom and management conduct. The study also examined teachers' component and parental participation impact on senior secondary school student academic outcome.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to find out was to examine teacher component and parental participation impact on senior secondary school student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised and answered in this study

What is the level of teacher component impact in secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun State, Nigeria?

What are the extents of parental participation impact in secondary schools student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

To guide this research, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested:

Ho1 There is no significant relationship between teacher certifications and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Ho2 There is no significant relationship between teacher years of experience and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Ho3 There is no significant relationship between parent participation and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Ho4 There is no significant relationship between teacher necessary skills and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. (Classroom management, planning, class control and so on).

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design of the ex-post facto type. The target population of the study covered teachers and students in some senior secondary schools in Ifo local government area of Ogun state. The sample that was used for the study was selected through simple random sampling procedure. The total number of schools sampled was 10. Fifty teachers in all the selected schools participated in the study while 200 students were sampled through stratified sampling technique. In all, 250 respondents were used for the study.

Instrument

The two research-designed instrument that was used for data collection: Teacher Component and Parental Participation Impact on Student Academic Outcome” (TCPPISAO) meant for the teachers and student academic outcome Test (SAOT) completed by the students and content validated. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for student academic outcome Test (SAOT) was 0.83.

Findings and Discussion

The data collected were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between teacher certifications and secondary schools student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 1: Relationship between teacher certifications and student academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	r	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
Teacher certification	50	16.8000	4.25092	248	.662**	.000	<.05

Table 1 displays the relationship between teacher certifications and student academic outcome, $r = 0.662$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between teacher certifications and student academic outcome. This implies that an increase in teacher certification will increase the certainty for students to perform better.

Ho2 There is no significant relationship between teacher duration of experience and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 2: Relationship between teacher duration of experience and student academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	R	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
Teachers duration of experience	50	17.2800	3.99266	248	.679**.	.000	<.05

Table.2 displays the relationship between teachers duration of experience and students' academic outcome; $r = 0.679$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between teacher duration of experience and student academic outcome. This implies that an increase in teacher duration of experience will increase the tendency for students to perform better.

Ho3 There is no significant relationship between parent participation and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between parental participation and student's academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	R	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
Parental participation	50	16.3600	4.88567	248	.601**	.000	<.05

Table 3 reveals the relationship between parental participation and students' academic output; $r = 0.601$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between parental participation and student's academic outcome. This implies that an increase in parental participation will increase the tendency for students to perform better.

Ho4 There is no significant relationship between teacher necessary skills and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. (classroom management, planning, class control and so on). Table 4: Relationship between teacher necessary skills (classroom management, class control and planning of instructions) and student academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	R	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
teacher necessary skills	50	17.5600	4.22798	248	.644**	.000	<.05

Table 4 displays the relationship between teacher necessary skills and students' academic outcome; $r = 0.644$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between teacher necessary skills and students' academic outcome. This implies that an increase in teacher necessary skills will increase the tendency for students to perform better.

Discussion

The findings from hypothesis one displays there was a significant relationship between teacher certification and students' academic outcome. A significant correlation coefficient ($r = 0.662$) that was significant was found. The finding agreed with Hazan and Musa (2019) had proven that student outcome had a relationship with teacher components because when teachers did not perform their duties and functions, the students would not be able to learn well and achieve success. Also, the result of the study is in agreement with Huang and Moon (2009) documents that teacher certification responsible for about 40 to 60 percent of the variance in average of students' goals in assessment. The good performance was related to excellent instructions given by qualified teachers in addition to other inputs. Findings from hypothesis two showed there is a significant relationship between teachers' duration of experience and students' academic outcome. A positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.679$) that was significant was found. This finding is explained in the context of the fact that an experienced teacher is more conversant with the curriculum he has been handling for years and all he needs to do is to adopt new methods in handling them. An experienced teacher is matured and is better adhere to teaching as a profession. This result agreed with what Hanushek et al (2005) cited by Amoli (2016) said that has been observed that there were significant relationship between teaching experience and students' academic outcome. A number of studies found teachers' duration of experience to positively correlate with students' goal. For example, Rivkin, Hanushek and Kain (2005) cited by Amoli (2016) showed that students of experienced teachers achieved better than students of new teachers (those with one to three years of experience). Furthermore, the result of the finding from hypothesis three showed there is a significant relationship between parental participation and student's academic outcome. A positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.601$) that was significant was found. This result also supported the statement of McWayne (2005); that children who came from economically advantaged home receive much support at home that enhance their academic goal. There is fact that the positive relationship between parental impact, which is a yardstick of socio-economic status of parents and the academic progress of their children was also established by Lee and Sungur (2009); Oluwatelure (2010) cited by Babalola (2019) in their findings. The implication of the finding indicated that those students whose parents had higher expectations for their children's academic goal performed better from the beginning of their academic career and accelerated faster in their academic progress during the transition period of middle to high grades. Finding from hypothesis four displayed that there is a significant positive

relationship between teacher necessary skills. This finding agreed with the finding of Lusuwe (2007) that the management of discipline are requirement for effective classroom control. All teachers are responsible for managing discipline in their classroom. These findings strongly agree with the findings of Awoyemi (2002) cited by Adegbile (2018) that a significant relationship exists between teachers' experience and students' academic outcome. Also, as suggested by some researchers that teacher attribute and experience may not directly influence students' goal, but may do so indirectly. This implies that experience is highly valued in the teaching profession.

Conclusion

The study concluded that strongest determinant of students' academic outcome is teacher teaching experience, followed by teacher necessary skills, while other variables (parental participation, teacher certification and teacher sufficient) are not real determinant of student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state. A greater academic progress can also be attained by students if their parents are much committed to the reality their children goals and aspiration. The study discovered that teacher long duration of teaching experience and teacher necessary skills correlated significantly with student academic outcome. This implies that every effort should be made to retain the more experienced teachers in the service while the less experienced teachers are also encouraged to learn from the experienced teachers; in addition, effective and efficient classroom management needs proactive teachers to instruct and communicate their effective academic expectations to their students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Federal Ministry of Education should ensure that adequate and sufficient facilities and equipment are provided. The availability of these facilities will improve the level of students' academic outcome.
- ii. Teachers should be implored to consistently attend workshops or seminars to deepening their teaching knowledge and understanding how to assess students learning in their various subjects.
- iii. Parents should be enlightened on the significance of consistent support of student education in schools through the Parent Teachers Association.
- iv. There is the need for teachers to be resourceful in instructional materials selection and utilization. The cost of production and maintenance of instructional materials should be reduced, especially the improvised materials.
- v. There is need for regular training and retraining of teachers to enhance the teaching and learning process.

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MENTAL WELL-BEING, BURNOUT AS CORRELATES OF AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF POLICE OFFICERS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA.

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*DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13372608>***Introduction**

Globally, the police play a significant role in maintaining law and order in the society. It is an important institution in the society. The primary goal of formal policing is to protect life and property ensure that society is in stable order. Section 4 of the Police Act 2004 provides that the Nigeria Police Force (now known as the Nigeria Police) is the institution charged with the responsibility of preventing and detecting crime, apprehending offenders, preserving of law and order, protecting life and property, enforcing all laws and regulations with which they are directly charged and also performing military duties within or outside Nigeria (Akuul, 2011).

The study of aggressive behaviour is the concern of different branches of psychology. Aggression itself is a social behaviour as it is a way of interacting with other members of the society. It is a personality characteristic closely linked to anti-social behaviour. Aggressive behaviour includes all forms of physical or verbal behaviour intended to cause harm or be destructive to a person or a group of people (Cole & Dodge, 2018). Although there is no generally agreed upon precise definition of aggressive behaviour, many of the different definitions that have been proposed point to the view that it is any behaviour enacted with the intention to harm another person who is motivated to avoid that harm (Bushman & Huesmann, 2010). Aggressive behaviour can take various forms varying in degree of severity such as kicking, pushing, hitting, stabbing, shooting and killing. Aggressive behaviour therefore refers to the attempt to cause injury or harm to another person, and it is associated with both individual and social factors. According to Hsieh and Chen (2017), aggressive behaviour can be destructive and lead to financial loss, emotional distress, physical injury, or even death, to those exposed to it, and many other more indirect interpersonal and social costs to individuals and social groups associated with the victims. Therefore, an investigation aimed at understanding and predicting aggressive behaviour is in no less an important one.

Previous studies (Bushman & Huesmann, 2010; Buss, 1961; Gendreau & Archer, 2005) have identified several types of aggressive behaviour. They are physical, verbal, active, passive, direct and indirect aggression (Haller, 2014). Aggression is exhibited in many ways, the police can be physical that is inflicting injuries, or verbal by abusing and saying uncomfortable words to the citizens. Physical aggression involves physically harming or injuring other individuals; it includes physical violence towards other people such as murder and attempted murder. Verbal

aggression includes the use of harsh and hostile words to hurt people. It includes verbal abuse like issuing threats of harm and using hostile swear words, yelling or screaming at another person (Foster, Bowers & Nijman, 2007; Kisa, 2008). Active aggressive behaviour refers to the attempt to physically or verbally harm the victim, while passive aggressive behaviour refers to failing to engage in helping behaviour. It is an inert form of aggression. Furthermore, aggressive behaviour can be displayed directly or indirectly. It is direct when it is explicitly aimed at a target person; it can take the form of physical attack and/or hostile verbal behaviours against a person such as when the victim is slapped, punched, bitten, or threatened with violence. (Adeoye, Okonkwo & Makinde 2014). Aggressive behaviour is manifested indirectly when it is aimed at a person but not explicitly such as when harmful words are said about the person behind their back aim at tarnishing the image of the victim or damaging the victim's property in his or her absence. It is characterized by social manipulation such as social exclusion that eventually cause harm to others (Ademola, Adeoye & Filade, 2018; Card, Stucky, Sawalani, & Little, 2008; DeWall, Anderson, & Bushman, 2012; Haller, 2014).

Aggression has been found to be a sign of an underlying mental well-being disorder, a substance use disorder or a medical disorder (Cherry, 2018). Increase of aggressive behavior has been observed in a number of serious mental illnesses, and it poses a clinical challenge for mental healthcare providers (Pompili, Carlone, Silvestrini, & Nicolo, 2017). The belief that mental illness is associated with violence is common and cuts across cultures and there is more support in literature for at least a moderate relationship between mental disorders and violence. A similar situation applies in Nigeria. Belief in the association between mental disorders and violence is one of the reasons for the stigma associated with the mentally ill.

Mental well-being has been defined as a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make meaningful contribution to his or her community (World Health Organization, 2001). Mental well-being has also been defined as a state of mind in which an individual can effectively utilize his or her capacities by displaying psychological resilience in making personal and social adjustments to fit the dynamic environment within which he or she co-exists with other persons (Mental Health Foundation, 2015). In this study, mental well-being will be measured by a self-report inventory that seeks to obtain information about the extent to which, over the past month, police officers are happy, calm and peaceful, nervous or depressed. Bello, Onunkun and Uwanna (2018) aver that mental well-being is a concept that is related to the social and emotional well-being of individuals and communities and to the enjoyment of life, ability to cope with stresses and sadness, the fulfillment of goals and potential, and a sense of connection to others. It is a complex construct that can be determined by depression, anxiety, despair, and life satisfaction (including dissatisfaction). These variables could lead to a wide range of outcomes including aggressive behaviour that could be detrimental to the aggressing individuals. Mental well-being is concerned with enhancing competencies of individual employees and aiding them in the performance of their tasks. Concepts related to mental well-being include subjective well-being, perceived self-efficacy, autonomy, competence, intergenerational dependence and recognition of the ability to realize one's intellectual and emotional potential.

Burnout is commonly used in reference to work. It has been variously defined, but the acceptable definition is that of Leiter, Maslach & Schaufeli (2001) who described burnout as being related to human services coping with the emotional demands of citizens, expressed by three dimensions: Emotional exhaustion as a subjective experience, depersonalization as an attempt to put distance between oneself and service recipients, and reduced personal accomplishment as a lack of efficacy. Ellrich (2015) also proposed a burnout-victimization model which averred that two of the dimensions of burnout, namely emotional exhaustion and depersonalization are associated with police aggression. In simpler terms, burnout is a situation in which employees are so stressed that they experienced emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a sense of reduced personal accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion occurs when an employee is overwhelmed by heavy workload. According to Edun (2018), burnout describes a situation where one is emotionally overextended and exhausted by one's work, causing one to suffer psychological fatigue and feel psychologically and emotionally drained. Depersonalization refers to a skeptical or scornful perception of other individuals and can often lead to detachment or indifference. Reduced personal accomplishment means the perception of self as no longer useful or effective at work. Burnout is a psychological syndrome in response to chronic interpersonal stressors on the job. Although burnout may be the result of unrelenting stress, it is not the same as too much of stress. It means feeling empty, devoid of motivation, and beyond caring. Burnout is a stress syndrome resulting from the individual's inability to deal with occupational stress. It mainly refers to an extreme state of psychological strain and depletion of energy resources arising from prolonged exposure to stressful situations that exceed the person's resources to cope.

Hence, the following null hypotheses were formulated and addressed in this study:

H₀1: There is no significant relationships among mental well-being, burnout and aggressive behaviour of police officers in Ogun State.

H₀2: There is no significant combined influence of mental well-being and burnout on aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State.

Methodology:

Research Design

This study adopted the survey design which enabled the researcher to collect data from a cross-section of the target population without manipulating any of the predictor variables (burnout and mental well-being) but measuring them as they pre-exist among the participants in the study. The design was appropriate because the study took place in a natural setting, and was retrospective in nature.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all police officers in Ogun State. The total number of police officers in Ogun State is 2,648.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size for the study was derived by using Yamane (1967) formula for calculating sample size for finite population. The proportional sampling technique was used to select number of participants for the study from each of the selected police stations in Ogun State, while simple random sampling technique was used to select the participants for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used because it eliminated bias in sampling which gave every officer an equal opportunity of being selected.

Instrumentation

The following instruments were used for data collection in this study:

Demographic Data Inventory (DDI): The Demographic Data Inventory (DDI) is a seven-item instrument developed by this researcher to measure the demographic characteristics of the respondents such as Senatorial District, gender, age, marital status, educational qualification, cadre and work experience.

Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI): The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) was developed by Maslach and Jackson (1997) for the purpose of measuring hypothesized aspects of the burnout syndrome. The inventory has been recognized for more than a decade as the leading measure of burnout, incorporating the extensive research that has been conducted in the more than 25 years since its initial publication. The MBI is a 10-item self-report survey which uses a 5-point scale for responses. The response to an item can range from 1 = Never, 2= A few times in a year, 3= A few times in a month, 4= Once a week and 5 = Every day.

The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS): The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) was developed by researchers at the Universities of Warwick and Edinburgh, with funding provided by National Health Services Health Scotland, to enable the measurement of mental well-being of adults in the United Kingdom. WEMWBS is a 14-item scale of mental well-being covering subjective well-being and psychological functioning, in which all items are worded positively and address aspects of positive mental health. The scale is scored by summing responses to each item answered on a 1 to 5 Likert scale. The minimum scale score is 14 and the maximum is 70. WEMWBS has been validated for use in the United Kingdom with those aged 16 and above. Validation involved both student and general population samples, and focus groups. People participating in studies of face validity found the scale clear, unambiguous and easy to complete. They volunteered the opinion that the scale measured mental well-being. Population scores on WEMWBS approximate to a normal distribution with no ceiling or floor effects, making the scale suitable for monitoring mental well-being in population samples. The scale is not designed to identify individuals with exceptionally high or low positive mental health, so no 'cut off' has been developed (analogous to a mental illness 'cut-off' on for example the GHQ 12 scale). The provisional Scottish population mean score is 50.7 with a 95% confidence interval of 50.3 to 51.1, obtained from a combined national dataset comprising data from the Health Education Population Survey 2006 (wave 12) and the Well? What do you think? 2006 survey. The WEMWBS was developed and validated on samples drawn from foreign

countries and has not been previously used with samples of police officers in Nigeria. This necessitates the need for the re-assessment of its reliability.

Validity of the Instruments

The copy of the instruments was given to the researcher's supervisor and other senior lecturers in the Department of Education and humanities at Babcock University. Their suggestions were taken and effected so as to ensure that the research instrument was able to measure the variables investigated effectively.

Reliability

The reliability of a research instrument involves the extent to which the instrument yields the same result on repeated trials. A pilot testing of the instrument was conducted twice at Obalende Police Station, Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State.

The internal consistency of the questions on the questionnaire scales was reliable since each had a value ranging from .737 to .801. The variables for the study were subjected to a reliability test of Cronbach's Alpha using the SPSS. The study's instrument is therefore thought to be valid. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient values for the variables are displayed in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Cronbach's Alpha Value of the Study's Variables

Variables	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI)	10	.801
Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS)	10	.737
Aggressive Behavior Scale (BUSS-PERRY Scale)	12	.778

Method of Data Analysis

The demographic data of participants was analyzed by means of frequency counts and percentage. The two hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis). All tests were carried out at the .05 level of significance

Results:

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationships among mental well-being, burnout and aggressive behaviour of police officers in Ogun State

Table: Correlation Matrix for Relationships among Mental Well-Being, Burnout and Aggressive Behaviour

	Burnout	Mental Well-Being	Physical Aggression	Verbal Aggression	Anger	Hostility
Burnout	1.00	-.785**	.779*	.627*	.641**	.341**
Mental WB		1.00	-.690*	-.715*	-.628**	-.343**
Phy Agg			1.000	.844*	.858**	.550**
Ver Agg				1.000	.862**	.637**
Anger					1.000	.787**
Hostility						1.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Note: Mental WB = Mental Well-Being; Phy Agg = Physical Aggression; Ver Agg = Verbal Aggression

Table 1 revealed significant results. Specifically, there were significant positive relationships between burnout and physical aggression ($r = .779, p < .05$), burnout and verbal aggression ($r = .627, p < .05$), burnout and anger ($r = .641, p < .05$), burnout and hostility ($r = .341, p < .05$), physical aggression and verbal aggression ($r = .844, p < .05$), physical aggression and anger ($r = .858, p < .05$), physical aggression and hostility ($r = .550, p < .05$), verbal aggression and anger ($r = .862, p < .05$), verbal aggression and hostility ($r = .637, p < .05$), and anger and hostility ($r = .787, p < .05$). There were significant negative relationships between burnout and mental well-being ($r = -.785, p < .05$), mental well-being and physical aggression ($r = -.690, p < .05$), mental well-being and verbal aggression ($r = -.715, p < .05$), mental well-being and anger ($r = -.628, p < .05$), and mental well-being and hostility ($r = -.343, p < .05$). Therefore, the hypothesis that stated "There is no significant relationships among mental well-being, burnout and aggressive behaviour of police officers in Ogun State" was rejected by the outcome of this findings.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant combined influence of mental well-being and burnout on aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State.

Table 2: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis of relative and composite influence of mental well-being and burnout on Aggressive Behaviour

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	55.194	1.370		40.297	.000
Mental wellbeing	.681	.050	.690	13.610	.000
Burnout	.811	.046	.779	17.770	.000
Source of variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P
Regression	10768.414	2	5384.207	167.943	.000
Residual	6508.115	203	32.060		
Total	17276.529	205			
R = .789, R ² = .623, Adj. R ² = .620, Std. Error = 5.66213					

The relative contribution of each predictor variable (mental wellbeing and burnout) to the variance in the aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State revealed that mental well-being has a beta value of .690 and t-value of 13.610 significant at less than .05 alpha level, while burnout has a beta value of .779 and t-value of 17.770 significant at less than .05 alpha level. Therefore, mental wellbeing ($\beta = .690$, $t = 13.610$, $p = .00$) and burnout ($\beta = .779$, $t = 17.770$, $p = .05$) are potent factors to the prediction of aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State.

Furthermore, aggressive behaviour among the police officers yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of 0.789 and adjusted multiple regression square of 0.620. This shows that 62% of the total variance in the aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State is accounted for by mental wellbeing and burnout. The Table also indicates that the analysis of variance of the multiple regression data produced an F-ratio value significant at 0.00 level ($F_{(2, 203)} = 167.943$, $p = .05$). Mental wellbeing and burnout combined to influence aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State. Therefore, the hypothesis that stated 'There is no significant combined influence of mental wellbeing and burnout on aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State was rejected.

Discussion:

The first null hypothesis stated that there are no significant relationships among mental well-being, burnout and aggressive behaviour of police officers in Ogun State. This hypothesis was subjected to appropriate test of significance and found to be unsupported by data. It was subsequently rejected and the alternative hypothesis was upheld, leading to the conclusion that there were significant positive relationships between burnout and physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger and hostility, physical aggression and verbal aggression, physical aggression and anger, physical aggression and hostility, verbal aggression and anger, verbal aggression and hostility, and anger and hostility. Also, there were significant negative relationships between

burnout and mental well-being, mental well-being and physical aggression, mental well-being and verbal aggression, mental well-being and anger, and mental well-being and hostility.

These findings revealed several significant positive relationships between burnout, aggressive behaviour, and related constructs. Firstly, burnout was found to have a significant positive relationship with physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger, and hostility. These findings suggest that as burnout levels increase among police officers, so does the likelihood of engaging in various forms of aggressive behaviour. This aligns with previous research linking burnout to negative outcomes and supports the notion that burnout can manifest in different forms of aggression, both physical and verbal. Additionally, the study found significant positive relationships between different types of aggressive behavior. For example, physical aggression was positively correlated with verbal aggression, anger, and hostility. This indicates that officers who display physical aggression are also more likely to exhibit other aggressive behaviours, such as verbal aggression or expressions of anger and hostility. Such findings highlight the interconnected nature of aggressive behaviours and the need to address them comprehensively. The positive relationships between burnout and various forms of aggression highlight the need to address burnout as a risk factor for aggressive behavior. Interventions aimed at reducing burnout levels, such as improving organizational support, workload management, and stress reduction programmes, could potentially contribute to a decrease in aggressive tendencies among police officers.

These findings were in line with Kop, Euwema and Schaufeli (1999) who averred that a positive correlation exists between burnout and use of violence by police officers. The findings also supported other studies such as McCarty and Skogan (2013) who found a positive relationship between physical stress and police aggression, Silva (2012) who found that burnout dimensions are a strongly related to aggressivity and Queiros, Kaiseler and Da Silva (2013) who reported statistically significant correlations between burnout dimensions and aggressivity dimensions.

The study also revealed significant negative relationships between mental well-being and various constructs related to aggression. A negative relationship was observed between mental well-being and burnout, physical aggression, verbal aggression, anger, and hostility. These findings indicate that as mental well-being decreases among police officers, the likelihood of experiencing burnout and engaging in aggressive behaviour increases. Furthermore, the negative relationships between mental well-being and different forms of aggression emphasize the importance of considering mental well-being as a crucial factor in mitigating aggressive behaviour. In conclusion, the findings of this study emphasize the importance of addressing burnout and promoting mental well-being as strategies to mitigate aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State. By implementing targeted interventions that focus on reducing burnout, improving mental well-being, and fostering a positive work environment, law enforcement agencies can strive to create safer and healthier work environments, benefiting both the officers and the communities they serve.

This finding corroborated Mulvey (2014) whose study revealed that mental well-being problems is generally associated with the likelihood of aggressing in some individuals, Buckley,

Noffsinger and Smith (2013), who found that mentally challenged individuals with threatening, paranoid delusions are twice as likely to become aggressive compared with non-paranoid individuals, Velden, Kleber, Grievink and Yzermans (2010) whose study revealed a significant association between mental well-being problems and aggression in police officers, Bello, Onunkun and Uwanna (2018) who averred that mental well-being is a concept that is related to reduced aggression among others.

The second null hypothesis stated that there is no significant combined influence of mental well-being and burnout on aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State. This hypothesis was subjected to appropriate test of significance and found to be unsupported by data. It was subsequently rejected and the alternative hypothesis was upheld, leading to the conclusion that there was a significant combined influence of mental well-being and burnout on aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State. These findings highlight the importance of considering both mental well-being and burnout simultaneously when examining aggressive behaviour in this population. The significant combined influences of burnout and mental well-being on aggressive behaviour among police officers in Ogun State highlight the importance of implementing comprehensive strategies to address these factors. Mental well-being and burnout were found to jointly contribute 62% of the variance in physical aggression. The combined effect implies that addressing mental well-being alone or burnout alone may not be sufficient to mitigate aggressive behaviour effectively. Instead, interventions should focus on improving mental well-being and decreasing burnout levels in order to reduce the risk of aggressive behaviour among police officers. This finding corroborated Ogunlusi and Adenuga (2018) who found in their study that mental well-being and burnout interacted to significantly determine aggressive behavior among Nigerian police officers. The finding was also in line with that of Adekunle (2019) who found that police officers with high levels of mental well-being exhibited a protective effect against burnout-induced aggressive behaviour, and that even in the face of burnout, officers with strong mental well-being were less likely to display aggression, highlighting the importance of mental health resilience.

Conclusion:

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made: Higher levels of burnout are associated with increased tendencies to engage in aggressive behaviours; physical aggression is positively related to verbal aggression, anger, and hostility. This indicates that individuals who display physical aggression are also likely to exhibit other forms of aggression; mental well-being is negatively related to burnout and aggressive behaviour and higher levels of mental well-being are associated with lower levels of burnout and reduced tendencies to engage in aggressive behaviours. Furthermore, burnout and mental well-being significantly predicts aggressive behaviour.

Recommendation:

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

Government and police authorities should develop and implement comprehensive burnout prevention programmes for police officers. These programmes should focus on stress management techniques, promoting work-life balance, providing social support and ensuring adequate rest and recovery periods.

Police Commands should prioritize the mental well-being of police officers by implementing mental well-being support programmes, such as counselling services and resilience training which can help officers cope with stressors effectively and improve their mental well-being.

Interventions aimed at reducing aggressive behaviour should adopt a holistic approach that simultaneously targets burnout and mental well-being. By addressing both factors, interventions can effectively mitigate the risk of various forms of aggression.

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IMPACT OF NEPOTISM ON TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN ABEOKUTA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT

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Abstract

Teachers' productivity should be a concern to any educational administrator. Nepotism, which has become prevalent in work environments, may be a major factor impacting either positively or negatively on teachers' productivity. Thus, this study assessed the impact of nepotism on teachers' productivity as perceived by teachers in the Abeokuta local government area of Ogun state. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 10 out of the 40 secondary schools in the Local Government Area. The sample size of the study (n=217) was arrived at using the krecjean and Morgan sample determination size table and proportionate sampling to afford each school equal chances of respondents. The instrument used in gathering data is a well-structured questionnaire. Findings reveal that there is a low prevalence of nepotism among teachers, and a high extent of teachers' productivity. Also, the study revealed that there is no significant influence ($R = .034$; $R^2 = .001$; $Adj R^2 = -.004$; $F_{(1,215)} = .243$; $p > .05$) of nepotism on productivity. Among other recommendations, the study recommends that a merit based evaluation system should not be compromised in schools, in order to enhance and sustain high productivity among teachers.

Introduction

The concept of productivity of teachers is a combination of many interacting factors in the workplace in the school while the inputs may be related to miscellaneous and sometimes intangible factors, the output is the outcome of the whole process in terms of student achievement and how it affects the development of the economy holistically (Oyedepo, 2011). The issue of productivity and how to raise the level of productivity of a nation and labour force is important and should be of chief concern to Educational leaders and leaders in all sectors of the economy.

Teacher's productivity is an issue of concern generally in Nigeria. Reports have it, that there is a general decline in the quality of education in Sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria in particular. Seventy (70) percent of children in Nigeria cannot read with meaning or solve simple math problems and only 49 percent and 55 percent of children in school achieve basic literacy and numeracy respectively; Nigeria is uppermost in the number of out-of-school children globally with 13.2 million children who are either drop-outs or unenrolled; one out of every 5 of 1 the world's out-of-school children is in Nigeria (UNICEF Nigeria, 2022).

There are also many graduates produced yearly who cannot functionally defend their certificates (Nwafor, 2022). Lack of confidence in Nigeria's educational system such that at the slightest opportunity, an average Nigerian prefers to go abroad to study (Olawale & Adeniyi, 2020), and the rush by Nigerian employers for individuals with foreign and precisely Western qualifications can attest to the preference for the quality of education in such countries compared to the quality of Education in Nigeria. However, all over the world national development, is indirectly dependent on the quality of education. Teachers are to be relied upon if a holistic national development will be realized in Nigeria. Evidence of teacher training, curriculum revisions, reformed programmes, and improved wages abound. All these efforts seem not to be significant.

This necessitates a refocus on other factors that might be influencing teachers' productivity and educational quality. Among the identified factors that might be influencing productivity is workplace behaviour or prevalent culture. It is often intangible but has a lot of far-reaching effects on the productivity of teachers. Such behaviours that could be potential predictors of productivity among teachers are sycophancy and nepotism.

The concept of nepotism is not new in human social interactions. Workplaces scarcely employ on merit in recent times. People get enlisted on the job because of the same religious, ethnic or political affiliation with people in leadership or for sexual or friendly relationships, not necessarily because of competence or possession of relevant skills. The relationship these variables have on Teachers' productivity is worth delving into.

Naturally, "nepotic" tendencies do not hamper an individual Teacher's productivity. It has been observed to be advantageous for some family businesses in terms of loyalty and giving feedback especially when there is trust. However, the observed impact by the researcher on the group relationship becomes an issue of concern in that both in life and literature, many cases of demoralization, unhappiness, unfair treatment, victimization, and alienation of "non-nepotic" workers have been severally evident because the unqualified but privilege Teachers in the in-group of the leader enjoy more privileges, promotions, high regard, affection, coveted perks, desirable assignment and growth opportunities more than their counterparts leading to alienation, absenteeism, withdrawal, increased turnover rate and intention, and sometimes hostility and unhealthy rivalry capable of hampering productivity at work. There is a need to investigate this observation because the productivity of Teachers is directly proportional to the entire outcome of a nation's education system and holistic national development.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers' productivity should be a concern to any educational administrator. The decline in educational quality in the nation is palpable. Many Nigerian graduates cannot functionally defend the certificates in their hands. Oftentimes graduates cannot sufficiently use the skill acquired from school to solve the nation's problems. The brain drain in which most of our youths and productive ages of the economy migrate into developed nations to study further attests to the quality of education being received in the nation. To worsen it, indigenous employers are also all out there to employ anyone with foreign certification and even place them above Nigerian certification in some cases. A deep reflection of all these pointers makes the researcher concerned about teachers' productivity, especially knowing its attendant effect on the holistic development of a nation.

Many investigations have identified technical issues such as poor curriculum, Poor remunerations of teachers, poor infrastructural supply, and lack of trained teachers to mention a few which the government is trying its best in one way or the other to improve yet there has been no improvement. This gets the researcher wondering that there may be other intangible inputs that may determine productivity.

Research question

In order to determine the impact of nepotism on teacher productivity, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the prevalence of nepotism among teachers in the Local Government Area?
2. What is the extent of Teachers' productivity in the Local Government Area?

Hypothesis

1. There will be no significant impact of nepotism on teachers' productivity.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design using regression was adopted in carrying out the study. To ensure a more representative and convenient sampling that can be generalized; the researcher adopted a multi-stage sampling technique for the study. In the first stage, Abeokuta South Local Government Area in Ogun state (ASLA) was selected as an area the researcher has lived in for many years (as a give-back to society initiative).

Population

The population of the study comprised all public secondary schools in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, of Ogun state.

Sample and sampling technique

In arriving at the sampling size for this study, ten (10) public secondary schools in Abeokuta South Local Government Area were purposively selected from the forty (40) public secondary schools based on proximity, cost, and availability of required data. The Krejciean and Morgan sample determination size table was used to arrive at a sample size of 217 teachers, who were respondents to the questionnaires. The proportionate sampling technique formula below was used to arrive at the sample size for each selected school to afford each school an equal proportion of respondents:

Instrumentation

The data for the study were generated through a questionnaire titled Nepotism Scale (NS). The questionnaire was designed to obtain information about nepotism, and favoritism ranging from religious affiliations, family ties, sexual relationships, and friendship and how this impacts teachers' productivity. The questionnaire contains 13 items. The format for the response is four Likert scales of strongly agree, agree, strongly disagree, and disagree.

Validity

To ensure the instruments are valid in measuring what they are meant to measure, Copies of the questionnaire were face-validated by the supervisor and two experts in the Department of Education, Babcock University. They ascertained the effectiveness of the scales for the research work.

Reliability

The instruments were further subjected to a pilot study on schools that are not part of the study using 20 copies of questionnaires. The data obtained was subjected to Cronbach's alpha reliability test to establish the internal consistency of the items. Results from the test were used to determine items included in the questionnaire.

Serial number	Scales	No of items	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
1.	Nepotism	12	0.712
2.	Teachers' Productivity	12	0.617

Method of Data collection

The data were collected using the research questionnaire which were administered by the researcher with the help of the research assistant who had been trained on data collection procedures. Appointment was fixed, and questionnaires were filled and collected at the appointment date and this aided a 100% retrieval of the questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analysed using linear and multi regression analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance and all analyses were executed by means of the statistical packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software.

Results:

RQ 1: What is the prevalence of nepotism among teachers in selected public secondary schools in Ogun State?

Table 1: *Descriptive Statistics of Prevalence of Nepotism among Teachers in Selected Public Secondary Schools in Ogun State*

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
1.	Education level is not important in the decision to enlist a teacher in this school?	16 (7.4%)	24 (1.1%)	73 (33.6%)	104 (47.9%)	1.7788	.91637
2.	Appointment of HODs does not have to be based on competence (qualifications, seniority and teaching experience).	11 (5.1%)	18 (8.3%)	64 (29.5%)	124 (57.1%)	1.6129	.84296
3.	Communicating with relatives or close ally of top management is not complicated, because they neither act as spies nor are suspected of acting as spies on behalf of top management	11 (5.1%)	81 (37.3%)	82 (37.8%)	43 (19.8%)	2.2765	.83724
4.	I became employed in this school because I am related to a member of the school management	9 (4.1%)	13 (6.0%)	60 (27.6%)	135 (62.2%)	1.5207	.78810
5.	I got this teaching job through my political party	8 (3.7%)	22 (10.1%)	54 (24.9%)	133 (61.3%)	1.5622	.82048
6.	I got this teaching job because of my religious affiliation	7 (3.2%)	13 (6.0%)	51 (23.5%)	146 (67.3%)	1.4516	.75075
7.	I got this teaching job through someone I have sexual relationship with	11 (5.1%)	9 (4.1%)	36 (16.6%)	161 (74.2%)	1.4009	.79384

8.	I take a dim view of a colleague who is a close ally or a relative of the Principal	8 (3.7%)	33 (15.2%)	88 (40.6%)	88 (40.6%)	1.8203	.82212
9.	I do not get frustrated when a co-worker is praised just because of his/her friendship / family connections	52 (24.0%)	93 (42.9%)	41 (18.9%)	31 (14.3%)	2.7650	.97424
10.	There is no mutual mistrust between me and a relative or loyalist of the principal	36 (16.6%)	102 (47.0%)	52 (24.0%)	27 (12.4%)	2.6774	.89603
11.	Most conflicts arise due to relatives employed and favored by top leadership	26 (12.0%)	80 (36.9%)	64 (29.5%)	47 (21.7%)	2.3917	.95671
12.	I carefully consider every word when I communicate with colleagues who are relatives/ friends of the administrative staff	39 (18.0%)	119 (54.8%)	41 (18.9%)	18 (8.3%)	2.8249	.82030
Mean = 24.083; Median = 24.000; Std. Dev. = 5.740; Skeweness = .827; Kurtosis = 1.592							

The result in Table 1 revealed that most of the respondents disagreed that education level is not important in the decision to enlist a teacher in this school (Mean 1.779 :SD = .916); also disagreed that appointment of HODs does not have to be based on competence (qualifications, seniority and teaching experience) (Mean = 1.6129; SD = .84296); disagreed that communicating with relatives or close ally of top management is not complicated, because they neither act as spies nor are suspected of acting as spies on behalf of top management (Mean = 2.2765; SD = .83724); disagreed that they became employed in this school because they are related to a member of the school management (Mean = 1.5207; SD = .78810); disagreed that they got this teaching job through their political party (Mean = 1.5622; SD = .82048); disagreed that they got this teaching job because of their religious affiliation (Mean = 1.4516; SD = .75075); disagreed that they got this teaching job through someone they have sexual relationship with (Mean = 1.4009; SD = .79384); disagreed that they took a dim view of a colleague who is a close ally or a relative of the Principal (Mean = 1.8203; SD = .82212); agreed that they do not get frustrated when a co-worker is praised just because of his/her friendship / family connections (Mean = 2.7650; SD = .97424); also agreed that there is no mutual mistrust between them and a relative or loyalist of the principal (Mean = 2.6774; SD = .89603); disagreed that most conflicts arise due to relatives employed and favored by top leadership (Mean = 2.3917; SD = .95671); agreed that they carefully consider every word when they communicate with colleagues who are relatives/friends of the administrative staff (Mean = 2.8249; SD = .82030).

The overall scores for nepotism among teachers in selected public secondary schools in Ogun State are mean (24.083); median is (24.000); standard deviation (5.740);

RQ 2: What is the extent of productivity among teachers in selected public secondary schools in Ogun State?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Showing The Extent Of Productivity Among Teachers In Selected Public Secondary Schools In Ogun State

S/N		SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
1.	I am effective in classroom management.	139 (64.1%)	76 (35.0%)	1 (0.5%)	1 (0.5%)	3.6267	.52159
2.	I am involved in making rules and regulations in my school.	33 (15.2%)	107 (49.3%)	69 (31.8%)	8 (3.7%)	2.7604	.75012
3.	I give suggestion that counts in vital issues in the school.	40 (18.4%)	150 (69.1%)	26 (12.0%)	1 (0.5%)	3.0553	.56657
4.	I demonstrate sound knowledge of the subject matter.	116 (53.5%)	97 (44.7%)	3 (1.4%)	1 (0.5%)	3.5115	.55370
5.	I adhere strictly to school time table	125 (57.6%)	86 (39.6%)	5 (2.3%)	1 (0.5%)	3.5438	.56860
6.	I achieve educational goals and objectives set	110 (50.7%)	104 (47.9%)	3 (1.4%)	-	3.4931	.52810
7.	I give performance feedback to students promptly	106 (48.8%)	103 (47.5%)	8 (3.7%)	-	3.4516	.56822
8.	My students always understand my lesson instructions.	97 (44.7%)	114 (52.5%)	4 (1.8%)	2 (0.9%)	3.4101	.57934
9.	I am a recipient of several awards on this teaching job	32 (14.7%)	127 (58.5%)	50 (23.0%)	8 (3.7%)	2.8433	.70931
10.	I conduct regular continuous assessment and mark tests/assignments promptly.	97 (44.7%)	108 (49.8%)	11 (5.1%)	1 (0.5%)	3.3871	.60661
11.	I am always found at this teaching duty post	115 (53.0%)	97 (44.7%)	5 (2.3%)	-	3.5069	.54535
12.	I love this job so much I complete the syllabus in their subjects within the stipulated time.	106 (48.8%)	98 (45.2%)	11 (5.1%)	2 (0.9%)	3.4194	.63406
13.	I keep accurate and adequate	119	94	2	2	3.5207	.56991

records of instructional activities.

(54.8%) (43.3%) (0.9%) (0.9%)

Mean = 43.530; Median = 43.000; Std. Dev. = 4.312; Skeweness = -.211; Kurtosis = -.383

The result in Table 2 revealed that most of the respondents agreed that they are effective in classroom management (Mean = 3.627; Std. Dev. = .522); agreed that they are involved in making rules and regulations in their school (Mean = 2.7604; Std. Dev = .750); agreed that they give suggestions that counts in vital issues in the school (Mean = 3.0553; Std. Dev. = .567); agreed that they demonstrate sound knowledge of the subject matter (Mean = 3.512; Std. Dev. = .554); agreed that they adhere strictly to school time table (Mean = 3.544; Std. Dev. = .569); agreed that they achieve educational goals and objectives set (Mean = 3.493; Std. Dev. = .528); agreed that they give performance feedback to students promptly (Mean = 3.452; Std. Dev. = .568); agreed that their students always understand their lesson instructions (Mean = 3.410; Std. Dev. = .579); agreed that they are recipients of several awards on this teaching job (Mean = 2.843; Std. Dev. = .709); agreed that they conduct regular continuous assessment and mark tests/assignments promptly (Mean = 3.387; Std. Dev. = .607); agreed that they are always found at this teaching duty post (Mean = 3.507; Std. Dev. = .545); agreed that they love the job so much they complete the syllabus in their subjects within the stipulated time (Mean = 3.419; Std. Dev. = .634); agreed that they keep accurate and adequate records of instructional activities (Mean = 3.521; Std. Dev. = .570).

The overall scores for productivity among teachers in selected public secondary schools in Ogun State are mean (43.530); median is (43.000); standard deviation (4.312);

Hypothesis One: There will be no significant impact of nepotism on teachers' productivity.

Table 3: Model Summary for the Influence of Nepotism on Productivity of Teachers in the Selected Government Secondary Schools

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	4.530	1	4.530	.243	.623 ^b
Residual	4011.526	215	18.658		
Total	4016.055	216			
Model Summary R = .034; R ² = .001; R ² _(Adj) = -.004; Std. Error = 4.320					

a. Dependent Variable: Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Nepotism

The results in Table 3 indicate that when nepotism enters into the regression model alone, there is no significant prediction of teachers' productivity in the selected public secondary schools (R = .034; R² = .001; Adj R² = -.004; F_(1,215) = .243; p > .05). This shows that nepotism accounts for -0.4% of the variance in teachers' productivity in the selected schools.

The null hypothesis, which states that there will be no significant influence of nepotism on the productivity of teachers in the selected government secondary schools, is accepted by this finding. This implies that there is no significant influence of nepotism on the productivity of teachers in the selected government secondary schools.

Discussion of findings

For the first research question, the finding reveals a low prevalence score of nepotism among teachers. Respondents disagree with statements indicating that job enlistment is through relationships with people in leadership. The respondents also disagree with job enlistment without relevant and appropriate qualifications. This implies that almost all teachers are employed not because they are related to people in leadership but because they have relevant qualifications. This findings negate the submission by Jhatial (2012), who reported that 80% of respondents in the government sector agreed that connection or ‘sifarish’, references, sycophancy, and cronyism play a significant role in the Human Resources Management decision-making process, whereas only 20% of respondents find that it is merit-based.

The outcome of the second research question on the extent of teachers’ productivity in selected public secondary schools in Ogun state indicates a generally high score. Respondents agreed with statements indicating good qualifications, efficiency on the job, autonomy, motivation, and a positive outlook on life in the discharge of teaching duties. This implies that the selected schools’ environment have low prevalence scores of nepotism. This means that nepotism does not prevail in the schools in the local Government Area which could have aided the high extent of teachers’ productivity. This agrees with Osuji et al. (2011) whose study reveals that there is a high and positive relationship between improved work environment, relaxation, and teachers’ productivity. Put differently, a positive school environment defined by Edo and Nwosu (2018), as “all existing circumstances affecting labour in the workplace organizational climate and workload,” aids teacher productivity.

For the hypothesis, the finding shows that there is no significant influence of nepotism on Teachers’ productivity. This finding is in agreement with Chukwuma et al, (2019) who examine the relationship between nepotism and emotional engagement among selected radio stations in South East, Nigeria, and reveal that nepotism does not significantly impact emotional engagement which enhances the productivity of workers in the selected radio stations. This finding, however negates Abdelghany & Karima (2021) who observed when investigating nepotism's effect on nursing staff job satisfaction, organizational commitment and intention to quit that nepotism has a highly statistically adverse effect on job satisfaction, leading to intention to quit among nurses.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, this study concludes that the secondary schools in Abeokuta South LGA understand ‘nepotic’ behaviours in their varying dimensions and do not practice it. Thus, the absence of nepotism in these schools could have been responsible for the high extent of productivity of teachers.

Recommendations

Given the findings stated earlier, the following recommendations are made in line with the findings:

A positive school culture that fosters a collaborative, inclusive and supportive school environment that encourages teachers to work together, share best practices and prioritise students' success is a key factor that should be considered by school leaders for productivity.

An implementation of merit-based evaluation systems that use objective performance metrics to assess teachers' productivity and effectiveness, reducing the influence of personal biases and favouritism will go a long way in enhancing and sustaining the productivity of teachers.

It should be a matter of policy that schools should engage in blind hiring and promotion by using anonymous applications and evaluations to reduce bias in managing their Human Resources as such qualified teachers will be hired and it will.

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EFFECT OF STUDENTS' BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE OF MATHEMATICS ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICS**AYOOLA, YEMISI, A. (PHD)¹, IJILA, PAULINA, O. (PHD)² AND AJIBADE, O.³**^{1,3}DEPARTMENT OF SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND MATHEMATICS
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13372606>**Abstract**

The study investigated effect of students' background knowledge of Mathematics on Senior Secondary School students' academic performance in Physics in Ilesa West Local Government Area of Osun State. The study was guided by two research questions. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 levels of significance. The study employed experimental design. The population comprised of one hundred (100) Senior Secondary School One (SSS1) students found in two (2) co-educational schools in Ilesa West Local Government Area of Osun state. The study sampled one hundred (100) SSS1 students randomly drawn from two public secondary schools. Simple Random Sampling Technique was used to select the sample used. The samples were divided into two groups, the experimental group N=50 and the control group N=50. Relevant data were gathered using Velocity-Time Graph Achievement Test (VTGAT). The instrument was validated by a Physics educator and another specialist in test and measurement. The reliability of the instrument used was established using Pearson's moment correlation coefficient which was found to be 0.73. t-test analysis was used to test the hypotheses raised. The study showed that students exposed to Mathematics teaching before being taught Physics performed significantly better in velocity-time graph achievement test than their counterpart that were exposed directly to Physics. This implies that there was a significant relationship between student's background knowledge of Mathematics and their academic achievement in physics. The researcher recommended that; teachers should improve Physics students' performance in the subject by exposing them to mathematical problems involving formulae and calculations. Also, science teachers should be science inclined and be versed in mathematical problems involving formulae and calculations.

Keywords: *Physics, Mathematics, Academic Performance*

Introduction

The advancement in technology in recent years has created a pace at which science becomes indispensable in all hemisphere of the modern society. At the heart of science lies Physics and Physics necessitates mathematical competence (Redish, 2006). Physics is one of the major natural science subjects that supplies the knowledge of the physical environment and matter to the learner. In the understanding of matter and its properties, mathematical analysis is inevitable because it has dealings with numeric entities. Therefore, the society has advanced in the manipulation of matter for beneficial uses because of the advanced understanding in the interaction of matter, force and energy. Physics serves as one of the most effective tools science uses to interact or utilize matter to meet human needs..

Young and Freedman (2004) defined Physics as an experimental science since its specialists observe the phenomena of nature and try to find patterns and principles that relate to those phenomena in the form of theories, physical laws or principles. Interestingly, the diversified concepts of the subject matter have made its study relevant in many disciplines, such as engineering, medicine architecture, integrated science, chemistry, science education and mathematics.

A complete understanding of the concepts in Physics requires fluency in the mathematical language in which these concepts are couched. However, many introductory, algebra-based Physics students perform poorly on mathematical problem solving tasks in Physics. Physics as one of the physical science subjects plays an important role in the technological development and industrial revolution of any nation. The knowledge of scientific skill in Physics is of tremendous use in solving diverse problems of humanity and providing solution to natural and artificial problems in the world at large. According to Esiobu, (2015) and Akinyemi &Orukotan (2005), Science, Technology and Mathematics (STM) education play a dominant role in the developmental effort of nations. The importance of Physics cuts across human endeavor such as Medicine, Pharmacy, Agriculture, Petroleum Engineering, Geology, Engineering, Industries and Computer. Mathematics, the creation, representation analysis, interpretation of numbers and symbols affects all aspects of the human environment significantly but at varying degrees.

Mathematics is and remains a dominant contributing factor to the performance of students in Physics and Chemistry and the control tool of Mathematics remains the basic skills underlying all scientific and technological skills. Mathematics is a subject that is related to other science subjects such as Physics and Chemistry in areas like number and numeration–fractions, logarithms indices, algebraic processes – solution of equations, variation, graph, and also in volume and students often perform poorly in the sciences (Jegede, 2012; Mkpananga, 2016). Although, Science has been accepted by many people including students as the bedrock for technological development they still feel that Mathematics is not necessary for achieving good performance in Science. The reason for this can be attributed to the controversy surrounding the nature of Mathematics (Hailikari, 2007) and one question beckoning for answer is under what branch of studies should Mathematics be classified? While one school of thought agrees that Mathematics is a Science another argues that Mathematics must be an Art. This later school of

thought is based on the fact that Mathematics, in its application is purely an Art. On the other hand students view Mathematics as a difficult school subject and so many of them tries to avoid it

Science has been regarded as the bedrock of modern day technological breakthrough. Nowadays, countries all over the world, especially the developing ones like Nigeria, are striving hard to develop technologically and scientifically, since the world is turning Scientific and all proper functioning of lives depend greatly on Science. Science is a dynamic human activity concerned with understanding the workings of our world. This understanding helps man to know more about the universe. Without the applications of science, it would have been difficult for man to explore the other planets of the universe. Science comprises the basic disciplines such a Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics and Biology. Many investigations have shown that secondary school students are exhibiting dwindling interest in Science. Besides, Physics is one of the Science subjects and one of the most difficult subjects in the school curriculum according to the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) (Samuel, 2016).

Studies have revealed that the academic performance of Nigerian students in Ordinary Level Physics was generally and consistently poor over the years. Physics is an important science subject that makes immense academic demands on the students in its learning. The learning of the Physics is difficult at best and almost impossible at worst but because of its enormous importance to science and technology, there is huge interest in student's achievement in Physics. In the light of this, the relationship between the background and classroom environments and students achievement in physics has generated a great deal of discussion for a long time. Family background should be an environment in which children have the opportunity to succeed and be happy. A conducive home influence manifests itself further in the school environment. It helps plan, execute and evaluate child's school experiences in relation to level of maturation and mental health of the child in order to help him/her excel academically.

Furthermore it has been x-rayed that some factors, which are attributed present in family contributes greatly to the academic performance of students. Among these are parental educational background, income, exposure, parental relationship with each other, strength of the family population, religion, sex differentiation, occupation etc. the interplay of these factors in the family determines to great extent the readiness of child to learn. Nevertheless, the influences of others factors like mental and physical disabilities can account for poor academic performance in physics..

Statement of the Problem

The decrease in academic performance of students in physics is alarming. This study is set out to examine the effect of good knowledge of Mathematics on secondary School students' academic performance in Physics. Physics is popular and known to be a boring subject among students in secondary schools. If this phenomenon is not addressed and is ignored, students who are neither interested nor motivated to learn this subject will increase and this will lead to negative attitude and perception towards Physics. In schools, teachers have always commented

that failure in Physics performance by some students is due to their poor background knowledge in Mathematics.

Shallow knowledge of mathematical concept affects internal motivation which in turn affects the academic achievement and students' participation in various subjects especially in Physics. Physics has always been perceived as a tough subject compared to its other two pure science subjects which include Biology and Chemistry. Hence, this research work investigated the effect of students' background knowledge of Mathematics on students' academic performance in Physics.

Purpose of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the effect of students' background knowledge of Mathematics on Senior Secondary School Students' academic performance in Physics. The study intends to specifically:

1. Investigate the relationship between students' background knowledge of Mathematics and their academic performance in Physics in secondary schools.
2. Examine the relationship between mastery of Mathematics and easy calculations of Physics by Secondary School Students

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between students' background knowledge of Mathematics and their academic achievement in Physics in secondary schools
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between mastery of Mathematics and easy calculations of Physics among Senior Secondary School Students.

Significance of the Study

The imperativeness of this study cannot be underrated. The study will be of high significance in that it will help the following categories of people in the following ways; teachers, parents, students and school administrators to consider the relevance of background of students in Mathematics to their academic performance in Physics.

This study will serve as an eye opener to the teachers in knowing the importance of students' background knowledge of Mathematics as a predictor of academic achievement in Physics. This research work will serve as information to the teachers on existing factors affecting students' performance in Physics especially in Secondary School.

The school authorities will benefit immensely from this study, as it will help to keep them informed on the use of effective mastery of Mathematical concept to influence better achievement in Physics in Schools.

The research work will help the government to see reasons why trained and qualified teachers should be recruited into our Secondary Schools, and why seminars and workshops should be organized by the government for the teachers to update their knowledge in Physics and Mathematical calculations.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design is an experimental study which involves two groups: The control group and the experimental group.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study consisted of one hundred (100) Senior Secondary School one (SSS 1) students randomly selected from two public Senior Secondary school in Ilesa West Local Government Area. From each secondary school selected, fifty (50) students were selected using stratified random sampling technique where male and female formed different stratum which include twenty-five male and twenty- five female students. One of the schools selected was assigned to be experimental group while the other was assigned to the control group.

Research Instruments

The research instruments used for this study were well prepared lesson notes on velocity-time graph in Physics and area of trapezium in Mathematics. The second instrument is a well-structured standardized achievement test titled “Velocity-Time Graph Achievement Test”. This is an achievement test containing two theory questions on (VTGAT).

Validity of the Instruments

The validity of the instrument was ensured by given it to the experts in Test and Measurement and those in field of Physics for face, content and construct validity.

Reliability of the Instruments

The reliability of the instrument Velocity-Time Graph Achievement Test (VTGAT) was ensured through test-retest method on selected Secondary Schools which was not formally included in the main study. The instrument was administered twice within an interval of two weeks on twenty (20) students. The two sets of responses were compared using Pearson Product Correlation Statistics. Reliability co-efficient of 0.73 was obtained for (VTGAT). The co-efficient was considered high enough for reliability of the instrument.

Experimental Procedure

The researcher made a formal visit to the two sampled schools with a letter of introduction to seek the Principals' permission. After which, the pre-test was carried out on Senior Secondary School 1 (SSS1) students by administering the VTGAT to ascertain their knowledge of the content. After which their scripts were marked to ascertain that both the control group and experimental group are at the same entry level.

After the pre-test, the researcher with the help of the schools' Physics teacher commenced the treatment. The treatment was when students in each group were exposed to teachings on velocity-time graph and while the experimental group was taught in addendum, how to calculate the area of trapezium in Mathematics. The treatment program lasted for two weeks as the teacher taught them once in a week using a period each week.

After the treatment, the researcher proceeded to administer the Velocity-Time Graph Achievement Test (VTGAT) on both groups within a pre-determined time sufficient to finish the questions. After this, the researcher gathered and marked the scripts and the results for both groups were compiled for analysis.

Data Analysis

The data collected for the study were analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was used to answer the research question raised while inferential statistics, t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses generated. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between students' background knowledge of Mathematics and their academic achievement in Physics in Senior Secondary Schools

Table 1: Comparison of the mean and standard deviation of experimental and control group in the Velocity-Time Graph Achievement Test.

Group	Number (n)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	50	13.84	10.34	9.3
Control	50	4.54	4.80	

Results from table 1 revealed that the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics and then later taught Physics was 13.84 while that of those taught Physics alone was 4.5. The difference of 9.3 in mean shows that the experimental group performed better than the control group. t-test was used to show whether the difference in mean was statistically significant or not.

The result is as presented in table 2.

Table 2: t-test showing relationship between Students' background knowledge of Mathematics and their academic achievement in Physics.

Group	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	t-cal.	t-crit.	ρ	Decision
Experimental	50	13.84	10.34	5.77	2.00	0.05	Rejected
Control	50	4.54	4.80				

Table 2 revealed that the calculated value 5.77 is greater than the critical value 2.00 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the difference in mean is statistically significant and so the null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

. That is, there was a significant relationship between students' background knowledge of Mathematics and their academic achievement in Physics in Secondary Schools.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between mastery of Mathematics and easy calculations of Physics among Seniors Secondary School students

Table 3: Comparison of the mean and standard deviation of experimental and control group in the Velocity-Time Graph Achievement Test.

Group	Number (n)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	50	13.84	10.34	9.3
Control	50	4.54	4.80	

Results from table 3 revealed that the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics and then taught physics was 13.84 while that of those taught physics alone was 4.5. The difference of 9.3 in mean showed that the experimental group performed better than the control group. t-test was used to show whether the difference in mean is statistically significant or not. The result is presented in table 4.

Table 4: t-test showing relationship between mastery of Mathematics and easy calculations of Physics among Secondary School Students.

Group	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	t-cal.	t-crit.	ρ	Decision
Experimental	50	13.84	10.34	5.77	2.00	0.05	Rejected
Control	50	4.54	4.80				

Table 4 shows that the calculated value 5.7 the critical value 2.00 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the difference in mean is statistically significant and so the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. That is, there was a significant relationship between mastery of Mathematics and easy calculation of Physics among Secondary School Students.

Discussion of the Findings

The discussion of the findings was done in relation to the results obtained from the results of testing of the hypotheses guiding this study. The results of testing of hypothesis 1 showed that students taught Mathematics that is having background knowledge of Mathematics performed better in Physics than those taught without background knowledge of Mathematics. The analysis revealed that a significant difference exists between the achievement of students having background knowledge of Mathematics and those without background knowledge of Mathematics. This finding was supported by Humanoid (2009) that Mathematics and Physics have always depended on each other. Many researchers have developed new Mathematical ideas while studying Physics and also developed new Physics ideas while studying Mathematics. Kim Hyoungsonas cited in Isaiah (2015) established that one of the major roles of Mathematics is to logically analyze and simplify various complex phenomenon and industrial problems. This is the reason behind the contribution of many Mathematicians to the development of natural science and engineering just by numerical definition of natural phenomenon. Also, the finding is in line with Stanley, (2012) asserted that Mathematics concerns itself with mathematical concepts and methods that can be applied in Science (Physics inclusive), engineering (Physics inclusive) and industries. This means Mathematics has direct or immediate applications in our natural world, including industries, engineering and environment generally. The study is also in conformity with the findings of Omeodu (2019) who found that students with High Mathematical competencies performed significantly better than those with medium or Low Mathematical competencies . This was confirmed in his work that there was a strong positive correlation between Mathematical competency and performance in Physics.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of student's background knowledge in Mathematics on Senior Secondary School Student's academic achievement in Physics .Based on the findings and interpretation of the study, students exposed to Mathematics teaching had significantly higher academic achievement than their counterparts that were not exposed to Mathematical teaching.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study;

- Physics teachers should be science inclined and be versed in Mathematical calculations.
- Science students, who aspire to excel in Physics should not ignore or exhibit truancy behavior toward Mathematics because Physics in particular has Mathematical aspects and

only those who know and can apply Mathematical principles, knowledge and ideas can excel in it.

- Physics students should be encouraged by teachers through extra lessons, seminars, orientation programmes, counseling, and guidance, to build their confident and ability in Mathematics. This will not only improve the performance of such students in Mathematics but also in Physics and Science in general.
- Science teachers, counselors, guidance, parents, educational psychologist, educational administrators, planners and policy makers should work together in enlightenment of science students on the relevance of Mathematics and its influence on other science subjects and Physics in particular.

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SHIFT WORK AND MARITAL STATUS AS DETERMINANTS OF WORK STRESS AMONG HOSPITAL EMPLOYEES IN IKENNE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OGUN STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Work stress among hospital employees is a critical concern affecting both individual well-being and organizational performance. This study investigates the influence of shiftwork and marital status on work stress levels among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government.

The study adopted a descriptive survey design and used a multi-stage sampling technique to select the 547 participants of this study. Three validated questionnaires were used for data collection, which was pilot tested through test-re-test. Four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated and tested. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics, simple linear regression, and Multiple Regression analysis fixed at 0.05 significance level.

The findings revealed that shiftwork has significant influence on work stress (Beta = -.342, $t = 8.378$, $p < .05$); marital status has significant influence on work stress ($t = 5.718$, $p < .05$); while it was also revealed that there is a combined influence of shiftwork and marital status on work stress ($F_{(2, 528)} = 36.906$, $p < .05$).

The study concluded that the combined effects of shiftwork and marital status significantly influence work stress among hospital employees in the area. This indicates that these factors interact to shape the overall experience of work-related stress among employees, emphasizing the importance of considering multiple factors simultaneously when addressing stress management strategies in the workplace.

Therefore, it is recommended that hospital management should review and potentially modify shiftwork policies to mitigate the impact of irregular or non-standard work hours on employee stress levels. This may include implementing more predictable scheduling practices,

providing adequate rest periods between shifts and offering flexibility in shift preferences where feasible.

Keywords: *Marital status, Shiftwork, Work stress.*

Introduction

The escalation of work stress among employees has become more pronounced due to heightened professional demands, particularly in healthcare. Notably, healthcare jobs are now acknowledged as some of the most stressful occupations, as emphasized by Onyiri, Amavi, Sunday and Chinda 2022; Tayo, Adeoye & Issah, 2014). The repercussions of excessive work stress extend to absenteeism, burnout, job abandonment, and heightened job dissatisfaction, all of which detrimentally impact occupational productivity. Heinen (2012) reports a staggering annual toll of over 1.1 million lives lost to job-related illnesses and workplace stress. While job stress is pervasive across various professions, hospital workers exhibit a heightened vulnerability compared to their counterparts in other healthcare domains (Glassberg et al. 2008).

The stress associated with providing health care compels millions of healthcare professionals worldwide to resign annually, with a notable increase in retirements surpassing constitutional limits. This phenomenon is a critical factor contributing to the ongoing shortage of health professionals in countries like Nigeria and other developing nations. The stress-induced proclivity of hospital workers to quit their jobs is underscored by Heinen's findings (2012), highlighting a strong correlation between the intention to leave the health profession and stress. This sentiment is echoed by a recent poll in several EU industries, revealing that 20–30% of workers perceive work-related stress as a threat to their health (Onyiri et al., 2022).

A concerning trend emerges, with 75% of hospital employees experiencing heightened workplace stress compared to a generation ago. The impact of workplace stress is evident in low employee turnover rates, with persistent distress leading to physiological and psychological issues, coupled with diminished enthusiasm for work responsibilities. Naghieh et al. (2016) underline that most job-related diseases causing missed work days are attributed to occupational stress.

Even in the healthcare sector, where stress is pervasive according to Mark and Smith (2011), the burden is substantial. Nelson's study (2019) further elucidates the strenuous nature of health practice, especially among hospital workers, contributing to burnout and stress-related symptoms. Challenges such as low enrollment in health professions and premature retirements exacerbate the shortage of healthcare workers, resulting in an inadequate response to emerging diseases in rapidly expanding populations. The strain is evident in the discrepancy between the actual hospital workers-to-patient's ratio in Nigerian hospitals (1:13) and the recommended ratios by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN) (1:6 and 1:4, respectively) (Zamanian et al., 2016). Global trends, as per the Global Emotions Report (2019), point to significant workplace stress levels, with countries like Nigeria recording a high prevalence at 58%.

Marital status serves as a significant indicator of stress affecting the occupational tasks of healthcare workers. In the competitive environment of healthcare workplaces, stress levels tend to be higher compared to other professions, impacting personal, professional, and overall well-being (Walton, Murray, and Christian, 2020). The personal and professional well-being of healthcare workers is closely tied to the quality of life, and prolonged stress can affect their performance (Dyrbye et al., 2019). Marital status plays a crucial role in determining the work efficiency and responsibilities of healthcare workers, affecting family care, financial management, and overall stress levels (Srivastava and Dey, 2020).

These healthcare workers, often considered role models, face unique challenges that can be detrimental to their personal and psychological health, with limited attention given to these aspects (Hungerford and Cleary, 2021). The scarcity of data on such conditions emphasizes the need for research to understand and address the impact of marital status on the work stress of healthcare workers (Hakim, Tahira, and Kalsoom, 2023). While marital status is recognized as an internal factor that can influence work fatigue, it is not considered a predominant factor compared to other internal factors (Evanoff et al, 2020). The working period is also associated with the adaptation of workers, with longer working periods posing a higher risk of work fatigue due to decreased stamina and increased pressure (Ferreira et al, 2019).

Uwannah., Egwuonwu, & James. (2022) established that the pressure an individual experience from work can affect other areas of that individual's life. For instance, when some married workers who are engaged in paid employment carries out two roles that are incompatible from the job and home, stress could arise leading to conflict which may adversely affect health as well as satisfaction (Mukarram et al., 2012) and they went further to opine that most married workers actively taking part in full time work are also the ones doing most of the house work at home. In a bid therefore to manage the two assignments successfully, conflict could arise (Ajayi et al., 2015). This conflict is eminent due to work scheduling, work orientation, marriage experience, presence of children and spouse engagement in paid work, marital tension and lack of child-care facilities (Adeoye & Afolabi, 2011; Chiappo & DiDona, 2014; Mukarram et al., 2012) hence marital status conflict could adversely lead to work stress among married employees. Chiappo and Didona (2014) strongly believe that work role interference with family roles may leave the worker in question to handle the family role before the work role and this may likely lead to absenteeism, lack of concentration, costly mistakes, accidents and injuries. Svedberg et al. (2018) in their studies conclude that marital status conflict could be the result of sickness absence excuses among men and women employees due to stress-related mental diagnosis.

Currently a majority of married mothers with children under age six are employed and employed wives contribute significantly to their families' total income (White & Rogers, 2002). In addition, women, like, men appreciate the personal rewards from paid work and value job advancement (Hodson, 1996). With respect to marriage, although marriage rates have declined in recent years, the great majority of men and women continue to marry (Cherlin, 1992). Although rates of divorce continue to be historically high, remarriage after divorce continues to occur for most women and men (Teachmen et al., 2000), suggesting that people place a high value on marriage. Work-related stress is the result of a conflict between the role and needs of the

individual employee and organizational, personal or ergonomic factors in their work place. There can also be an unacceptable tension between the demands of work and the individuals' life outside work. As stated by McCarthy, stress is often typified by a lack of control over conditions at work (2004). The workers' life away from the job can cause stress on the job. Burke and Weir, (2007) found that a close supportive marriage in which an employee can informally discuss job problems with his or her spouse is likely to prevent or reduce on the job stress and increase both family and occupational satisfaction.

In various organization however little or no work was carried out on these variables (shiftwork and marital status) among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, none has specifically examined these variables as determinants of work-related stress in public and private-owned organizations in the country. Therefore, this study examines the extent to which shiftwork and marital status determines work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. Hence the following hypotheses were raised:

Research Hypotheses

- Ho1:** There is no significant influence of Shiftwork on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.
- Ho2:** Marital status will not have any significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.
- Ho3:** There is no significant combined contribution on Shiftwork and marital status on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted the survey research design which enabled the researcher to collect data from the study participants without manipulating either of the independent or predictor variables (shiftwork and marital status) but measuring them as they pre-exist among the participants in this study. This is because the independent or predictor variables being investigated has already occurred and the researcher was only interested in determining their influence on the dependent or criterion variable (work stress).

Population of the Study

The target population for this study consisted of the 628 hospital employees in the 26 registered hospitals in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State., according to data obtained from the Nigeria Health Facility Registry (HFR).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A total number of 547 hospital employees were selected through multi-stage sampling techniques. At the first stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select 13 out of the 26 registered hospitals in Ikenne Local Governments Area of Ogun State representing 50%. This is to ensure that each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected.

At the second stage, total enumeration was used to select a sample of 547 hospital employees from the 13(thirteen) randomly selected hospitals. The total enumeration method was used because, it involves gathering data from the entire population rather than just a sample and also because of the following reasons; the population under study is relatively small, conducting a total enumeration becomes more feasible, it is more efficient to gather data from the entire population rather than sampling.

Research Instrument

The following instrument were used to obtain information

Demographic Data Inventory (DDI), Stress Rating Scale (SRS), Shiftwork Scale (SS)

Stress Rating Scale [SRS]

The Stress Rating Scale was developed by Levenstein et al (2000) and was adapted by this researcher to assess the quality of stress among hospital workers. The scale prompted response on stress which consists of 7 items which are rated on a 4-point Likert scale scoring from (strongly disagree) to (strongly agree). Sample items on this scale are:

My hospital offers retirement preparation for workers that are close to retirement age

My work environment is pleasant for workers of all ages

The Perceived Stress Questionnaire (PSQ) was developed as an instrument for assessing the stressful life events and circumstances that tend to trigger or exacerbate disease symptoms. With stress bearing significantly on the quality and consistency of the sleep cycle, the PSQ is a potentially valuable tool for evaluating the underlying causes of sleep disturbances. The scale is specifically recommended for clinical settings, though it has been employed in research studies as well. Population for Testing The PSQ has been validated with a population of in-patients, outpatients, students, and health care workers with a mean age of 31.8 ± 13.9 . Administration of the scale is a self-report, pencil-and-paper measure requiring between 10 and 15 min for completion.

Shiftwork Scale

The shiftwork scale was developed by Albishi (2021) and was adapted by this researcher to assess the quality of shiftwork among hospital workers. The scale prompted response on

shiftwork which consists of 8 items which are rated on 4-point Likert scale. Sample items on this scale are:

I feel more stressed working during a night shift system

I experience more health issues when working during night shift

The scale has demonstrated good instrument validity, the instrument was presented to three experts in the field of research and occupational health. The experts were asked to express their views about relevance, necessity and clarity of the questions. Inputs and feedback received from the experts were included while finalizing the instrument. Data Analysis Exploratory factor analysis was conducted to determine the underlying constructs of the study. Exploratory factor analysis is a statistical method employed to increase the reliability of the scale by identifying inappropriate items that can be removed and the dimensionality of constructs by examining the existence of relationships between items and factors when the information of the dimensionality is limited. To determine the correlations between the items in the identity matrix and determine the suitability of using factor analysis, Bartlett's sphere city test and Kaiser-Meyer-Elkin Test were performed. The degree of deviation from scores from the normal distribution was analyzed by examining asymmetry and kurtosis.

Reliability of instrument

To ensure that the instruments are consistent in measuring what it meant to measure, a pilot study was conducted. The research instruments namely Stress Rating Scale and Shiftwork Scale were administered to 20 hospital employees located in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State but outside the selected sample. The reliability test conducted shows Cronbach's Alpha of 0.762 showing that the instruments are reliable.

Table 3.3 Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient

S/N	Scales	No of items	Cronbach's Aplha Coefficient
A	Stress Scale	7	0.643
B	Shiftwork Scale	8	0.732
Total		15	0.762

Validity of Instrument

In order to ensure the instrument are valid in measuring what they are meant to measure, the supervisor and some lecturers in the Department of Education, Babcock University were able to ascertain the effectiveness of the scales for the research work. Some copies of the instrument were sent to different lecturers of the department and they confirmed that this test measures what it claims to measure.

Method of Data Collection

The research assistant, who has received training on data collecting techniques, assisted the researcher in administering the study questionnaire, which was used to gather data. A letter of introduction was obtained from the Department of Education, Babcock University, Ilisan-Remo. The researcher presented the study's goals and any related advantages to the hospital employees at each location. The researcher was then introduced to the staff by the hospital.

Hospital staff members who volunteer to participate were ensured of secrecy and urged to provide genuine and honest answers to the questionnaire topics. The assistant and researcher then gathered the completed questionnaire right away and expressed gratitude to the hospital administration and staff for their cooperation and transparency in the study. Thereafter, the data obtained was subjected to data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical methods of a frequency distribution (percentages, frequencies, mean, median, and standard deviation, displayed in tables and charts) was used to examine the participant demographic data. Regression analysis was utilized to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. Simple linear regression analysis was used to test hypotheses one, t-test was used to test hypotheses two while F-ANOVA analysis was used to test hypotheses three.

Results and Findings

Hypothesis One

Shiftwork will not have any significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Table 1: Model Summary and Coefficients of the simple linear regression analysis for influence of Shiftwork on work stress

R = .342				
$R^2 = 0.117$				
Adj. $R^2 = 0.115$				
Std.Error of the Estimate = 1.82407				
		Standardized		
	Unstandardized	coefficients		

	coefficients		Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
Constant	21.562	.283		76.264	.000
Shiftwork	-.137	.016	-.342	-8.378	.000

Dependent Variable: work stress

Table 1. revealed significant results (Beta = $-.342$, $t = 8.378$, $p < .05$). This implies that the null hypothesis is unsupported by the data and is therefore rejected. The alternative hypothesis is subsequently upheld, leading to the conclusion that shiftwork has a significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. Table 1. further revealed that shiftwork is negatively associated with work stress (Beta = $-.342$) and that shiftwork accounted for 11.7% of the variance in work stress (Adj. $R^2 = .117$).

Hypothesis Two

Marital status will not have any significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Table 2: Independent t-Test for influence of marital status on work stress

	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	T	Sig.
Single	238	8.6387	7.65857	492	5.718	.000
Married	256	12.5742	7.62982			

Table 2 revealed significant results ($t = 5.718$, $p < .05$). This implies that the null hypothesis is unsupported by the data and is therefore rejected. The alternative hypothesis is subsequently upheld, leading to the conclusion that marital status has a significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Hypothesis Three

Shiftwork, age and marital status will not have any combined influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Table 3: Model summary showing combined contribution and the F- ANOVA of the influence of Shiftwork and marital status on work stress

R = .350					
R ² = 0.123					
Adj. R ² = .118					
Std Error of Estimates = 1.82163					
Model	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
• Regression	244.909	2	122.4545	36.906	.000
Residual	1752.089	528	3.318		
Total	1996.998	530			

Dependent Variable: work stress

Table 3 revealed significant results ($F_{(2, 528)} = 36.906, p < .05$). The null hypothesis was therefore, rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that shiftwork and marital status have significant combined influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. Table 3 further revealed that shiftwork, age and marital status jointly contributed 11.8% of the variance in work stress (Adj. R² = .118).

Discussion of Findings

This study examined shiftwork, age and marital status as determinants of work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. It sheds light on several crucial aspects affecting work stress among hospital employees.

The first null hypothesis stated that shiftwork will not have any significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. This hypothesis was tested and found to be unsupported by data. It was subsequently rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that shiftwork has a significant influence

on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. The study found a significant negative association between shiftwork and work stress among hospital employees. This means that those engaged in shiftwork experience lower levels of work stress compared to those on regular schedules.

Shiftwork is a common practice in many healthcare settings, often necessary to ensure continuous patient care. The finding that shiftwork is associated with lower work stress contradicts common assumptions that irregular work schedules contribute to higher stress levels. However, it is essential to consider potential confounding factors such as job role, workload and support systems in the workplace that may influence this relationship. This finding corroborated Frost (2009) and Gerben et al. (2020) who found that shiftwork has a negative impact on sleep, physical health and mental well-being. The finding was also in line with Luk (2009) who found that work conditions including shiftwork are significant causes of workplace stress. The finding also supported Frick et al. (2018) whose findings showed that the consequences of shiftwork for occupational health include increased rates of tardiness, absenteeism, occupational accidents, decreased job satisfaction, higher occupational stress, lower work engagement, lower work performance, and overall higher levels of fatigue. Finally, this finding supported Patton (1990) and Plante (1995) whose study revealed that psychological and/or physical health issues resulting from work stress associated with shiftwork can have direct impacts on stress-related outcomes, including poor mental well-being.

The second null hypothesis stated that marital status will not have any significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. This hypothesis was tested and found to be unsupported by data. It was subsequently rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that marital status has a significant influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. The study found a significant difference in work stress between married and single employees, with married employees experiencing significantly greater levels of work stress compared to single employees. The higher work stress experienced by married employees could be attributed to various factors, including family responsibilities, financial pressures, and conflicts between work and family demands. This finding underscores the importance of considering employees' personal circumstances and support networks outside of work when addressing work stress. This finding corroborated Khanna (2020) who found that managing responsibilities such as raising children, domestic duties and adapting to diverse work schedules contributes to stress levels among married health employees. Hence, married individuals experience somewhat higher levels of overall stress, highlighting the potential impact of marital status on stress.

Finally, the third null hypothesis stated that shiftwork and marital status will not have any combined influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. This hypothesis was tested and found to be unsupported by data. It was subsequently rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis, leading to the conclusion that shiftwork, and marital status have significant combined influence on work stress among hospital employees in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that marital status is a significant determinant of work stress among hospital employees. The results suggest that married employees experience lower levels of work stress, potentially due to the emotional and practical support provided by a spouse. In contrast, single, divorced, and widowed employees may lack such support, leading to higher stress levels. Healthcare organizations should consider these differences when designing stress management interventions. Recommendations include offering counseling services tailored to employees' marital status, providing flexible work schedules to accommodate family responsibilities, and fostering a supportive workplace culture. Future research should explore the specific mechanisms through which marital status affects work stress, such as social support networks, financial stability, and family dynamics.

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QUALITY INCONSISTENCY: CONSEQUENTIAL POOR SYNERGY AMONG UNIVERSITY'S QUALITY ASSURANCE STAKEHOLDERS

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Abstract

Quality of education does not depend only on resource output, but also on the input, which encompass the external and internal quality assurance efficiency. For more than three decades, Nigerian University System has been criticised for input and output quality variations. It is against this backdrop that this study evaluated the quality assurance measures for effective output in universities in Southwest, Nigeria. 5 research questions were raised for this purpose. Survey research design was adopted for this study. The research population is one thousand four hundred and seventy-two professors from thirty-six universities in Southwest, Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to select five hundred and eighty-eight respondents. Eight universities were proportionally selected from three states of Oyo, Ogun and Lagos. Two instruments were used for data collection, namely; Questionnaire for External and Internal Quality Assurance Measures (QEIQAM) ($r = 0.86$) and the Evaluation Checklist (ECL) ($r = 0.78$). Data were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, and frequency count. The result indicated that universities in Southwest, Nigeria scored low on Compliance with National Universities Commission's benchmark for staff mix ($\bar{x} = 1.436$); Low on compliance with NUC provision for Staff quality, including NUC mandate of five postgraduate candidates per supervisor and mandate for university teacher certification ($\bar{x} = 1.358$); They equally scored low in Global/African Ranking (80%); Low on dominance at international space (in terms of students', teachers' publications) ($\bar{x} = 1.463$); However, they scored high on NUC request for academic staff to obtain Ph.D. ((75%); The study concluded that there is a contradiction between the perception of quality by the respondents on the ground and the results in accreditation exercises conducted by the NUC. It was recommended that any benchmark that scored low should be reviewed, for example, the NUC mandate for five postgraduate candidates per supervisor and the benchmarks that scored high should be enhanced. The External Quality Assurance Agency, must carry along their Internal Quality Assurance counterpart in all the policy plans for dexterity and adherence. The culture of window dressing for the purpose of accreditation should be discouraged by all universities.

Key words: Universities, External and Internal Quality Assurance Measures, Effective Input Quality Output.

Background to the Study

Quality assurance exercise within university circle, is a primary responsibility of university's External and Internal Quality Assurance Agencies, two bodies that are generally known for propelling the internal quality process and output of any higher education institution that must remain relevant in the present global university's competitiveness. Hence, Akinpelu (2000) argued that education without quality can even be more dangerous than no education. Fortunately, both the Nigerian chapter of the university's external quality assurance body and the first five home grown universities were established in 1962. The two quality assurance bodies were able to synergise and successfully positioned Nigerian University System at the forefront of global university competitiveness, even produced a Nobel Prize winner in Literature.

However, the flourishing story started shrinking, till date the system has been variously criticised for quality variation. For example, Oni (1995) said, it is believed in many quarters that the standards of education in Nigerian is in a steep descent, especially when people who had their education decades ago look back nostalgically to those good old times, in agreement, Olaleye and Babatope (2013) submitted that, it is disheartening to note that throughout the previous thirty years' Nigerian university system had kept on seeing a drop in quality. Benefactors or parents are sending their children and grandchildren to other countries in the region for quality education, (Obasi, 2004).

This study therefore is asking to know why the stakeholders resorted to criticism and seeming contention against self, instead to seek for solution and end the challenges quietly? For instance, Amidu (2023) cited Professor Siyan, Oyeweso, who delivered a lecture entitled, "Interrogating Issues in The Proliferation of Universities in Nigeria" at the 80 Interdisciplinary Research Discourse of the Postgraduate College, University of Ibadan on Tuesday, June 27, 2023. He blamed the leadership of National Universities Commission against proliferation of universities: unguardedly granting licence for new universities whereas the existing universities are seriously gasping for air due to inadequate funding, weak administrators, shortage of academic and administrative staff respectively, incessant and uncontrollable strike actions and acute brain drain, and finally counsels that funding and sustainability is one of the criteria to administer a competitive quality higher education system.

In the same vein, Gbenro (2017), quoting Idowu Olayinka who focused on that which makes an elite university is the nature of Human Resource, (HR), and inquired about the number of foreign lecturers and student's Nigerian universities could attract given the country's poor infrastructure conditions. However, on what seem to be a response to the above, Owe (2018) cited Prof. Adamu Abubakar Rasheed, the current Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission, as stating that Nigerian universities are failing to fulfil their mandate. In a seeming sharp divergence to Rasheed, Adepoju & Akinola, (2011) questioned the reliability of accreditation quality assurance reports when some universities scale through without being detected of sharp practices. Hence, Ade-Ajayi (2003) advocated outright proscription of the National Universities Commission, as it has become a Federal parastatal that could not be reformed.

Could it be that some of the benchmarks no longer met the purpose? Or could it as well be that the National Universities Commission (NUC) oversight functions have been compromised, thereby lost its thoroughness posture and sanction? Or still, that the universities are unable to continue meeting the expected standards? Is it possible that the universities have lost faith in some of the benchmarks that the National Universities Commission (NUC) has recommended? Additionally, could it also be that the universities internal administrations seized from being carried along by the external while drafting their benchmarks and regulations?

Providing leeway for the aforementioned apparent uncertainty, Oni (2014) stated that the success of the law on education depends on the cooperation, support, dexterity, effort, firmness, and steadfastness of all those who work under it. Also that, if there are good education laws, if the laws enjoy compliance by stakeholders, if there are right personnel to man the education system, and if the educational system is properly administered, the result will be a stable, qualitative and striving system of education that will stand the test of time.

The preceding assertion from Oni (2014) hereby served as a solid foundation for the expected direction of this research. That the created higher education laws and their implementations bear the burden of quality or worthlessness, superiority or inferiority, success or failure, and ability or inability to compete, all of which must include the following four elements: That higher education requires laws or regulations that must be close to zero flaw to guide its quality goals, that the laws must be well-drafted to drive the input process for quality output purpose, that the law must be generally accepted by all input stakeholders for cooperation and compliance, and that oversight functions must attract the dexterity necessary for it to be properly and strictly administered in order to be trusted and adhered to. Hence, to discover the reason for the decreasing in quality and the essence of the much criticisms by the two principal quality assurance bodies, this investigation evaluated the National Universities Commission guidelines or regulations, likewise to ascertain the collaboration between the external and internal quality assurance bodies, to see if their approach to the university's laws works well, poorly, or in no way at all to improve input quality assurance to achieve effective output.

National Universities Commission (2015), concord that the internal input measures for quality assurance are ensured in the powers granted to the Senate in the universities as the highest academic decision making body. Therefore, the selection of the three academically focused NUC benchmarks (Teacher Quality; Teaching Quality and Learning Quality), fits properly with the choice of university professors for this study's population, because apart from being the natural members of each university's Senate (the custodians of internal academic measures) they as well act as experts in the NUC accreditation membership team, and most times function at the level of accreditation panel's chairperson. Meanwhile, this research focused on the experience and awareness of the professors on the subject matter, not their intelligence.

Objectives of the Study

The primary goal of this research is to Evaluate stakeholders' attitudes toward Quality Assurance Measures for Effective Output in South-West Universities, Nigeria. Hence, to determine the level of legally mandated quality-focused benchmarks effect interaction or synergy

that ought to exist between the internal and external quality assurance of higher education in terms of oversight functions and compliance for effective output in Nigeria's South-West Universities.

Statement of the Problem

So much anti quality abnormalities have been detected in Nigerian University System over the course of more than three decades or more, as a result, there have been numerous critics alleging that the Nigerian university system's input and output are of low quality. The fact is that a large portion of the reactions come from the stakeholders of the two legitimately enabled bodies that are intended to create and uphold regulations and guidelines that are quality engaged and driven. What happened to all of the laws, regulations, and oversight functions of the National Universities Commission, including the various accreditations, among other things

Research Questions

Five research questions were raised in line with the variables and the evaluation models used in this study:

What is the level of compliance with NUC benchmark staff mix in Universities in South West, Nigeria?

Do universities comply with NUC provision for staff quality?

To what extent do universities in south west feature in global/ African ranking?

To what extent do universities in South-West dominate international space (in terms of students, publications)?

What is the level of adherence to Ph.D. criteria for academic staff in Southwest universities in Nigeria?

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for this study. The research population is one thousand four hundred and seventy-two professors from thirty-six universities in Southwest, Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to select five hundred and eighty-eight respondents. Eight universities were proportionally selected from three states of Oyo, Ogun and Lagos. Two instruments were used for data collection, namely; Questionnaire for External and Internal Quality Assurance Measures (QEIQAM) ($r = 0.86$) and the Evaluation Checklist (ECL) ($r = 0.78$). Data were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, and frequency count.

General Description of Data

Data analysed for this study was obtained from one major instrument (Questionnaire). Five hundred and five hundred and eighty-eight (588) Professors completed the questionnaire.

Answering Research Questions

Research Question 1. What is the level of compliance with NUC benchmark staff mix in Universities in South West?

Table 1 Universities Compliance with NUC Benchmark on Staff Mix

SN	Statement	Agree	Disagree	Mean	Std
1	NUC staff mix mandate of 20% professors is appropriate to achieve university's quality output	329	259	1.451	.498
2	NUC staff mix benchmark of 35% senior lecturers and Ph.D. with notable publication is not enough to achieve academic quality for my university	350	217	1.388	.487
3	NUC staff mix benchmark of 45% lecturers 1 (L1) and Assistant Lecturers (AL) is enough to achieve academic quality for my university	335	235	1.418	.493
4	My department complies strictly with the NUC staff mix mandate of 20 professors per Department	327	243	1.433	.495
5	My university is responsive in replacement of any shortage of academic staff in other to maintain NUC staff mix mandate	294	276	1.492	500
Total		1790	1610	1.436	0.394

The analyses in Table 1 shows universities level of compliance with NUC benchmark on staff mix. The criterion means of 1.5 was used to categorise items as low or high. Means obtained below the criterion mean are taken as low compliance with NUC benchmark while items above the criterion means are taken as high level of compliance. The result shows that all the six items representing 100 % of the total items are rated below the criterion mean. The table also shows grand mean of 1.436 which is below the criterion mean of 1.5. This implies that there is low of compliance with NUC benchmark on staff mix.

Research Question 2. Do universities comply with NUC provision for Staff quality?

Table 2 Distribution of Responses on Compliance with NUC provision for Staff Quality

SN	Statement	Agree	Disagree	Mean	Std
1	NUC staff development Scheme of SDS (seminars, workshops and orientations) is a laudable recommendation to my university	373	209	1.347	.476
2	NUC mandate that all academic staff should be encouraged to obtain a Ph.D. degree is good for the university	348	213	1.379	.485

3	NUC regulation on Professional Examination without quota is a quality mandate for my university	378	201	1.344	.475
4	My University makes provisions to motivate lecturers to attend staff development programme and conferences abroad for more updates	344	235	1.404	.491
5	NUC mandate for university teacher Certification	392	187	1.319	.466
6	NUC mandate of 5 postgraduate candidates for a supervisor is practiced in my department	200	379	1.430	.510
Total		1998	1386	1.358	0.478

Result in Table 2. shows the analysis of universities compliance with NUC provision for staff quality. The criterion means of 1.5 was used to categorise responses to item into high and low. Means obtained below the criterion means are taken as low compliance with NUC provision while items above the criterion means are taken as high level of compliance. The result shows that item number four (mean = 1.404, Std = .491) recorded the highest mean while item number five and 6 (mean =1.358, Std = .466) recorded the lowest mean. The table further shows that all (100 %) are rated below the criterion mean while the table also shows grand mean of 1.358 which is below the criterion mean of 1.5. This implies that there is low level of compliance with NUC provision for staff quality. Basil, Felix and Eno (2013) also found that Lecturers' participation in capacity building programmes is significantly low with respect to workshops, seminars, conferences, ICT training and mentoring. Yohanna and Simon (2013) submitted that the place of academic staff in any academic institution cannot be overemphasized. Peretomode and Chukwuma (2007) in their study revealed that a significant relationship existed between manpower development and lecturers' productivity. In addition, Asiyai and Oghuvbu (2009) reported that lack of staff development programmes accounted for the decline in quality of tertiary education in Nigeria. Similarly, Adeogun, (2006) noted that an employee who is not trained and exposed to continuous retraining in the modern methods and new discoveries in his or her field will soon become irrelevant to the organization. The study agrees with the report of Nwogbo (2018) the findings shows that public and private universities in Nigeria do not employ adequate measures towards ensuring quality of teachers for quality assurance.

Research Question 3. To what extent do universities in Southwest feature in Global/African Ranking?

Table 4.7: Distribution of Responses on Universities Ranking

Universities	Agreed	Disagree	Extent
1	8	5	High feature
2	20	135	Low feature
3	0	33	High feature
4	10	22	Low feature

5	30	105	Low feature
6	40	135	Low feature
7	2	16	Low feature
8	6	12	Low feature
Total	116	463	Low feature

Results in Table 4.7 shows extent to which universities in south west feature in Global/ African ranking. The distribution from the table shows that only one university seems to be aware and feature in Global/African ranking according to responses. The remaining seven universities do not agree to have current feature in Global/African ranking. This means that 20% of the sampled universities indicated high feature in Global/ African ranking while 80% of the sample universities indicated low feature on in Global/African ranking. . Hence it can be concluded that universities in South west feature to a low extent in Global/African ranking as perceived by staff. Performance gaps existing in the university to a great extent led to the low ranking of universities in Nigeria.

Global and national rankings has become inevitable in present day universities and cannot avoid national and international comparisons, this has caused changes in the way universities act and function having the consciousness to put the goals and objectives forward. university ranking has garnered a lot of significance in Nigeria owing to the necessity to have tools that can be used for management, policymaking, grant location, quality assurance, quality assessment, quality improvement, benchmarking and sustainability among other factors (Stolz, Hendel, & Horn, 2010)

Similarly, Adebayo (2007) commented that the non-inclusion of any of the nation's universities in the world best 500 universities is unsatisfactory and worse still, Nigeria ranked number 44 after Ghana, Kenya and South Africa in the ranking of African Universities. The purposes for ranking universities are basically three (Waltman et al 2013). Governments funding agencies and media need ranking information to measure performance indices of their universities; university administrators use rankings as marketing tool while parents and prospective students use ranking as a basis for choice of courses.

For university rankings to achieve these purposes however, the culture differences of the universities are ignored particularly at the global ranking level. Most literatures on purposes of web metric rankings focus on provision of information to students on which universities to attend and which subjects to offer. University rankings also form a basis for governments „to have a transparent and objective mechanism for identifying centres of excellence that could benefit from preferential funding. (Kighoto 2013; National Universities Commission (N.U.C.), 2012; Okojie, 2013). Factors responsible for low ranking are lach of consistent and affordable electricity supply, incessant strikes by university teachers. Inability of university to meet the capital and running cost of establishing both the internet and intranet facilities.

The desire of the universities to achieve in the academic might have an indirect impact on economic growth through increased productivity occasioned by better yields through teaching and learning. None of the Nigerian universities (public or private) is within the top 1000 in the world in 2013. Also, the quality of research carried out in Nigerian universities does not appear to favour collaboration which results in cut-edge researches. The frequency of strikes makes the Nigerian universities score very low. The negative consequence of this is that while many Nigerian universities might strive to scale up their Journal of Educational Studies. Reputable ranking bodies (ARWU, QSWUR, THEWUR) focus on specific criteria. Rykhtik, Baluev, and Efimova (2016) found that more than half of the students were not aware of various university rankings.

It was revealed that the state of awareness of the students influences their choice of university. This shows that students' lack of awareness about university rankings may impact their choice of university. Adeyanju et al. (2020) confirmed that university ranking influenced students' choice of university but university reputation had more influence on students' choice of university than university ranking. In Nigeria, university reputation is usually spurred by factors such as year of establishment, rave review of alumni in their various walks of life, the calibre of current students, and awards/recognition. However, university ranking has been adopted in recent years as a tool to boost reputation among Nigerian universities. Sabir, et al., (2013) found that Higher Education Commission ranking and reputation were part of the important predictors of students' choice of the university. Bastedo and Bowman (2010); and Bowman and Bastedo (2011) emphasized the influence university rankings have on the development of university reputation.

It was established in these studies that university rankings have an influence on potential university reputational assessments by stakeholders. Universities in Nigeria may not be able to attain higher ranking because there is less money to spend on teaching, research and community services. Libraries are ill equipped, laboratories lack essential apparatus, classrooms are dilapidated and office accommodations are a mirage (Babalola 2001).

Research Question 4. To what extent do universities in South-West dominate international space (in terms of students, teachers and publications)?

Table 4.1. Analysis of South West Universities dominance of International Space

SN	Statement	Agree	Disagree	Mean	Std	R
1	My university has the tradition of publications in renown international journals	300	279	1.497	.500	Low
2	My university standard attracts foreign students' enrolment	331	248	1.427	.495	Low
3	Foreign reputable lecturers apply to lecture in my university due to the	322	257	1.443	.497	Low

standards						
4	My university features favourably in the Global/Africa Sub-Region Rankings	317	262	1.452	.498	Low
5	My university has a Nobel winner in literature and sciences	322	257	1.496	.497	Low
		1.534	1.311	1.463	0.497	Low

Table 4.1 shows the analysis of the extent to which universities in south west dominates international space (publication and students). The criterion mean of 1.5 was used to categorise item responses. Means obtained below the criterion means are taken as low dominance of international space while items above the criterion means are taken as high level of dominance. The result shows that item 1 recorded the highest mean (mean = 1.497) while item 5 recorded the lowest mean (mean = 1.496). The table further shows that none of the items recorded up to 1.5 criterion mean thus, all the items are rated below the criterion mean.

The table also shows grand mean of 1.463 (Std = .497). The recorded 1.463 grand mean is also below the criterion mean of 1.5 and this implies that there is low level of compliance with south western universities dominance of international space (publication and students). Adomi and Mordi, (2003) submitted that insistence on publication of articles in foreign or international journals as a precondition for promotion implies that a paper accepted and published abroad is therefore adjudged to be better in terms of quality and content than the one published by a local or national journal as the publication processes of local journals have been subject to inappropriate influence.

Ondari-Okemwa (2007) identified the challenges to include lack of incentives, non-participation in scholarly conferences, language challenges, technological challenges, and environmental challenges. This study confirms the finding of Baro and Ebhomeya (2012) who reported low scholarly publication rate in Nigeria which suggests a problem of knowledge diffusion for the country and possibly low knowledge generation.

Research Question 5. What is the level of adherence to Ph.D. criteria for academic staff in South West Universities?

Table 5.1 Universities Adherence level with Ph.D. Criteria

Universities	Adherence	Low adherence
1	High Adherence	
2	High Adherence	
3		Low adherence
4		Low adherence
5	High Adherence	
6	High Adherence	
7	High Adherence	
8	High Adherence	

Result of analysis in Table 4.3 represents the responses of 8 universities represented by figures one to eight. The result shows that 75% representing responses from six of the sampled universities that adhered to NUC mandate on encouraging staff to obtain Ph.D. While 25 % represents the two universities of the sample shows low adherence to NUC mandate on encouraging staff to obtain Ph.D. Thus, universities in South-West showed high adherence to NUC request for academic staff to obtain Ph.D. In order for the goals of tertiary education to be effectively achieved, the National Universities Commission (NUC) 2014 made the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) degree the minimum teaching qualification for academic staff in Nigeria universities. The importance of Ph.D. was further re-emphasized when NUC remarked that professional societies should not equate fellowship of anybody with Ph.D..(NUC, 2021). Not feeling the names of universities in table 4.2 is for ethical reasons

Summary

This study hereby summarised that Quality of university education does not solely depend on resource output, but includes the input, which incorporates the external and internal quality assurance effectiveness. For more than three decades, Nigerian University System has been criticized for input quality variations, and the quality of its output. It is for this reason that this study evaluated stakeholders' attitude towards the quality assurance measures for quality output in universities in South-West, Nigeria. Five research questions were raised for this purpose.

Survey research design was adopted for this study. Simple random sampling was use to select five hundred and eighty-eight (588) Professors, while all the Deans and Provosts from the eighty-two (82) faculties, in eight (8) proportionally selected universities in Ogun, Lagos and

Oyo States were selected to fill the research checklist. Two (2) instruments were used for data collection, namely; Questionnaire for External and Internal Quality Assurance Measures (QEIQAM) ($r = 0.86$) and the Evaluation Checklist (ECL) ($r = 0.78$) were used. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, and frequency count.

The result indicated that universities in South-West, Nigeria scored low on Compliance with National Universities Commission's benchmark for staff mix; compliance with NUC provision for Staff quality, including NUC mandate of five postgraduate candidates per supervisor; feature low in Global/African Ranking; and low in dominance at international space (in terms of students' teachers' publications). However, they scored high on National Universities Commission' request for academic staff to obtain Ph.D.

Conclusion

The study concluded that for respondents to have scored low on seven (7) out of the ten (10) items analysed, while scoring high on three (3) only, is an indicative of contradiction between the perception of quality by the respondents on the ground and the results in accreditation exercises conducted by the National Universities Commission. It included the respondents seemingly not very familiar with the output and input stands of their individual universities, and the possibility of poor oversight function and compromise on the side of the external quality assurance body.

Recommendations

It was recommended that the External Quality Assurance Agency, must not only carry along their Internal Quality Assurance counterpart in all the policy plans. External and internal oversight functions must be thorough, intentional and quality driven at all times. National Universities Commission must be strict and meticulous in awarding sanctions or commendation to any recalcitrant or compliant university to ensure improvement in quality. The bottleneck to access Tertiary Education Trust Fund should be reviewed. Any benchmark that scored so low should be reviewed or expunged if possible, for example, NUC mandate for five postgraduate candidate per supervisor and the certification as qualification to teach. The benchmarks that scored high should enjoy quality enhancement. While international publication will bring about visibility of the university, local publications should also be encouraged, because it solves immediate and local problems, meanwhile, the international reputable journals were once local breeds. The culture of window dressing for the purpose of accreditation should be discouraged by all universities.

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EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY IN NIGERIA: EMPHASIS ON THE INTRODUCTION OF ELECTRONIC-LEARNING SYSTEM IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study aimed at describing the inequality that exist in the education system in Nigeria, it evaluated the possible consequences of an already existing inequity in the Nigerian educational system as made more popular by the unexpected health emergency of coronavirus and also attempted to investigate how the government is addressing the issue of inequity in access to e-learning and examined the limitations hindering the wide spread of electronic-learning infrastructures in Nigeria. The research concluded that the introduction of the electronic-learning form of education in Nigeria shows that technology has really transformed almost all aspects of human life in Nigeria and that Nigerians can keep pace with their global counterparts as it concerned education in the face of problems such as the one posed by dreaded coronavirus pandemic that resulted in global lockdown and closure of schools. However, there still remained the issue of social exclusion of the majority of poor Nigerians who cannot access this form of education. It therefore recommended that the government at the three levels government authority should put in place programs to alleviate the endemic poverty among Nigerians, there should be improvement of infrastructures in the country and there should be equity in the educational system in Nigeria.

Keywords: *inequality, inequity, equality, equity, e-learning, social-exclusion, access and alleviation*

Introduction

The pattern of education system in the developing countries has failed to cover up the gap between the wealth and poor (UNESCO Meta Survey, 2004). Rather, the form of education has widened the space of educational inequality, despite the crucial place of education as a key reason in gaining status and moving in the upward in social ladder, as well as a determinant of one's life styles and chances (Morgan and Morgan 1998; Onwuameze 2013).

In most developing countries, access to education has always remained a serious problem (Moll, 2004; Yuthas & Epstein 2012). In Nigeria, for example, about 13.2 million school children with in the age of 5-14 years are not in school, making it the highest in the world. Only 61% of 6 to 11-year-olds regularly attend primary school. Some states in the north east and north west Nigeria have more than half of the girls not enrolled in schools as marginalization ensures that girls are deprived of basic education. Nigeria contributes approximately 20% of the total global out-of-school population (UNICEF, 2020).

Issues regarding access are due to individual differences, selection methods, cost and inadequate finance, gender discrimination, humanitarian emergencies and armed conflict, limited capacity, poor or lack of infrastructures and unavailability of qualified teaching staff (Garba 2014 and Nwogu 2015). Various strategies to bring to the barest minimum the disparity has been on the going before the advent of coronavirus, to ensure young children stay in school and have access to proper education. However, the inequality gap between students in different financial situations, which has been present in education systems for a long time, is being exacerbated by the Coronavirus pandemic. The pandemic has, as well, has further compounded the existing educational inequalities, with vulnerable and disadvantaged children at the receiving end. “These inequalities are a real threat to learning continuity at a time of unprecedented educational disruption” (UNESCO, 2020). Children in rural and underserved communities in Nigeria are being left behind as they are not equipped to adapt or transition to new methods of learning. As emphasized by UNESCO, 2020, temporary school closure comes with high social and economic costs, with severe impact on children from disadvantaged background.

Coronavirus pandemic has adversely affected institutions globally. It has made government across the world to temporarily shut down and restricted the movement of people while exempting providers of essential services who are to strictly observe social distancing rules while providing services as a way to contain the spread of the virus. Due to the disease pandemic, more than 99 percent of the world's learners, around 1.725 billion learners, are out of school, in 190 countries and regions (UNESCO 2020). With the advent of the coronavirus pandemic, cyber learning has become the most available alternative way to obtain knowledge and keep up with classes for students. Several technological innovations have been embraced to cushion the effect of the pandemic, replacing the face-to-face engagements. Cyber learning has been made possible through electronic learning platforms, video lessons, increased numbers of cyber courses (MOOCs), and use of various social media platforms and aired through radio and television. However, the success of online learning centers on the availability of power supply, internet connectivity, digital skills of teachers and students, and the availability of learning infrastructures. As innovative as this technology is, it is only accessible to learners from more privileged socio-economic background, while learners from low-income communities will be left out and being to access learning during this period.

Since the lockdown began in Nigeria, it has drawn the attention of many actors, (government, educational institution and international organizations) questioning the readiness as it relates to the availability of infrastructures to cater for the estimated number of students (46 million) affected, the skills required by both the students and the tutors to engage in remote learning, and the majority of students who do not have access to the online learning platforms

recommended. Furthermore, in sub-Saharan Africa, 89 percent of learners do not have access to household computers and 82 percent lack access to the internet, which are necessary to aid online learning. The momentary school closure comes with high social and economic costs, with severe impact on children from disadvantaged background (UNESCO 2020). Evidently, coronavirus is magnifying the educational inequity in Nigeria as only those with access to digital learning resources will keep learning in the comfort of their homes while those without access (the majority) are left behind.

While the increase in the influx of technology has been applauded for combating the issue of social divide (Kling, 2000), and an alternative to combat inequalities (McLuhan 1996), it has also been contested that it is a means of promoting stratification as well as inequality (Carr-Chellman 2005). Information pertaining to the introduction of the online learning mode around the world show the countries' agreement on switching over to a new mode of education that is, online learning, keeping in mind its perceived benefits of extended access to quality education, the benefits of online learning are looked at without much attention being paid on individuals (majority) who do not have access not because they do not like the technological innovation but as a result of lack of access.

Disparity in the education system serves the purpose of drawing the line between two classes by maintaining the status quo of elites (Bari and Sultana, 2011). In this process of class inequality, educational institutions are serving as agents of transforming certain values to specific classes. While applying this thought to educational system in Nigeria, a clear segregation of public and private institutes is visible, setting on different standards of pedagogy and affordability. Public educational institutions are perceived to serve the middle and the poor social class and private schools are set for specific groups of the upper-class. Due to unaffordability, the middle and poor classes are bound to send their children to public institutes that are perceived as economical and of low quality (Bowles and Gintis, 2013). This case is typical of the educational system in Nigeria. Worthy of note, only few private institutions in Nigeria have successfully adopted online learning in the teaching of their students. While some schools had since commenced their individual online learning programs, others reawakened at the dawn of the lockdown.

However, one major issue that will stem from this inequality is that these students who currently cannot maintain with their peers thanks to inaccessibility to digital tools may never catch up and can still feel the effect of this gap long after the pandemic is over. This might end in a severely diminishing pool of young adults who haven't garnered the required skills to remain ahead within the future. With Nigeria already behind in preparing its graduates for the workplace of the long run, the consequences of the pandemic further exacerbate this issue. The magnifying educational inequality in Nigeria, has created a scarcity within the knowledge gap and is probably going to culminate within the un-employability of the learners upon graduation.

It is against this background that this study examines the inequalities that emerge within the educational sector as a result of electronic learning. It also attempts to interrogate how the government is addressing the difficulty of inequity in access to online learning and also the challenges inhibiting the wide spread of online learning infrastructures in Nigeria.

Review of Literature

Educational Inequality and Inequities: Effects on Online Learning

Education could be a principal instrument of bringing about changes within the lives of people, and it also helps to direct the society within which they live. Education is thought to be a tool for development (Fafunwa, 1980). It's been said that the standard of the education of the people determine the speed of their development. Oyekan (1994 & 1997) sees education as never-ending development whose broad understanding and application enable individual to contribute meaningfully toward the expansion and development of the society.

Fairness and inclusion in education (Field, Kuczera & Pont, 2007) ensures every child, with no restraint, is entitled to all or any levels of education to succeed in their learning potentials. In essence, personal or socio-economic circumstances, like gender, ethnic origin or family background shouldn't inhibit the education of any child. The needed resources to effectively facilitate online learning isn't available to most) students because of effects of social and economic inequalities. Access to education is way impacted by students' background (OECD, 2010a). A baby whose parents are well educated tends to own access to books, journals and other learning resources, which can consequently improve such child's academic achievements.

Educational equality implies that all students receive equal access to the identical educational pathways. All students should be afforded the chance to develop the knowledge and skills necessary to realize their future goals. Conversely, inequities within the education system still stifle those opportunities for several students especially within the aspect of online learning. The web has become one in all the vital ways to form available resources for research and learning for both teachers and students to share and acquire information (Richard & Haya, 2009). Technology based online learning encompasses the utilization of the net and other important technologies to supply materials for learning, teach learners, and also regulate courses in an organization (Fry, 2001). European Commission (2001) describes online learning because the use of latest multimedia technologies and also the internet to extend learning quality by easing access to facilities and services furthermore as distant exchanges and collaboration. Clark & Mayer (2011) help define online learning as instruction delivered by any technological mode intended to market learning.

In recent decades, the utilization of data and communication technologies for educational purposes has increased, and also the spread of network technologies has caused online learning practices to evolve significantly (Kahiigi et al., 2008). Sims et al., (2005) and Lewin et al., (2003), assert that the benefits from the utilization of educational technology is restricted to those whose homes have high cultural capital. It's not simply a matter of getting physical access to technology, or perhaps of participating in online learning, but knowing a way to use of information and communication technology and, or, online learning in an exceedingly

way which maximizes one's opportunities and using it to consolidate advantages that one may enjoy offline. There are plethora of evidence that students from lower socio-economic who have low exposure and knowledge in ICT wouldn't be enthusiastic in online learning, this can ultimately affect their performances in class especially within the face of the constraints caused by the coronavirus pandemic.

The proportion of scholars from lower socio-economic backgrounds, who cannot currently afford a computer to be used reception or internet access while they're studying is unknown but one can assume it an unlimited majority. It could even be speculated that students from lower socio-economic background may, for financial reasons, have slower take-up of every new device or technology that comes onto the market which offers internet access. Access to online learning in a very kind of ways and from a spread of devices may therefore still be unequally distributed on the premise of one's economic or status.

Educational Equity and Equality: Government's Roles towards a higher Education through Online-learning

An equitable education system can redress the effect of broader social and economic inequalities as student's life chances are high that strongly influenced by the standard of their education. Attention on equity takes into consideration the varying personal experiences and social identifiers that impact students' educational opportunities, including race, gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, disability, family background et al. to handle these inequities, government must first understand that diverse students have diverse needs.

Government policies must support parents and students in such the simplest way that they'll all get pleasure from online learning education because it plays a vital role in breaking the link between socio-economic background and life prospects. Research shows that information and communication technology plays a number one role in promoting the economy of a rustic and studies have shown that the rapid development of economies in countries like China, Brazil, India, Russia and other developed economies is attributed to the impacts of information and communication technology. So as to develop socially and economically, government should make computer and other information and communication technology facilities cheaper and affordable to the people and supply of information and communication technology facilities and infrastructures within the rural areas, to form online learning accessible for educational growth and skill acquisition.

Along with a commitment to educational policy reforms, it's imperative for government- policymakers, to harness their power to create equity-focused policy decisions. States should strive for equity in educational opportunities, providing all students with the unique supports they have to succeed, since they need power to advance educational equity by targeting resources and crafting policy that challenge the establishment. Success in improving equity in education also depends upon other policies (such as health, housing, welfare, justice, social development). Thus, there's urgent must reinforce the importance of fostering the links between these areas. While the education system is chargeable for giving students the opportunities for

educational achievement, other government policies also have to be aligned to confirm students' success.

In this age of knowledge technology, a concept which will make citizens not just computer literate but capable of using electronic media to hold out daily functions including learning should be put in situ. With this, government's efforts to produce education for those that desire and qualify for pedagogy would be accomplished. Also, that specialize in provision of education that promotes equity by recognizing and meeting different educational needs (Faubert, 2012) must be implemented because it is one in every of the key drivers of intergenerational social and income mobility (Causa and Chapius, 2009).

The relationship between goals of efficiency and equity can take many various forms: certain educational policies can make education systems more efficient, without having a negative impact on equity; within the same way, some policies can make systems more equitable without hindering efficiency. Government can reply to equity and efficiency concerns and develop synergies among them (Woessman, 2008). Designing the correct policies to boost equity and improve online learning is essential; but so has well-developed means for turning those policies into action across large numbers of faculties and communities. For this, resources and levels of governance in pursuit of those goals have to be aligned (OECD, 2010a).

Addressing the challenges faced by disadvantaged individuals in accessing online learning might sound to be a difficult endeavor as improvements across a complete schooling system can come only with strong and consistent political support and leadership sustained over time. Designing fair and inclusive education systems could be a stepping stone to providing top quality education for each child. Inappropriate design and practices of education systems allow educational inequities and faculty failure (Hanushek and Woessmann, 2010). The best performing OECD education systems develop comprehensive education systems that provide top quality opportunities to the overwhelming majority of scholars, compensating for disadvantages caused by students' family backgrounds and private circumstances (OECD, 2010a).

As an example, recent reforms in Germany and Poland have improved both academic achievement and narrowed the gap between students (OECD, 2011a). Replicating such education systems won't only improve the individual but compliment the expansion of the country. For the next performing education system, government policies should accommodate top quality and equity. In such education systems, the overwhelming majority of scholars can attain high level skills and knowledge that depend upon their ability and drive, quite on their socio-economic background.

Challenges Inhibiting the Wide Spread of Online Learning Infrastructures in Nigeria While the reduction in overall cost and time (Gill 2000), convenience and adaptability (hall 1997), accessibility and better retention (Millbank 1994), reduced learning time (Hall 1997; Horton 2011), greater collaboration and interactivity (Kruse 2002), environment impact reduction (Roy, Potter and Yarrow 2008) make online learning appealing, it's been fraught with

numerous challenges. Despite the very fact that there's a growing and rapid demand for the acceptance and adoption of online learning worldwide, the challenges are numerous especially in Nigeria as a developing country (Oye, Salleh and Iahad 2011). Recent advancement in technology, specifically online learning, have the potential to narrow the digital educational divide (Journell 2007). Inequality within the Nigerian educational sector has remained constant throughout history, the means by which the system oppresses the underprivileged continually changes. One among the key factors deepening this variation is that the rise within the use of technology for learning. Olulube (2016) noted that, the main challenge faced by the education sector in Nigeria is that the insufficient budgetary allocation to the world. Furthermore, the annual budgetary provision for education in Nigeria is a smaller amount than 7 percent. Furthermore, the challenges identified as inhibiting the widespread of online learning in Nigeria, steams from the shortage of access, lack of computer literacy, inappropriate training of the top users, internet connectivity, energy, limited experts, and fear of online learning technology taking on jobs, among other.

Lack of access: The technology access can be a challenge for the educational process since the learner must have access to the net, own a private computer, and therefore the software and possess the requisite skills (Pongpech 2013). Salawudeen, (2010) noted that unequal of access to the technology itself by most students constitute a significant challenge inhibiting the spread of online learning in Nigeria. Therefore, if this challenge of access isn't resolved, online learning will only remain a task. Lack of access also cuts across the socio-economic status (SES) (Kazeem et al., 2010), gender (Colclough, Rose and Tembon 2000), geographical location (Ahmed 2010; Chen and Tseng, 2012).

The national of Nigeria through the Ministry of Education announced a free online learning portal intended to make access to online education across the state, likewise as radio and to classrooms. This, notwithstanding, has remained mere intentions as reports indicate that this is often not working and so not serving the required need of closing the tutorial gaps because of lack of instructional design and implementation but there was a scarcity psychological science tool to support online learning (Salem, 2020). In keeping with Salem (2020), the low rural internet penetration, lack of preparation, lack of online curriculum, unaffordability of necessary learning gadgets, low knowledge and skillset, present an enormous challenge, which has caused major setback for the adoption of online learning in Nigeria. Despite the efforts of the govt., the academic system remains lagging behind by not being functionally conscious of the current reality of online education. Further research shows that the amount of online learning and preparedness in Nigeria is about 10 percent or less (Nwagwu 2019). Hence, there's an urgent must salvage the already battered educational system that has been further humbled and bruised by the coronavirus pandemic.

Lack of computer literacy: Folorunso, Ogunseye & Sharma 2006; Olakulehin 2007 found that low computer literacy level could be a crucial factor that affects the acceptability of information and communication technology/online learning by students and teachers in educational institutions. Furthermore, the dearth of information and communication technology training for college students, teachers and/or lecturers makes it hard for them to produce digital

content, even when given all necessary infrastructures. Consistent with the net world stat (2020), there are about 757 million adults of which 115 million are youths that cannot read or write, talk less of having the ability to surf the net.

Poor infrastructure/Energy: per Mac-Ikemenjima (2005) and Oye et al. (2011), inadequate or non-availability of information and communication technology infrastructure including hardware and software, bandwidth access and epileptic power supply constitute challenges inhibiting the spread of online learning in Nigeria. The net learning technical infrastructure in Nigeria isn't highly developed, which implies that phone lines and internet connections are unreliable or slow thanks to narrow bandwidth. Studies Mac-Ikemenjima (2005); Oye et al., (2011) show that the majority users access the net in cyber cafes, with shared bandwidth or from their mobile phones, thus slow internet connections and high data usage, as not everyone encompasses a laptop computer or laptop.

In Nigeria the matter is made worse by the epileptic supply of electricity. Not too frequent and interrupted supply of electricity in Nigeria may be a perennial problem affecting almost every aspect of the economy, education inclusive. Ajadi et al. (2008) observed that it's been a serious setback for technological advancement within the country. Most rural areas in Nigeria aren't connected to the national grid. The consequence of this can be that students residing in such areas may find it difficult to use information and communication technology effectively. A number of the scholars that reside in cities and towns are equally faced with the matter of epileptic supply of electricity.

Operating cost: Cost is often mentioned joined of the foremost significant barriers toward accepting and putting to use online form of learning. The affordability of the of Information and communication technological gadgets may be an inhibiting factor as it concerns reaching out to a broad audience and ensuring that everybody can afford these services (Salawudeen, 2010). The operating or running cost of ICT infrastructures are specified, it's the exclusive preserve of the haves. For the have-not, the struggle for survival may be a top priority. A reduced number of students that are privileged to own a private computer/laptop aren't connected to the net as this do attract extra cost which they can't afford all of the time. Also, the value of accessing internet continues to be very high in Nigeria. Technology as a crucial component of online learning, isn't predictable and expensive, which makes the prices of putting it to use and maintaining it excessive (Murray, 2001; Simmons, 2003).

Unwillingness of end users to adopt online learning

Technology is critical in implementing and adopting online learning. Hence, it requires change and adjustments from all actors. Rogers's diffusion of innovation theory states that people are adopt new technology at differing rates. The determinants to accepting of technology, according to Roger (1962), include relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trainability and observability. For actors to effectively put to use online learning, they need to know how important the new technology is, how the new technology is better than the previous, the extent to which the innovation is thought to be consistent with prevailing values, how easy or difficult

the new technology or innovation is to understand, use and maintain, the extent to which the innovation can be tested before a commitment for adoption is made, and, the extent to which the innovation provides tangible results. These factors determine to a great extent the willingness of actors to adopt online learning. Online learning provides users with the ability for independent learning and most users are not interested in assuming responsibility for their own learning. The generational dynamics or dichotomy clearly provides an explanation for the willingness or unwillingness of end users to adopt online learning.

Fear of online learning technology taking over jobs

Though advancement in technology has been praised and credited for its convenience, ease of use, flexibility and speed in the accomplishment of task, ongoing debates suggest that its adoption is feared to eliminate some aspect of human work relation. A lot of institutions have fought to ensure that technology is not adopted. Without the end users embracing and supporting its usage, it will just be a done in futility. Layne and Lee (2001) argue that, as any new system become more established in an organization, the organizational structure may consequently be changed in two ways, internally and externally. The changes are likely to experience some challenges, namely, resistance to change and distrust; the technology users may become suspicious about the threat to their positions by using and adopting these new technologies (Irani and Love, 2013).

Moreover, the use of new system such as online learning may cause the actors (teachers/lecturers and students) to become resistant, since they will lose their control over traditional pedagogies (Doherty and King, 2005). Accordingly, those users, who have lost control, will try to resist the electronic learning system as it is seen as a threat to their position, control and skills (Heeks, 2002; Doherty, 2014). Indeed, resistance to change towards using technology is emerging as one of the most visible barriers in online learning success. Even if it was well aligned with the objectives of the organization or well designed with the job specifications, online learning systems are expected to fail if the users resist them (Doherty, 2014). This however depends on how these new systems and solutions are implemented in the organizational culture. If users feel that online learning creates more problems than benefits or if they simply do not know how to use it or cannot apply it to their own tasks and projects, they will not feel comfortable using what they disapprove of and will resist it. Simmons, (2003) noted that the way to resolve the resistance is to progressively create an organizational culture.

Lack of policy

New advancements in online learning technology has the ability to reduce the digital divide in public schools, provided the states give sufficient funds and political support to such programs. At the level of the government, there exist no policy formally stating and enforcing the acceptance and adoption of online learning to institutions at all levels in Nigeria, hence, the slow adoption of the learning technology. At the level of the institutions, online learning has not been entrenched in the curriculum at all educational level. Information and communication technology (ICT) are not fully integrated into the pedagogy in Nigeria (Aduwa-Ogiegbaen & and

Iyamu 2005). Where you have them entrenched in the curriculum of an institution, it is to help market or it is used as a market strategy to increase the publicity and in turn increase the intake of students.

Since the challenges associated with online learning are complex in Nigeria, the major actors (government and educational institutions) must make use of a myriad of potential solutions in reducing the inequalities that exist. While access to technology remains important, lack of access, lack of online learning infrastructure and other key challenges must be addressed and solutions proffered.

Bridging the Online Learning Disparity/Gap in Nigeria

From time immemorial, there has been an educational gap and more recently the online learning disparity in Nigeria. This has been defined in terms of people who have access to information and communications technology for learning and those who do not have access. Access to the internet and information and communications technology is an aspect of disparity, other factors such as affordability, quality of connection and other related services, availability of infrastructure, and skills are inherent issues propagating disparity. These issues are however complex and debatable. According to OCED (2000 p9), the introduction of information and communications technology in learning have important home and global repercussion especially in the context of existing inequalities. In a country like Nigeria, the problem of educational stratification, segregation and inequalities are central and are deeply rooted in demographic, economic and cultural divides. It has therefore become imperative to promote equity in educational opportunities, hence bridging the online learning gap.

In bridging the online learning disparity in Nigeria, all or relevant stakeholders' (government, academia, civil society) must be involved in making decisions. The government as the apex institution in the society, must take the lead by adopting electronic/online tools in governance. This in no doubt will heighten the electronic readiness and project her as supporting the establishment and acceptance of information and Communication technology in her affairs and other spheres of the society. Furthermore, when policies are adopted, they must address the local content (that is, how the new technology can be situated in the one present in the society) and diversities (economic, social, demographic, geographical). Also, government must ensure equitable access and empowerment, adopt realistic approach; build capacity as well as partnership networks.

Another aspect that needs to be addressed is the cost and affordability of ICT. Studies have shown that, over 40 percent of the global population do not have the opportunity to learn using a computer. Though there has been gradual acceptance of technology for shopping, the acceptance of same technology for education is still farfetched. Increased access does not necessarily leads to cyber equality. Hence, in order to bridge the online learning gap in Nigeria, adequate funding of the education sector must be ensured to cut across all the divides (gender, socio-economic status, geographical among others). It is important to note that, the financial aspect must form a major part of the educational equity gap policy and budgetary allocation yearly (Obor, 2019).

Theoretical Framework

Conflict Theory

Karl Marx, a foremost conflict theorist, posited that the usefulness of social institutions could best be seen within the economic structure in which they operated. For Marx, every society is divided into two distinct classes that is, the class of the bourgeoisie, the haves; and the class of the proletariat, the haves not. Marx opined that social institutions exist to serve the interest of the bourgeoisie at the expense of the proletariat through what he called “the ruling class hegemony”. In every typical capitalist society, the bourgeoisie through the existing social institutions dictate how society is to be run for their own interest. Conflict theorists do not hold positive views of the roles that the educational system performs in society. For conflict theorists, the educational system exists to serve the interest of the powerful group in society. Education helps to maintain and justifies the power, privileges and wealth of the powerful group.

According to the American Sociologists, Bowles and Ginitis, in (Haralabos and Holborn, 2013), there is an association between education and the workplace. For them, schooling is subservient to the needs of those who control the workforce that is, those who own means of production. According to Bowles and Ginitis, schooling operates “a closed curriculum”. The closed curriculum incorporates things that pupils and students learn through experience while attending school rather than the stated educational objectives of schools. The hidden curriculum has the followings as its assumptions:

The educational system produces subservient workforce who are uncritical and passive, they are docile, unimaginative, unquestioning and easily manipulated by employers.

2. The educational system encourages the acceptance of hierarchy. According to Bowles and Ginitis, schools are arranged in hierarchy of authority and control. Teachers issue out orders while pupils and students obey. Students have less or absent of control over the subjects that they study and how they study them. The subservient attitude is what they would eventually take to the workplace.
3. The educational system posits that teachers possess all the knowledge and they transmit this knowledge to pupils and students.
4. The educational system gives pupils and students the notion that it is only through education that they can get higher positions in society.
5. The educational system inculcates in pupils and student’s passive consumption of uncritical acceptance of the existing social order of society by its nature of discipline.

The educational system posits that education exist for the needs of the capitalist employers by providing surplus skilled labour.

The educational system also helps to legitimate the inequality that exists in the wider society. Schools in the affluent neighbourhoods are found to have facilities and amenities

that aid good education. Schools in affluent neighbourhoods could pay higher salaries to their staffs thereby attracting better and qualified teachers and could provide better technological equipment that aid learning.

The notion of meritocracy as posited by the functionalist theorists is an illusion according to Bowles and Ginitis. For them, the children of the wealthy and powerful tend to obtain higher qualification and highly rewarding jobs irrespective of their abilities. The educational system disguises this with its myth of ‘meritocracy’ thereby, making those who are denied success to blame themselves for their failure rather than blame the pattern that has made them become failures.

Bowles and Ginitis observed that a strong relationship between educational attainment and family background. The higher the social class of a person’s parent, the longer he or she remains in the educational system (Haralambos and Holborn, 2013 and Giddens, 2009).

Application of Conflict Theory to E-Learning in Nigeria

An e-learning mode of education involves the transmission of ideas, information, knowledge and skills using technology such as the internet, computer, Smartphone, laptops and other related electronic gadgets to a wide range of audience or recipients who live remotely from the instructor or teacher.

The novel dreaded coronavirus saw the restriction of mass gathering of people and the closure of public places including schools in a bid to halt the spread of the disease. The need for teaching and learning to continue even in the face of the global lockdown, saw the acceptance of the electronic form of education. Schools in most developed countries with the availability of facilities that aid such mode of learning keyed into it. The e-learning mode of education was also advocated in developing and underdeveloped countries as the only way learning can continue while the lockdown last, in order not to lag behind in the education of citizens of these various countries. The government of Nigeria also advocated the e-learning mode of learning for its citizens, which led some schools to adopt this mode of teaching and learning while the lockdown continued. Teachers, pupils and students who adopted the e-learning mode of learning kept the pace in education with those in developed countries. The reliance on technological gadgets and facilities that aid e-learning saw the continuity in education even in the face of the lockdown and closure of schools in Nigeria.

As good and laudable the acceptance of the electronic form of learning in Nigeria appeared to be, it does not serve the interest of all in Nigeria. The e-learning system only saw the continuity of education of the children of the rich while those of the poor were left out of education. The vast majority of pupils and students are from the poor socioeconomic background who cannot afford the electronic gadgets that aid e-learning mode of education, live in neighborhoods where poverty is endemic and there is inadequate or lack of facilities such as electricity, network connections and servers, attend schools that lack facilities and have teachers who lack the knowledge to operate e-learning education. While e-learning form education brought substantial advantages to the children of the affluent in Nigeria as they continued with the pace of learning with their global counterparts, it however led to the exclusion of the vast

majority of pupils and students who are from poor socioeconomic backgrounds as they could not access this form of learning.

The number of students from lower socio-economic class, who are currently unable to afford computers for use at home or internet connection while they are studying cannot be determined but one can assume it a vast majority. It could also be speculated that students from lower socio-economic background due to lack of money, have slower take-up of each new device or technology that comes onto the market which offers internet access. Access to online learning in a variety of ways and from a variety of devices may therefore continue to be unequally distributed on the basis of one's economic or social status.

Recommendations

The percentage of Nigerians living below poverty line currently stands at 69% and majority of Nigerian students who cannot access the e-learning form of education fall into this category. The government of Nigeria needs to do much in alleviating the poverty level of Nigerians. Government programmes on poverty alleviation should be practical and far reaching not merely on paper policy as this would help flatten the level of poverty.

Government should make effort to improve on the infrastructures of the country as the current state of infrastructure in the country reveal a great deal of decay. Facilities and amenities that facilitate teaching and learning are currently lacking or are in poor state.

The government should focus on the provision of a form of learning that guarantees equality recognizing and meeting the different educational needs of all Nigerian pupils and students.

In this age of information technology, a plan that will make citizens not just computer literate but capable of using electronic media to carry out daily functions including learning should be put in place.

For a higher performing educational system, government policies should accommodate high quality and equity. In this type of educational system, majority of students can attain high skills and knowledge that depend on their ability and drive, more than on their socioeconomic background.

Conclusion

The acceptance of the electronic form of education in Nigeria shows that technology has really transformed every aspect of human life in Nigeria, the educational system inclusive. Also, there are indications that Nigerians can keep pace with their global counterparts as pertaining learning in the midst of challenges such as the one posed by dreaded coronavirus pandemic that resulted in global lockdown and closure of schools. However, there still remains the issue of social exclusion of the majority of poor Nigerians who cannot access this form of education. The exclusion of majority of Nigerian pupils and students from the e-learning mode of education has been brought to bear in this paper. The issue of inequality, which engenders the broad gap

between the rich and the poor in Nigeria, has also brought to bear government's lack of commitment toward improving the lots of Nigerians through the provision of basic facilities and amenities that improve the life and wellbeing of Nigerians. It is made evident in this study that much is needed to be done in alleviating the poverty that is ravaging majority of Nigerians.

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ADMINISTRATIVE EFFICIENCY, ACCOUNTABILITY, PRINCIPALS' UTILIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES AS CORRELATES OF INTERNAL EFFICIENCY OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Expenditure on public secondary education is largely regarded as an investment which required continuous appraisal to ensure the functionality of the system. On a contrary, there are elements of inefficiency in the operation of secondary schools in Nigeria. The problem of low productivity of educational products is a great concern to stakeholders in education sector. This study, therefore investigated principals' administrative efficiency, accountability and educational resources utilization as correlates of public secondary school internal efficiency in Ogun State, Nigeria.

This study used a descriptive survey design. One thousand two hundred and seventy-three (1273) respondents participated in the study, and were selected through a multi-stage sampling technique, which include simple random technique and convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using four adapted instruments. They were Administrative Efficiency Inventory (0.891), Accountability Scale (0.788), Educational Resources Utilization Questionnaire (0.812), and Internal Efficiency Scale (0.763). The three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, while data were analyzed using of descriptive statistics (means, standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Pearson Product Moment Correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis).

Results indicated significant positive relationships between administrative efficiency and internal efficiency ($r = .209, p = .01 < .05$), resources utilisation and internal efficiency ($r = .097, p = .01 < .05$), while accountability and internal efficiency ($r = -.019, p < .05$) were negatively correlated. All the predictor variables (Resources utilisation, Accountability, Administrative efficiency) jointly predicted internal efficiency of public secondary schools in Ogun state ($R = .143; R^2 = .020; \text{Adj. } R^2 = .018; F_{(3, 1249)} = 8.654; p = .000 < .05$); while the most potent predictor

of internal efficiency among the predictor variables of the study is resources utilization ($\beta = .195$; $t = 5.027$; $p = .000 < .05$), followed by accountability ($\beta = .098$; $t = 2.996$; $p = .003 < .05$), and lastly by administrative efficiency ($\beta = .081$; $t = 2.333$; $p = .020 < .05$).

It was recommended that the facilities available in the institutions should be improved upon in order to accommodate more students. Additionally, there is an urgent need for an inter-sectoral budget restructuring to release more resources for education this will go a long way in meeting both students and teachers requirement for effective service delivery in improving the school system efficiency.

Keywords: Accountability, administrative efficiency, educational resources, internal efficiency utilisation, public secondary school

INTRODUCTION

Education has been referred to as the cornerstone of all societies and a means of fostering national development throughout the world. In all human societies, education is also considered as a tool that promotes advancement and diversification in the fields of economics, social studies, politics, and technology. It is noteworthy that education encompasses more than just teaching students how to read and write; it also serves as a tool for fostering a positive mindset and character in each person, which is essential for the advancement and development of nation-building.

The foundation for moving on to higher education is secondary education. It acts as an essential link between primary and postsecondary education. Secondary education serves the dual purposes of "producer" (supplying input to the tertiary level of education) and "consumer" (absorbing the output from the primary level of education) (Obi & Ogbuagu, 2020). Given the benefits of a secondary school education, it is imperative to preserve these institutions' internal efficacy. According to Korir et al. (2023), internal efficiency in an educational setup is the relationship between inputs and the yield of the system, or the input-to-output rate.

An internally efficient educational system produces graduates from secondary school without wasting any student years, repeaters, or dropouts. If the graduates don't meet the needs of the economy, society, or higher education, Olanipekun (2018) claims that the system may be outwardly highly inefficient. Afolabi (2016) emphasized that even in the event of a decrease in input level, the output generated from a given quantity of inputs may be increased or maintained at the same level. This suggests that the process of using the fewest inputs to maximize output is known as internal efficiency. Internal efficiency, according to Ileuma (2017) and Maimbolwa (2019), can be assessed by looking at completion, dropout, repetition, and transition and promotion rates. Additionally, cycle completion and survival rates at specific grade levels as well as cycle-to-cycle transfer rates are included in the definition of efficiency.

Education stakeholders are deeply concerned about the issue of educational waste at the secondary school level, which can lead to a high failure rate in public exams (Akinsolu, 2012). When an investment fails to provide the anticipated profit or product, or when the outcome is

deemed to be less than the intended value, it is deemed to be a waste and a sign of internal inefficiency.

According to Akinsolu (2012), funding determines how much is allocated for secondary education services. Despite the large sums of money invested in education, the productivity of educational products appears to be low. Although anecdotal observations of secondary school operations in Nigeria reveal some inefficiencies in the system. Nigerians expect the secondary school system to be efficient in the sense that a given quantity of output is obtained with minimum input (Olanipekun, 2018). Wastage was occurring in the public secondary school as a result of the majority of students repeating classes, dropping out, and the rising percentage of failed students (Olatoun, 2016). Students' recent decline in desire for achievement and transition to postsecondary institutions indicates that the goals of secondary education have not been fully achieved, as evidenced by the system waste experienced.

In fulfillment of secondary school education objectives, it is obvious that principal's administrative efficiency cannot be over-emphasized. Administrative efficiency in the context of this study can be described as the process of ensuring that things are getting done at the right and appropriate time by the administrator of an organisation. According to Inter-state School Leadership Consortium (2014) in Enwezor (2021), administrative efficiency relates to the standards for what the school leaders should know and are able to do. According to Enwezor (2021), administrative efficiency refers to how well secondary school principals accomplish the aims and objectives of their institutions. Operationally, administrative efficiency is the result of positive administrative actions and efforts directed toward the achievement of the specified objective.

Administrative efficiency is defined as the degree of integration, output, drive (high motivation), teacher turnover, utilization of resources to the fullest, individual potential maximization, and significant contribution to society (Manafa, 2020). According to Manafa (2020), there are other signs of a well-run secondary school, such as positive behavior from staff and students, students and teachers attending classes during school hours, a significant decrease in exam malpractice, the maintenance of all school records, high performance on secondary certificate exams, the principal's exemplary leadership, a clean school environment, and parents lining up to get their kids admitted.

In order to create an effective secondary school administration, principals occasionally take on the role of agents and enhance school administration. For example, Chukwubueze (2022) claimed that the school curriculum will be useless and pointless if necessary facilities are not provided in an acceptable quantity and quality at the appropriate times through the principal's administrative skill. He went on to say that proficiency in managing various facets of the educational system is a prerequisite for efficient facilities management. In order to accomplish the goals set forth by the school system and maintain appropriate accountability, the aforementioned calls for the principal to possess the necessary skills to establish necessary objectives, oversee facility usage, create procurement strategies, and guarantee actual management and supervision of available facilities.

Accountability is synonymous with responsibility and it involves giving feedback to the appropriate authority. In the case of secondary school education, the school principals are accountable to the critical stakeholders in the education sector such as parents, governments, students, employers of labour, and the larger society, etc. To Eze and Onwudinjo (2021) accountability implies responsibility and answerability, which means any person given a job to do should be responsible or accountable for the successful execution of the job.

The use of educational resources, the amount of learning occurring, and the effectiveness and efficiency of the educational system are all considered aspects of accountability in education. Federal, state, and local educational policymakers, parents, and taxpayers use it as a tool to keep an eye on how well students and schools are performing (Eze & Onwudinjo, 2021; Odei-Tettey et al., 2019; Alumode & Onuma, 2016). Accountability is a process that helps actors fulfill their obligations and accomplish their objectives (Global Education Monitoring Report, 2018). With respect to legal, political, social, or moral grounds, people or organizations are required to give a detailed account of how they fulfilled their explicit obligations. Accountability, therefore, does not easily rest with single actors.

For secondary schools' education to fulfill its stated goals, aims, and objectives, the place of resource utilisation is very vital and it cannot be undermined and /or jettisoned. The even distribution of resources among the end users (that is the students and the teachers) is one of the areas expected of the school principals to give an account of their stewardship to the authorities on regular basis.

According to Ugwuanyi (2013) in Umeozor (2019), utilization is just the teacher's real use of the school's resources, tools, and facilities when they are instructing. Utilization is the process of using the resources that are at one's disposal. According to Umeozor (2019), utilisation is the state in which something satisfies a stated or implicit need to the fullest extent possible. It also refers to how resources are used to produce positive outcomes. When schools have an adequate supply of resources, teachers are satisfied with the way they can use them to teach, and they are assured of giving their best effort when utilizing the resources in the classroom.

One of the main factors influencing the quality of education provided in educational institutions is the use of resources for learning. Principals of secondary schools have a crucial role to play in the efficient management of these frequently scarce resources by implementing a resource management strategy that is in line with the goals and objectives of the entire school community (Likoko et al., 2023). This is very difficult, particularly in secondary schools where there are a lot of students, a growing diversity of cultural backgrounds, wide income gaps between households, and special learning requirements and skills.

According to Akinsolu (2012), stakeholders expect secondary school managers to use the limited educational resources wisely in order to ensure that students remain enrolled in the system for the minimum number of years required, thereby promoting high system efficiency and minimizing waste. Meanwhile, the quality of education is negatively impacted by ongoing resource shortages in schools (Mayake, 2019). Teachers may purposefully, carelessly, or as a

result of a lack of technical expertise abuse the physical and material resources in the school. Inadequate planning may also lead to overuse and neglect of school facilities (Usman, 2016).

In light of this, the study posits that establishing a relationship between genders and the independent variables will yield unique insights not found in previous research, particularly concerning the potential gender-specific effects of principals' administrative effectiveness, accountability, and use of educational resources on the internal efficiency of public secondary schools. Thus, this study investigated principals' administrative efficiency, accountability and educational resources utilisation as correlates of public secondary school internal efficiency in Ogun State, Nigeria.

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship among principals' administrative efficiency, accountability, educational resources utilisation, and public secondary school internal efficiency in Ogun State, Nigeria
- Ho₂: There is no significant composite contribution of principals' administrative efficiency, accountability and educational resources utilisation in the prediction of public secondary school internal efficiency in Ogun State, Nigeria
- Ho₃: There is no significant relative contribution of principals' administrative efficiency, accountability and educational resources utilisation in the prediction of public secondary school internal efficiency in Ogun State, Nigeria

METHOD AND MATERIALS

Research Design: The descriptive survey research design was used for this study. The survey research design is appropriate for this study because it enables the researcher to collect data on the identified research problem and report the way things are without manipulating any of the variables of interest in the study. This design also enables the participants the opportunity to express their opinions, attitudes, and perceptions on the variables of the study.

Population: The population consisted of three hundred and thirty-four (334) principals and eight thousand two hundred and fifteen (8,215) teachers in public senior secondary schools in Ogun State (Ogun State Teaching Service Commission, 2023).

Sample and Sampling Techniques: Sixty-seven (67) public senior secondary school principals and one thousand two hundred and thirty-three (1,233) teachers constituted the sample of the study. This study adopted multisampling techniques. In the first stage, 20% of principals were randomly selected from disarticulated public senior secondary schools and combined public senior secondary schools in the four (4) divisions (Remo, Ijebu, Yewa, and Egba) in Ogun State.

This amounted to 3 principals from disarticulated and 4 principals from combined public senior secondary schools in Remo, 10 principals from disarticulated and 9 principals from combined public senior secondary schools in Ijebu, 11 principals from disarticulated and 10 principals from combined public senior secondary schools in Yewa and 11 principals from disarticulated and 9 principals from combined public senior secondary schools in Egba which makes a total of 67 principals from Ogun State.

In the second phase, 15% of teachers from combined and disarticulated public senior secondary schools in Ogun State's four divisions (Remo, Ijebu, Yewa, and Egba) were chosen using a straightforward random sampling technique. This resulted to 98 teachers (from 3 schools) from disarticulated and 113 teachers (from 4 schools) from combined public senior secondary schools in Remo, 149 teachers (from 10 schools) from disarticulated and 88 teachers (from 9 schools) from combined public senior secondary schools in Ijebu, 158 teachers (from 11 schools) from disarticulated and 141 (from 10 schools) teachers from combined public senior secondary schools in Yewa and 287 teachers (from 11 schools) from disarticulated and 200 teachers (from 9 schools) from combined public senior secondary schools in Egba to make a sum of 1233 teachers and 67 public senior secondary schools from Ogun State.

Moreover, a convenience sampling method was used to collate the senior secondary students' unified promotional examination of SS 1 students and SS 2 students for five (5) consecutive academic sessions from 2017/2018, 2018/2019, 2019/2020, 2020/2021 and 2021/2022 respectively to ascertain their level of academic performance which is part of schools' internal efficiency. Mathematics and English Language are the two core subjects collated from the respective secondary schools.

Instrumentation: The following four instruments were used for data collection in this study:

Administrative Efficiency Questionnaire: Administrative Efficiency of secondary school principals was measured using Administrative Efficiency Questionnaire developed by Akomolafe (2012). The questionnaire consisted of 19 items. The items are measured using a 4-point likert scale with the rating scale of Strongly Agreed-4 points; Agreed-3 Points; Disagreed-2 points; and Strongly Disagreed-1 points. It was subjected to pilot testing in secondary schools which the current study did not cover in the study sample, hence the reliability co-efficient of 0.891 was calculated showing that the questionnaire and consistent in measuring what it is supposed to measure.

Accountability Questionnaire: Accountability of secondary school Principals was measured using Accountability Questionnaire. Questionnaires developed by Familusi (2016) and Ojekudo (2019) to measure principal's accountability in secondary schools was adapted for the study. The researcher modified three of the eleven items in the Familusi (2016) questionnaire for this investigation. Additionally, six items were modified from the fourteen items in the Ojekudo (2019) questionnaire. Hence, the Accountability Questionnaire consist of 9 items. The items are measured using a 4-point Likert rating scale of High Extent (4); Moderate Extent (3); Low Extent (2); and Very Low Extent (1) respectively. For the questionnaires, Familusi (2016)

reported a positive reliability co-efficient of 0.65 and Ojekudo (2019) reported 0.75 reliability co-efficient.

Educational Resources Utilisation Questionnaire: Educational Resources Utilisation Questionnaire was measured using school facilities availability and utilisation checklist developed by Esongo (2017). The instrument consists of 23 items and it was adapted for this study. It was measured using 4-point Likert rating scale of Adequately/Always Utilized (A/AU), Utilized (U), Rarely Utilized (RU) and Not Utilized (NU) for School Facilities Utilisation. For the scale, cronbach's alpha of 0.797 was reported by Esongo (2017).

Internal Efficiency Inventory (IEI): This instrument was adapted from the work of Muhammad (2014). The instrument was designed to measure the internal efficiency of secondary schools. It was used to collect public secondary data on students' enrolment, repetition and dropout of SS1 and SS2 students for five academic sessions (2017/2018, 2018/2019, 2019/2020, 2020/2021 and 2021/2022). The instrument is standardized based on percentage rating to determine the school internal efficiency on aforementioned students' data.

Template for Collating the Students' Academic Performance: This was a self-design template by the researcher. It is to be used in collating the students' academic performance (Mathematics and English Language) in the unified promotional examinations conducted by the State Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology. This is to ascertain the level of academic attainment of the students in five academic sessions ranging from 2017/2018, 2018/2019, 2019/2020, 2020/2021 and 2021/2022. The school principals are to populate this current study template with academic results of the students from senior secondary schools one to two (SS 1 and SS 2) respectively in the trend of the sessions in question. The school principals are also expected to sign their signature on the template and also put an official stamp to validate the template.

Method of Data Collection: The head of the Department of Educational Management and Business Studies (EMBS) provided the researcher with a letter of introduction, which she used to approach the chairman of the Teaching Service Commission for permission to conduct the study in each of the chosen secondary schools. Training for the research assistants involved in the study took place during the first week. An instrument administration course was completed by three (3) research assistants. The instruments were distributed by the researcher and her helpers as they visited each of the chosen schools. The instrument was administered and data was gathered over the course of three weeks. The administration was done on the participants in their place of work.

Method for Data Analysis: Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data gathered for this investigation. The Internal Efficiency Inventory results were converted to standard scores (Z-scores) because each school used a different set of rubrics to grade the results. In order to eliminate the decimal fractions and negative values that appeared, the Z-scores were further converted to T-scores. This simplified the process of using SSPS. The study's guiding hypotheses were analyzed using multiple linear regression for hypotheses two through five and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation for hypothesis one at the 0.5 level of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Relationship between Principal's administrative efficiency, accountability, utilisation of educational resources and internal efficiency

	Administrative efficiency	Accountability	Resources utilisation	Internal Efficiency
Administrative Efficiency	1	.255**	.585**	.209**
Accountability		1	.517**	-.019
Resources Utilisation			1	.097**
Internal Efficiency				1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 revealed significant results. Specifically, there were significant positive relationships between administrative efficiency and accountability ($r = .225, p = .01 < .05$), principal's administrative efficiency and resources utilisation ($r = .585, p = .01 < .05$), administrative efficiency and internal efficiency ($r = .209, p = .01 < .05$). Additionally, there were significant positive relationships between accountability and resources utilisation ($r = .517, p = .01 < .05$), resources utilisation and internal efficiency ($r = .097, p = .01 < .05$), while internal efficiency and accountability ($r = -.019, p < .05$) were negatively correlated.

Table 2: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis of the joint contribution of principal's administrative efficiency, accountability, utilisation of educational resources in the prediction of internal efficiency

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	611.570	3	203.857	8.654	.000 ^b
Residual	29421.188	1249	23.556		
Total	30032.758	1252			

$R = .143, R^2 = .020, \text{Adj. } R^2 = .018, \text{SE} = 4.853$

a. Dependent Variable: Internal efficiency

b. Predictors: (Constant), Resources utilisation, Accountability, Administrative efficiency

Results presented in Table 2 show that when all of the predictor variables (resource utilization, accountability, and the administrative efficiency of the principal) were included in the regression model, the internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun State was jointly predicted ($R = .143; R^2 = .020; \text{Adj. } R^2 = .018; F(3, 1249) = 8.654; p = .000 < .05$). This

demonstrated that the internal efficiency variability of public senior secondary schools was explained by all predictor variables in 14.3% of cases. This finding refuted the null hypothesis, which said that a principal's administrative efficiency, accountability, and use of educational resources do not significantly contribute to the prediction of internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun state. This implies that there is a significant joint contribution of resources utilisation, accountability, administrative efficiency on internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun state.

Table 3: Coefficients of the relative contribution of principal's administrative efficiency, accountability, utilisation of educational resources in the prediction of internal efficiency

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	25.129	1.640		15.323	.000
Accountability	.110	.037	.098	2.996	.003
Resources utilisation	.264	.053	.195	5.027	.000
Administrative efficiency	.072	.031	.081	2.333	.020

a. Dependent Variable: Internal efficiency

The strength of the predictor variable's causal relationship with the criterion variable was shown by the results in Table 3. Among the predictor variables in the study, resource utilisation has the strongest correlation with internal efficiency ($\beta = .195$; $t = 5.027$; $p = .000 < .05$). In the prediction of internal efficiency, accountability is the next powerful factor ($\beta = .098$; $t = 2.996$; $p = .003 < .05$), followed by the administrative efficiency of the principal ($\beta = .081$; $t = 2.333$; $p = .20 < .05$). This result disproved the hypothesis that the internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun State could be predicted by the principal's administrative effectiveness, accountability, and use of educational resources. This suggests that the internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools is significantly influenced by the administrative effectiveness, accountability, and use of educational resources by the principal. Internal efficiency was found to be the most powerful predictor of the three.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The outcome of the first hypothesis revealed significant positive relationships between internal efficiency and principal's administrative efficiency, internal efficiency and resources utilisation while internal efficiency and accountability were negatively correlated. The results on the positive relationship between internal efficiency and principal's administrative efficiency. It is believed that the effective functioning of the school depends largely on principals' efforts that extend beyond formal role requirements. It is imperative that leaders of every organisation should showcase a leadership behaviour that promotes wholesome traits of survival and competitive advantage because majority of the outcomes on this subject of discussion as revealed in the literatures showed that exemplary leadership plays significant roles in determining

organisational success (Richford, 2020; Liderlik, 2019). This is liken to the position of Ngari (2020) that internal efficiency has to do with the input and output ratio in a given system.

The result that shows a positive association between internal efficiency and resources utilisation. The reason for this attention could have been as a result of the key role the school head plays in harnessing all things together by creating a viable network among every stakeholders, and thus, achieving the overall organisational goals. It is hypothetically believed that if the school has a viable collaborative culture by showcasing an enriched and valuable belief, values and behavior patterns, then it will continue to turnout a better output and productivity. Thus, this study complements the research of Kolawole and Ogbiye (2020); Ileuma (2017) on the quantity and quality of teachers in addition to school variables like funding, classroom and school sizes, etc., which have been demonstrated to raise internal school efficiency when provided adequately. Furthermore, this study supports the findings of Ayodele and Adeleke's (2015) investigation into the "internal efficiency of public and private secondary schools in Ekiti State," which showed that the state's secondary schools had low rates of dropout and repetition, indicating a fairly efficient internal structure.

The results that revealed the negative relationship between internal efficiency and accountability. It is a little surprising, as the principal is usually the chief financial officer and executive charged with overseeing the school's revenue collection and making sure the PTA levy and other funds are used wisely. In addition, the principals' formal positions within the schools give them legitimacy for their authority, and school governing bodies hold them responsible for their actions. This result is in contrast to that of Iwerebor and Imarhiagbe (2022) and Oboegbulem (2013), who conducted investigations and found that principals, in their capacity as chief accounting officers of their respective secondary schools, are responsible for raising funds internally and making sure that funds contributed by stakeholders are appropriately recorded. Additionally, he discovered that school administrators are well-versed in the proper accounting practices established by the Ministry of Education and Post Primary Schools Board. They thoroughly review payment vouchers, bills, and account books to ensure the accuracy of the information before signing them. In a similar line, Bua and Adzongo (2014) discovered that principals are in charge of overseeing all aspects of school administration, including financial planning, budget creation, accounting for all petty funds received by the school, revenue from events, and any other documentation that needs to be properly maintained.

The outcome of the second hypothesis revealed that all the predictor variables (resources utilisation, accountability, principal's administrative efficiency) jointly predicted internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun state. It was further showed that all the predictor variables accounted for about 18% variance observed in the internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools. This implies that there are other factors within the school system apart from resources utilisation, accountability and administrative efficiency that predicts internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools. As a result, a major determinant of the internal efficiency of schools is the planning and management of those institutions by school administrators. This is consistent with the measures of a school's internal efficiency that have been found by Okinyi et al. (2021), Kolawole and Ogbiye (2020), Dufitumukiza (2020), Ibrahim (2018), and Ileuma (2017). These measures include enrollment, completion or graduation, and

dropouts or repeaters rates. Cohort analysis, which illustrates the pattern of student flow by gender and includes information on promotion, repetition, and dropout rates, is used to assess the internal efficiency of the educational system (Iwerebor & Imarhiagbe, 2022).

The third hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relative contribution of principal's administrative efficiency, accountability, principals' utilisation of educational resources in the prediction of internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun State cannot be sustained. The results revealed the strength of causation of the predictor variables on the criterion variable. The most potent predictor of internal efficiency was resources utilisation followed by accountability, and principal's administrative efficiency. It can be deduced therefore that resources utilisation will not only help the schools to achieve their goals at a given time, but it could help to reduce wastage of the available resources.

In this case, the use of resources has a positive and advantageous influence on school productivity. One plausible explanation is that the resources under the institution's control have a significant impact on the caliber of its output, which is students' academic achievement. When school resources are used effectively, the educational process is facilitated, teacher and student morale is raised, the institution's value is determined, the school's community relations are impacted, and the school serves as a cultural, civic, recreational, and youth center. Physical resources are the major factors contributing to internal efficiency. This corroborate the findings of Akinnubi and Oladimeji (2021) who in their study found out that the institutions' physical facilities has a direct influence on students' grades at the end of the semester/ academic session, which is an indicator of internal efficiency in the institutions.

The result on the accountability is supported by the findings of Ozen, Iscan, and Paltan (2017) who investigated the impact of school-based accountability on secondary school efficiency in Turkey. The results showed that accountability positively influenced school efficiency in terms of student achievement, teacher performance, and resource allocation. This is also supported by the findings of Gavish and Friedman (2017) who investigated the relationship between accountability policies and secondary school performance in Israel. The findings showed that accountability policies positively affected school performance. These findings are in line with Oboegbulem (2013) and Ojekudo (2020) who in their investigations revealed that principals as chief accounting officers of their respective secondary schools are to generate funds internally to run their schools, they ensure that funds provided by stakeholders are properly accounted for. Therefore, accountability is one of the core determinants of every organisation's success as it influences organisation's internal efficiency.

The outcome of the findings of the influence of the principal's administrative efficiency on internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools in Ogun State was confirmed by this study. It is a real fact that principal's administrative efficiency is the key to creating a viable network among every stakeholder in academia. Thus, Overstreet (2017) in his study sees efficient leaders as those whose behaviour and practice are to build collaborative culture that put together the interest of everyone for team building and achievement of common goal. Also, Chew *et al* (2018) re-emphasized the fact that the principal's administrative efficiency of building collaborative culture, which promotes the career and job commitment of every members

of staff in order to enhance work engagement, knowledge sharing, and capacity building in achieving common goals. The studies by Louis and Robinson (2012) and Uwannah et al (2022) supported the significance of having leaders with a distinct vision and a comprehension of their instructors and significant others within the school. Principals cannot influence teachers' capacity to change their practices or their dedication to pursuing goals without a clear educational vision.

The advantage of hypothesis three's findings is that they suggest that a principal's use of educational resources, accountability, and administrative effectiveness may act as catalysts for beneficial changes in secondary school education, improving efficacy and efficiency, addressing the needs of the school culture, and meeting the needs for innovative approaches to secondary school management and accountability. Actually, a principal's positive and relative contribution to administrative effectiveness, accountability, and resource utilization will help schools advance their standing as professionals and gain more organizational authority.

CONCLUSIONS

According to this study, the most important factor influencing the internal efficiency of public senior secondary schools is how well their resources are used. The results of this study have also demonstrated the importance of resource utilization in enhancing public senior secondary schools' internal efficiency. The utilization of educational resources is important because it contributes to the accomplishment of learning objectives and goals. The utilisation of educational resources may have an impact on how well an educational institution meets its goals. What matters is not the quantity of resources allotted, but rather the efficiency with which the existing resources are applied to further the advancement of education. Within this framework, educational resources encompass both time and tangible assets, including buildings such as classrooms, labs, libraries, staff offices, and dorms; equipment such as internet access, power sources, and various visual and audio-visual devices; computers and printers; photocopier machines, etc.

Accountability is the second potent factor of the study predicting internal efficiency. In the educational system, it strengthens the checks and balances, allowing for the recognition and improvement of conformities and the prompt and appropriate identification, sanctioning, and correction of nonconformities. Accountability in the educational system has been observed to support administrators' steadfast pursuit of learning objectives and guard against misappropriation of public monies. Better teaching and learning occur in the classroom when there is educational accountability. It prevents the misappropriation of public resources, including money.

The study offers a foundation for understanding how the internal efficiency of secondary schools is impacted by the administrative effectiveness of the principal. Today, administrative effectiveness of the principal raises student achievement across the globe. The data indicates that the administrative efficacy of senior secondary school principals in public schools is primarily focused on function delegation, decision-making, meeting organization, communication cues, staff motivation and requests, safeguarding school property, financial management, and building strong relationships. Conversely, the administrative efficacy of principals in private secondary

schools is primarily focused on teacher supervision, enforcing rules and regulations, and admission methods. The results showed that a rise in the independent variables would raise the public secondary school's internal efficiency.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The facilities available in the institutions should be improved upon in order to accommodate more students. This would, in no small measure, reduce the pressure on the existing physical resource of the schools in Nigeria. Also, schools should admit only those students that they can cater for in terms of facilities utilisation so that the available facilities would not be over utilized. This would reduce incessant breakdown of these facilities.
- ii. Concerted efforts should be made to reduce student wastage rate to the barest minimum by ensuring that admission is based more on merit. When admission is based more on merit, issues of student drop out and student repetition would be efficiently and effectively managed. Those admitted would be capable of facing academic challenges which would help in achieving high graduation rate and the development of the country.
- iii. To increase access, engagement, and retention and allow students to continue their education, education planners and managers must fortify the monitoring and assessment systems in schools.

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